

“A Critical Analysis of the Training and Development Programme of the Bangladesh Bank and Developing a Guideline to Enhance the Programme”

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Abbreviations

ATM	Automated Teller machines
BACS	Banks Automated Clearing System and Access
BB	Bangladesh Bank
CCCL	Cheque and Credit Clearing Company Limited
VaR	Value at Risk
BBTA	Bangladesh Bank Training Academy
BPR	Business Process Reengineering
EE	Employee Engagement
BI	Business Intelligence
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ROI	Return on Investment
EI	Employee Involvement
BSC	Balanced Score Card
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
SHRM	Strategic Human Resource Management
RBV	Resource Based View
SWOT	Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technology, Legal and Environment
MVIS	Minimum Viable Innovation System

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Abstract

BB is the regulatory body of the country's banking system, so it is necessary that the programs related to training and development regarding non-technical and non-financial perspectives like leadership, must be effective to provide a clear and effective guideline to other banks to bring efficiency in their performances as well. BB is a role model for all the banks of Bangladesh as it is empowered by the government of Bangladesh and one of its prime aim is to ensure an effective guideline of training and development that brings efficiency in the banking system that is in place within the country. This study is very crucial for organisational performance because employees play a vital role as significant assets of the organisation who can work better and enhance the organisational productivity. Organisation cannot achieve its organisational goals and objectives without educating their employees about their duties and responsibilities. The primary aim of this research was to investigate the effectiveness of the current training programs of BB and develop guidelines for further addition in the programs. The literature was gathered through secondary sources which include official training programs source of BB, relevant journals to the chosen non-technical programs and relevant books. The researcher also used primary research, gathered by doing interviews with senior officials of different banks in Bangladesh and by conducting survey. In the survey only, knowledge workers were contacted to make the result reliable and useful to achieve the objectives. The findings showed that majority programs of BB are not effective and need to be revised by using the guideline, formed after thorough analysis of secondary as well as primary data. This research targeted selected non-technical areas of training programs and opens door for further research on remaining non-technical areas. There is no pinpoint research has been done on this topic, so this research will contribute in existing literature relevant to the identified 12 areas in training and development programs of BB. The managerial contribution of this study is exclusive as the formulated guidelines in this research can be used by BB to bring improvements in its training and development programs. As the guideline covers all important information regarding the identified non-technical as well non-financial areas of the actual manual of BB which is not only helpful for BB in bringing improvements in its program but also enhance the knowledge of readers specifically to the 12 identified areas. It can also be used by other banks in different countries to use it as a benchmark.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Smith (1996) stated that training is a planned process of modifying employees' attitude, behaviour, knowledge and skills through an organised learning experience in order to enhance the effectiveness of their performance and productivity. Armstrong (2012) defined training as the systematic development of the knowledge, skills and attitudes of an individual in order to perform effectively. Over the last three decades, employee training and development has emerged as a significant edifying subject. This substantial rise is concomitant with a demand in the workplace for employees to improve their performance. The improvement involves developing their personal and professional skills, behaviour and attitude so that they are capable enough to successfully accomplish their given tasks.

Training and development help the employees at all levels to develop their performance in the current job to obtain knowledge and skills to be able to complete new tasks and continue to progress with their career in a rapidly changing and highly competitive world of work. Many organisations advocate that people are the key to many successful business functions. It is becoming gradually clear that no human organisation can succeed without skilled and well-trained human resource. Reilly (1987) mentioned that continuous employee development programme is very critical for both short and long-term success of any profit or non-profit business organisation.

1.2 Research Background

BB is the central bank of Bangladesh. It is the supreme regulatory body of the country's monetary and financial system. BB was founded just after the born of Bangladesh in 1972. BB is currently possessed 6000 employees and operating from 10 different branches. BB is responsible for the formulation and implementation of monetary and credit policies. The bank is also responsible for the regulation and supervision of banks and non-bank financial institutions, promotion and development of domestic financial markets. BB is the management of country's international reserves and also the issuer of currency notes. BB regularly supervise the payment system and acting as the banker of the government. One of the most significant roles of BB is to work effectively for the money laundering prevention. They are also involved in collecting and furnishing of credit information. BB implements foreign exchange regulation Act. They are responsible for implementing and managing an effective deposit insurance

scheme. The main function of BB is to supply money to the country, but it is also responsible for controlling the loan interest rates. BB is important than commercial bank because it is fully responsible for controlling and generating currency for the country.

BB is also accountable to ensure that all the banks and financial institutions are complying according to the country's compliance regulations. There are various laws and acts which controls the power and functions of the BB. These laws and acts include. BB order 1972, the Banker's Books Evidence Act 1891, Foreign Exchange Act 1947, Anti-Money Laundering Act 2002, Bankruptcy Act 1997 and Financial Institutions Act 1993 etc. In accordance with those laws and acts, it is the duty of BB to develop an effective training and development programs to bring effectiveness and efficiency in overall performances in daily activities, compliance, prevent frauds and other risk management perspectives like operational risk, stress management and legal risk (BB, 2018)

BB is the regulatory body of the country's banking system. Therefore, it is necessary that the programs related to training and development regarding non-technical and non-financial perspectives like leadership, must be effective to provide to clear and effective guideline to other banks to bring efficiency in their performances as well. Therefore, BB is a role model for all the banks of Bangladesh as it is empowered by the government of Bangladesh and one of its prime aim is to ensure an effective guideline of training and development that brings efficiency in banking system is in place within the country.

1.3 Rationale of the Study

This study is very crucial for organisational performance because employees play a vital role as significant assets of the organisation who can work better and enhance the organisational productivity. Organisation cannot achieve its organisational goals and objectives without educating their employees about their duties and responsibilities. Employees can get a clear view of the organisational goals and its expectations through a clear and effective training program. Pots (1998) stated that each employer spends \$30 billion on formal training and around \$180 billion on informal on-the-job training. At the current world of business, the demands of industry and commerce are significantly and constantly changing and also reflecting in the activities of the training and development programme for employees. Kumar and Siddika (2017) said that the most effective way of developing the quality and productivity of current employees by providing inclusive and effectual training. Training and development not only just increase the performance and productivity, but also increase job satisfaction and

self-confidence, escalate motivation among employees and increase the ability to adopt new technologies and systems.

According to Reilly (1987), management of public organisations in the third world countries did not make sufficient progress in terms of training and development. Many have argued that training and development is requisite tactical tool for the organisation to enrich the employees' performance and organisational productivity. Training and development program allow the employees to acquire new techniques which enhances their productivity and skills. Training and development also help the employees to develop and update their knowledge regarding their work which precisely increase the organisational and personal productivity.

Many factors such as strong market competition, high demand of effectiveness, need of efficient productivity and quality and aim to avoid the litigation etc. Human resource is the most vital resources for an organisation under extreme antagonism. Human capital can unleash their dexterousness with proper training and development programme. Kumar and Siddika (2017) argued that an intense and reflective training and development program is very vital for any organisation because it work as driver to enhance employees' skills and knowledge which enables them to become more productive and perform better.

1.4 Problem Statement

BB became the victim of one of the most successful bank robberies of all time. The cyber-attack happened because of the weakness in the BB's security and also possibly with the involvement of some of its own employees. Committers attempted to steal \$951 million from the BB's account with the Federal Reserve Bank of New York between 4-5 February in 2016. This clearly shows the flaws and weakness in IT related expertise and skills of the employees (Financial Times, 2016). There are some other compliance issues that has the BB in the recent past. This is a very crucial concern for the bank because BB is responsible for the effective banking system of the country.

As mentioned earlier, BB is empowered by the government and is responsible for checking and stopping money laundering and fraud. If the central bank of a country gets victimised by the cyber attacker, then the concern is very high for all other banks and financial activities. BB is facing several issues related to poor quality services to customers and lack of future leadership development even those banks practice management training programs, but still managerial expertise is lacking in those banks. Moreover, there are several courses related to strategic perspective like use of ERP, strategic planning, strategic human resource management in the

training and development courses but results are not satisfactory in subordinates of BB. That result seems alarming and actuates the interest to choose this topic to investigate the training and development programme of BB with the support of existing relevant literature.

It has been identified in the literature review that one of the main reasons behind this problem is lack of effectiveness in the current training and development programme of BB. This study identifies the most important sectors of BB's training and development programme which requires development.

The training and development program list cover financial, non-financial, technical and non-technical perspectives of banking industry. It is very crucial to critically evaluate the non-financial and non-technical perspectives (mentioned in the conceptual framework) of banking industry which play vital role in the successful implementation of financial and technical perspectives as well. Those non-financial and non-technical perspectives are related to business administration and justify the chosen topic for DBA thesis. For example, leadership (non-financial and non-technical) play crucial role in the development of required skills in employees to perform technical and financial activities in banks. Similarly, lack of strategic planning expertise and managing cultural expertise in partnership businesses of banks create disturbance at workplace which in return affect other financial and technical matters of banks.

1.5 Research Aims

The main of this research is to evaluate the current training and development programs of BB along with the benchmark for training and development programs for bank employees. This research study aims to conduct a critical analysis on the main issues, problems and challenges faced by the human resource development of the BB, in order to develop a new guideline for training and development in banks with incremental and innovative changes regarding non-technical and non-financial identified areas.

1.6 Research Question

- What is the current state of the training programs of BB and what are the benchmark of training and development programs in the banking industry?
- How effective are the training and development programs of the BB regarding conformity to compliance?
- What improvements can be made to enhance the effectiveness of the training programme in BB in the field of compliance regulations?

1.7 Objectives of the Study

1. To examine relevant literature on banking industry and evaluate the benchmark of the training and development in the banking industry.
2. To assess the main challenges faced by the HR of the BB and identify the primary data regarding effectiveness of the training and development programs of BB by conducting a field survey in Bangladesh.
3. To formulate a guideline for the BB with a view to enhance the effectiveness of training programme for the employees.

1.8 Structure of the research

The research consists of 6 chapters. In chapter 1, the researcher developed the background based on advanced and useful knowledge, extracted from the reliable secondary sources. The actual problem is discussed in detail which supports the purpose of this research. This chapter provides justification in the form of rationale, chosen questions and the purpose which developed credibility and reliability of this research.

In chapter 2, the researcher gathered literature which helped to answer two research questions in which the analysis of current training programs of BB and relevant literature on identified 12 non-technical programs were successfully done. In this chapter, the author tried to include all the necessary areas of the chosen non-technical and non-financial areas which are essential to be known by bank's employees to carry out the effective operational as well as managerial tasks. The author used previous relevant useful sources that includes journals and books to get the concise and useful information about all the chosen 12 areas. The gathered data helped the author in the final chapter in making guidelines for each non-technical and non-financial area after comparing with the current training programs of BB. The chapter 2 covers all the necessary advanced as well as fundamental knowledge regarding the 12 non-technical programs which assist the researcher in forming the guideline. This chapter contributes almost 70 % of the total success of this research. The survey questions were also designed according to the literature. This chapter also helped to develop the conceptual framework.

In chapter 3, the researcher did research methodology which designed the part of this research as it includes research philosophy, methods, design, strategies and data collection related techniques. This chapter also includes sample size and data measurement information that helps the readers to understand the theme of this research. The researcher also gave justification for the rejection of any method and the selection of the method.

In chapter 4, the researcher did analysis, based on primary and secondary data collected from the surveys with a view to achieve objective 3 which is the main aim of this research. This is the main chapter to support inductive research and graphical analysis method was chosen as SPSS in which graphical presentation was done through Likert Scale. The result of the interviews is also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 5 conducts a case study to understand the need of training and development programs at banks. This chapter evaluates a case study which was written on Citi Bank which is quite relevant to the selected topic for this study.

Chapter 6 covers the formulation of the guidelines of training and development programme for BB. This chapter also concludes all the research objectives as well as finding. This chapter is mainly based on inductive approach.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Training has become very challenging because of today's flat organisation and lean department. As mentioned by Green (2002) training is the assisting process to enhance an individual's personal efficiency, knowledge, abilities, and skills. Training plays an important part for the organisational growth because organisational growth and profitability closely related on the training. However, training cannot be defined as a course of organisational development. It is one of the key functions of organisational development.

The aim of training and development is to improve the individual as well as group performance which improves the organisational performance. Hackett (2004) stated that, training and development also known as different names such as employee development, human resource development, learning and development etc. Training and development are the key framework for aiding individuals so that they can develop their personal and organisational knowledge, skills, and capabilities.

This chapter begins with focusing on defining the training and development broadly. It also demonstrates the importance of training and development. Then this chapter attempts to evaluate the banking industry and different types of banks in practice followed by banking in Bangladesh. It has also attempted to indicate different types of risks involved within the banking industry. After that, this chapter pays attention on the different types of training for the banking industry and tries to identify the key benchmark for effective training and development for banks employees.

2.2 Definition of Training and Development

Training plays a very important role in this current highly competitive and challenging business world. Training is the spirit that serves the demand of eloquent and smooth functional activities of any organisation. Development is the procedure that leads employees, especially at the management level to qualitative and quantitative advancements within the organisation. Development focuses more on the advancement of knowledge, values, performance, behaviour and attitudes rather than individuals' physical skills. Development is a continuous and long-term procedure of employee development in the organisation, where training has short-term and specific goals. Nowadays, the demands of industry and commerce are constantly changing and reflecting in the training and development department. New tactic, skills, aptitudes, tasks

and new procedures requires modification of the existing training programme or developing new training programme.

Many authors have defined training and development differently. As mentioned by Armstrong (2001), training is the systematic development of knowledge, skills and attitude that required for individuals to perform the given tasks effectively. Training helps the organisation to take systematic steps for the development of their employees. Flippo (1984) stated that training is the efficient act of improving an employee's knowledge and skills for doing a specific job. Training is a set of acts which helps the organisation to increase the skills and productivity of their employees. Aswathappa (2000), described training as the process of improving employees' attitude, knowledge and productivity in order to enhance their ability of doing the required tasks effectively. Training and development are help the organisation to run its operative functions smoothly and efficiently. Smith (1996) cited that, training is the planned process of modifying employees' knowledge, skills and behavior through learning experience in order to improve their performance and achieve effective productivity. Training is the planned effort made by an organisation to assist its employees' acquiring of job-related proficiencies. These competences are knowledge, skill and behaviours which are vital for the overall success of the organisation.

The prime objective of training and development is to ensure that the employees are skilled, and a willing workforce is available for the organisation. Kulkarni (2013) discussed four major objectives of training and development. Which are individual, organisational, functional and social objectives. Organisational objective assists the organisation to achieve its desired goals by enabling individual efficiency. Individual objectives are essential to employees, because it helps them to achieve their personal goals and improve their skills which enhances their contribution to their respective organisations. Functional objectives contribute to maintain the effectiveness of organisational functions and fulfilling organisation's demands. Social objectives are responsible for ensuring organisations are complying ethically and socially responsible to the desires and confronts of the society. Training and development help the organisation to prepare both existing and new employees to meet their organisations' work standard and to prevent desuetude.

The importance and necessity of training and development cannot be ignored in this rapid changing competitive world. Effective training and development programme develop the necessary set of skills in employees which allows them to do their tasks autonomously and

productively. According to Kulkarni (2013), training for new employees is must because they need to have the knowledge and information about their job. Training helps the new employees to educate themselves about their tasks and provide an idea of the organisation's goals and expectations. Development programme helps the experienced and existing employees to further develop their skills and progress within the company. Training and development of existing employees significantly increases the productivity of an organisation as it helps the employees to gain effective knowledge and to be multi-skilled. Training and development play a substantial role in the organisation by increasing its performance and efficiency. Pots (1998) has discussed the importance of training and development programme. He mentioned that training and development programme is very crucial for the organisations as it helps them to achieve employee satisfaction. It also allows the company to maintain effectiveness and consistency with its operational activities.

2.3 Importance of Training and Development

It is argued by many researchers that the success of an organisation depends on the quality of its human resources along with money, materials and machines. In this increased competitive business domain, people become pivot around which successful organisations revolve. Organisation recognizes the training and development as an assisting and important tool that can help to gain momentum and assist people to develop themselves within the organisation. Effective and efficient work enforcement is the key to be productive, profitable and successful organisation. In order to maintain and manage an effective and efficient workplace in the organisation, it is very essential to have skilled and knowledgeable administrators. Organisation can be directed to the right direction to achieve organisational goals and objectives by the direction of skilled and proficient executives. Many organisations have been forced to opt for modernization and diversification because of the impacts of innovations, technological advancement and market driven economy. Many organisations have started to restructure the organisation. Consumerism and competitive market are also affecting and directing many organisations towards restructuring and modernization.

The environment of workforce for the managers has been changed due to the economic liberalization. Organisations have lost the protective layer long ago and they are in the age of extremely competitive business world. In this modern era competition comes from within and from the technologically highly advanced and stable organisations from the developed countries. The organisations must be preparing to accept the change and also ensure their employees are well trained and prepared to adopt the change and accept the challenges. The

employees must be well prepared, developed and updated according to the changing business environment. The success of the organisations is fundamentally determined by the effectiveness of their employees. Organisation may consider several facts in order to determine its success. Redefining the organisational goals and objectives can be crucial for the success of an organisation. Assessing the existing activities also crucial. Organisation need to consider gearing up all their resources including human resources development and technological upgradations.

Abdullah (2009) conducted a study on training and development programs of banks and found three major challenges regarding training and development. The study conducted in Bangladesh which revealed that there is a shortage of HRD professionals, inadequate knowledge workers and lack of learning environment in most of the banks in Bangladesh. The study found that there is need to develop policies for HR as well who designs training and development but without bringing improvement in HRD itself, effectiveness of training and development programs could not be achieved.

Khan et al. (2011) conducted a study and revealed that job training has positive impact on organisational performance, but design of the training and development programs is a key to success as if the programs are not designed efficiently then learning outcome would have no effect on organisational performance.

According to a study conducted by Falola et al. (2014), there is a strong relationship between training and development, employee performances and competitive advantage. However, effectiveness of training and development is essential as the management of banks should develop the programs which cover all necessary areas to get better outcome. If the management fails in developing effective programs, then it seems wastage of money and time.

Tahir et al. (2014) found in the study that training and development programs are essential, and their design must not be given in the hands of unskilled HRD. Banks must do careful selection while planning to design training and development programs. It is better to hire specialist like hire specialist of CSR to design CSR training and development program instead on relying on one individual to design all the training and development programs.

Ampomah (2016) found that there are some things that need to be considered before engaging employees in training and development programs of banks in which introductory session like conference, workshops or any formal meeting to develop interest in employees. Indeed, motivation is essential in employees to learn new skills and gain new knowledge.

Olaniyan and Lucas (2008) concluded in the study that bank's productivity and overall efficient performance are solely based on effective training and development programs of banks. It is necessary to include all the fundamental as well as advanced areas of training and development programs. In on job training, the management of a bank should hire appropriate and skilful person by assessing through various means as leadership qualities in the trainer is essential to pour knowledge in sub ordinate employees within his or her span of control.

Alton (2017) revealed that lack of appropriate and effective training and development programs de motivate employees who possess some knowledge. It is necessary that the management of banks should consult or assess the weaknesses in employee's knowledge. In fact, it is better to design the programs as per the requirement of individuals by assessing through survey or formal meetings and make a group as per required knowledge. The study revealed that motivation comes when employees feel they would learn something new as well as useful and it only comes when the designed programs are appropriate according to the individual's requirements.

In another study conducted by Driskell (2011), it was revealed that trainee expertise and skills play vital role in overall training and development program's outcomes. It is necessary to adopt suitable ways to deliver the programs as every individual learns in different ways. Such ways include learn through observations, learn through practical and learn through case study approach.

Haslinda and Mahyuddin (2009) found that lack of support for trainees could impact negatively on the learning outcome of such employees as the management must engage itself with the trainees by taking feedbacks during the training session to address the issues of the trainees.

Thompson and Prottas (2006) conducted a study to find the factors that contribute in successful training and development programs in which the author found that finding the right person by assessing the eligibility of HRD official. Training and development programs of banks must be handled by the experts.

Noe (2002) found in his study that providing training to HRD if they are not enough professional before handling them the task of making training and development programs of banks. Indeed, hiring new staff or team to do so will cost to banks higher than it could be through providing training to existing employees.

According to Guest (1997) training and development programs is a key responsibility of HR departments in companies including banks to design suitable and effective training programs that impact on overall performances of employees.

Tzafrir (2005) also asserted strongly that banks should spend time and money in developing key skills in employees through different training methods as it is necessary that training is provided to perform the tasks efficiently. Effective training and development programs have positive relationship with overall performances of banks which includes leadership development. Valle et al. (2009) found that it is necessary to develop programs with careful consideration of all the required areas which not only engender new skills and knowledge in employees but also motivate employees to attend training sessions.

Cheng and Ho (2001) discussed in the study that training and development must be designed and deliver in such a way that it enhances career growth and career potential of employees. Trainees must be aware of the learning outcome in detail before starting the training session of any specific area as it doesn't only motivate employees but also clears the path for trainees. In fact, the management can easily assess the performances of trainees and the trainees would have no excuse that they were not fully aware of the learning outcomes.

Swart et al., (2005), Concluded that due to globalization, advancement in knowledge and technologies comes by time to time which put pressure on banks to design training and development programs to keep the employees up to date by using reliable latest sources while designing. It helps to bridge the gaps between current required knowledge and the knowledge of employees.

Watson (2012), found in the study that it is not necessary that every trainee get the same required skills and knowledge through training programs of banks as capability of every individual is different. It is essential for the management to assess the capabilities of employees through various personality assessment tools and design special programs to develop learning capability in employees first.

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Ahmad and Bakar (2003) stated that training and development programs must be effective that brings employee commitment as the trainees learn as well as motivate to learn new skills by time to time when they see the learning outcome does not only enhance their skills but also enhance their career growth.

Therefore, it is very essential and important for the organisations to ensure that they arrange effective training and development programme in order to have well trained and skilled employees. Employees often gets confuse with the strategic change of structure and work process at their organisation. This can be a crucial impediment towards organisational growth and development, innovation and change efforts. Effective training and development programme can be the key to the organisation to avoid such obstacles. Efficient and role clarified training helps the organisations by developing their employees' skills and knowledge, behaviour and attitude and enhance the performance by increasing productivity. Training and development also enhance the employees by increasing individual's potential, developing proficiency and prospects for career progression. Training and developing programme help both organisation and individual to achieve their desire targets.

Different inception of human being in different forms in the society resulted the existence of training and development. Training works as bridge or medium to transfer different skills and knowledge from one individual to another, from one generation to another. Training and development have gone under tremendous change. Advancement of technological tools and range of different training methods and techniques has brought a significant change in the idea of training and development. These different techniques and methods have added new dimensions to the function of training and development.

2.4 Banking Industry

Cross (1995) stated that bank is the financial transitional establishment that deals in loans and various financial activities. Bank offers a various range of services, but loans, deposits and payment service are its main activities. Heffernan (2005), mentioned that, bank is an institution which is responsible for collecting money temporarily form the public and lending to other people according to their need. Bank involves in various financial activities such as; monetary policy, payments and infrastructure, information system, corporate governance, bank notes, accounting and financial reporting etc. The supreme objective of a bank is to establish as a financial organisation for amplifying profits and to conduct several economic activities. Banks play important role in maintaining a country's economic stability by controlling the money

market. Central bank of a country is responsible to provide advices to the government on various economic concerns. It also assists the government for trading and business as well as socio-economic development of the country. Central bank is also responsible for issue and control notes and currency and maintain exchange rates in the country.

One of the most crucial sectors in business is banking. According to Heffernan (2005), banks are responsible for accepting and providing safety to the public and entities money and lending the money to acquire profit in return. Bank works as the safe house and provide safety to the money of individual and organisation. Banks are involved in many different kinds of activities. The activities of banks are increasing enormously at the present days. Banking activities includes issue of debit and credit cards, opening current and saving accounts for the customers, providing loans, offering safety lockers for valued substances, Cash Point/ATM service and online banking service to the customers. Nowadays, customers are able to transfer money all over the world by using the online banking service as well as the mobile banking apps. The activities that banks are involved with are very sensitive and confidential. Banks need to undertake these actions very confidentially with compliance. It is very crucial to maintain the privacy of the customers as well as to follow the data protection act.

Bank has many significant objectives and the major one is to inaugurate as an institution for amplifying profits and undertake several economic activities. Banks intend to build inclination of savings among the public and motivate people to invest their money in order to bring affluence in return. Banks collects money from the public at a low interest rate and lend this money at a higher interest rate.

2.4.1 Types of Banking

2.4.1.1 Traditional Versus Modern Banking

The banking industry has immensely changed in the last 30 years. Banks has expanded its narrow activities to full service financial firms. Conventionally, the main activities of banks are taking deposits and lending money to people and organisations. Majority of banks' income resulting from the lending business. Banks main profitability driver is the net interest margins. Banks often boost their profit by maximising the interest margins and controlling the operating costs including labour and other costs. Banks' main objective and they are extremely concerned on lending money and collecting deposits.

Until the late 1980s, competition within the banking industry was very restricted and the banking market was decidedly controlled. For example, British banks were restricted from several securities and investment banking business until 1986. After that commercial banks began to obtain stockbroking firms and things started to get changed. Banking restrictions were still in place until 1992 in some European countries such as; Spain and Italy. Under those restriction banks were limited in terms of conducting several activities. In 1992, the European Banking Directive has rephrased the banking definition and developed a banking model for the Banks of European countries called universal banking model. This universal banking model allows the banks to expand their activities including insurance, pensions, securities operations and leasing etc. Since the development of universal banking model, banks within the European Union were undertaking a wide range of financial services activities along with their basic banking activities.

The activities of banking organisations have increased intensely. There are various factors that have affected the global banking business significantly. Capital restrictions were controlling the free flow of funds across the national boundaries. But progressively it was vanished throughout the growth of international operations in the 1980s. Privatisation and various balance sheet restrictions has affected the role of state-owned banks of the European Union and it started to decline. The privatisation and balance sheet restrictions have been eradicated which allowed greater freedom for the banks especially in the financial management of their activities. Rapid advancement of technology has complemented these global trends. It has also modernised the back-office processing and front-office delivery of financial services to the customers. The general developments in communication technology and the consequent drop in costs countenance propagation of information throughout an extensive organisation, making it practical to operate geographically in differentiated marketplaces. The role of competitive forces has increased due to the lower communications costs, as physically distant financial service providers become gradually significant as rivals.

Modern technology continuously shadows the lines of specialisation within the financial intermediates. The development of the internet and various computing technology has been a revolution for the banking industry. The internet has enabled the banks to offer their banking service online. Insurance companies are also enjoying the benefits of internet by offering their services online. Advanced computer technology allows the investment banks and other financial institutions to offer account with similar characteristics of a bank account.

Technological advancement significantly helped the banking industry to expand its range of financial services for the customers and enhanced the competitive environment. The banking business has changed dramatically from an activity characterized by limited competition and a restricted product offering to a much more competitive and diverse activity.

The nature of banking business has changed significantly. The activities of banks are now much more dynamic than the previous moderately restricted and uncompetitive activities. Many banks of this modern world have started to drop the word 'bank' from their name as banks are nowadays regarded as full-service financial firms. Banks transformation into full service institutions has been highly motivated by their strategic objectives and to be able to offer a wide range of financial service to the customers. It helped the banks to increase their products and services that can be sold to the customers. This will also be effective for the banks to improve customer relationship and enhance the profitability of the banks over the longer period. Banks have managed to increase their income sources in the immensely increasing competitive business environment by complementing interest revenue from their lending activities with fee and commission income from selling non-traditional banking products like insurance. Banks need to be much more demand-oriented, focused on meeting the customers' needs from diverse and financially sophisticated client base due to the greater emphasis of building customer relationship.

Banks had less pressure of generating high profits when the market was restricted and uncompetitive. Banking organisations had to pay greater attention to their operational performance. They had to boost the stock price and increase profitability in order to satisfy the shareholders. Banks used to be more focused on strategies based on asset growth, nowadays this is no longer deemed appropriate. Banks now mainly concerned about creating value for the shareholders and it started since banks were focusing to become larger and it was the main indicator of commercial success. The shareholders' demands have increased as has banks demand for capital. In banking the term capital is described as the available resource to the bank that can be used to protect the bank against potential losses and to finance acquisition or expansion to the bank.

There is a minimum capital requirement for the banks which is set by the regulators so that the banks have enough resources to tackle any losses which may be incurred as a result of bad loans or any other activity. Banks are required to generate sufficient profit for their equity to increase the value which will significantly help them to attract new shareholders as well as to retain the

established and valued shareholders. Therefore, senior managers of banks give priority to the strategies that focuses on increasing the overall value of their bank. Modern banks prioritize the strategies that seeks to enhance banks stock prices and improve banks profitability.

2.4.1.2 Universal Banking and the Bancassurance Trend

The deregulation trend has allowed the bank to expand its financial activities in the areas that were prohibited until the recent days. Since the beginning of 1990a, universal banking model has been a vital feature of European Banking. Ho Han (2017), stated that, universal banking model has been the amplified role of commercial banking. The European banking experience provides a clear view of how the combination of banking and insurance business has developed. Bancassurance is the combination of banking and insurance business. The French term bancassurance is used to define the distribution of insurance products and services through the bank's distribution channels. This bancassurance model became famous to the customers because it is a package of financial service which can satisfy customers' banking and insurance needs at the same time.

Nowadays, high street banks offer mortgages and insurance services including life insurance, travel insurance and gadget insurance to the customers. The cross-selling opportunities for banks significantly motivating the banks to use the bancassurance term since the early 1980s. The use of bancassurance model is immensely increasing within the banking industry because of its risk diversification. Bancassurance allows the banks to convert into full service financial institutions.

There are various types of banks within the banking industry. Many authors have categorized banks into three different categories such as central bank, commercial bank and specialized bank. There are some other types of banks for example; retail or personal banking, savings banks, co-operative banks, Islamic banks, investment banking and finance houses etc.

2.4.1.3 Retail or Personal Banking

Personal banking refers to the service provided by the financial institutions for the individuals including current accounts, savings, different types of lending options etc. These lending options includes personal loans, mortgages and credit card services etc. personal banking is a type of service and product which is offered by the banks to the retail customers. Personal or retail baking is small in nature. Usually all the large banks offer personal banking services

including current account, credit transfers, standing orders, direct debits, loans and mortgages, insurance, pensions and other services. The following banks offer personal or retail banking services to the consumers:

2.4.1.4 Commercial Banks

Commercial banks are the main financial intermediate of any country's economy. Commercial banks are the one who operate the payment mechanism and they are the main providers of credit to the corporate and household sector. Joint stock companies, companies that are publicly or privately on the stock exchange are usually the commercial banks. Commercial banks offer full range of financial services to both retail and corporate customers. Lending and deposit collections are commercial banks' main business and they are the key operators of most countries' retail banking markets. There are three different types of commercial banks; such as Public-sector banks, Private sector banks and Foreign banks. Most of the country's largest banks are the commercial banks such as Citibank, HSBC, Barclays etc.

Example of Bangladesh's private commercial banks are AB Bank Limited, Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited, Mercantile Bank Limited, Bank Asia Limited, Bangladesh Commerce Bank Limited, BRAC Bank Limited, BASIC Bank Limited, One Bank Limited, Prime Bank Limited, City Bank, The Premier Bank Limited, Dhaka Bank Limited, Dutch-Bangla Bank, Eastern Bank Limited etc. Habib Bank Limited, Bank Al-Falah Limited and HSBC Bank are the foreign commercial banks which are currently active in Bangladesh. Pubali Bank, Sonali Bank, Rupali Bank and Janata Bank are the public commercial banks of Bangladesh. (Faruk, 2015)

2.4.1.5 Savings Bank

Savings Bank refers to the financial institutions who offers various interest-based saving accounts to the customers to hold their deposit. Different types of saving accounts offer a variety of interest rate for the customers deposit. Savings banks are very similar to the commercial banks in many ways. However, the main difference between savings and commercial banks relates to their ownership features. Mutual ownership is a common type in savings banks which is being owned by the banks' members or shareholders who are also the depositors or borrowers of the bank. Most of the personal or retail banks offer a wide range of savings account facilities to their customers.

2.4.1.6 Building Societies

Another types of financial organisation that offers personal or retail banking services to the customers are known as building societies. They have mutual ownership same as the savings and co-operative banks. Building societies focuses on taking deposits and lending mortgages to the customers. Every building society has a board of directors who are responsible for setting up the societies' strategy and direct the affairs of the society. Building societies are owned by and run for their shareholders.

2.4.1.7 Private Banking

Private banking is closely related to personal banking which has developed substantively over the las decades. Private banking focuses on the wealthy clients and are concerned to provide high-quality provision of a range of financial services. Private banking refers to a customised banking and financial services offered to high level of income recipient private individuals. The services of private banks are similar to the retail banking services. Private banks provide payments and account facilities as well as wide range of up-market investment related services to the customers.

Due to the growing wealth of individuals and relative profitability, many large banks have targeted the market of private banking services. Key components of private banks are long-term relationship orientation, personal contract, anticipating client needs and prudence etc. some of the world's famous private banks are HSBC Private Bank, JPMorgan Private Bank, BNP Paribas Private Bank, Citigroup Private Bank etc. Some of the large commercial banks such as; Barclays and Deutsche Bank have substantial private banking operations.

2.4.1.8 Corporate Banking

Corporate banking is the custom financial and banking services for corporations which is offered by commercial banks. Corporate banking deals with corporate customers which is also known as the business banking. Corporate banking typically provided to the large firms. Many large commercial banks also provide business banking facilities to the corporate customers. For example; Barclays, Halifax, NatWest bank etc. provide business banking facilities. The banking service that are provided to small and medium firms are similar to personal banking services. There are four main types of banking service on offer for the business firms.

2.4.1.9 Payment Services

Banks play the most significant role in the payment system. Banks ensures the smooth process of transactions within the current account, issues credit and debit cards which allows the customers to make payments and get instant access to cash through the auto mated teller machines (ATM) and from the branch. The payment services offered for small firms are quite similar to retail customers. Payment services in the UK include cash and cheque deposit facilities, cheque writing facilities, access to BACS Limited (Banks automated clearing system) and access to CCCL (Cheque and credit clearing company limited).

2.4.1.10 Debt Finance for Small Firms

One of the most critical ingredients of success for the development of any business firms is the access to external finance. The main source of the external finance are traditional bank loan and overdraft facilities. The lending facilities provided to small firms may vary from country to country. For example, the Grameen Bank of Bangladesh provides small loans to developing firms in low interest rate. Grameen Bank also offers personal loan to individuals in very low interest rate. The main sources of external finance also include asset-based finance, venture capital, trade capital and factoring and invoice discounting etc. (BB, 2018)

2.4.1.11 Banking Services for Multinational Corporate Clients

Various financial service firms including commercial banks, investment banks and asset finance firms offers banking services to the multinational corporate clients. The main services that are provided to the multinational corporate clients include; cash management and transaction services, credit and other debt financing facilities such as; loans, overdrafts and bonds etc. The multinational corporate clients also receive services like commitments and guarantees, transactions related to foreign exchange and interest rate, securities and fund management services.

Cash management and transaction service differentiates the larger companies from the small firms. other services such as account reconciliation services, funds concentration, cheque deposit services, computerised pension fund services, risk management services, electronic data interchange and electronic funds transfer facilities are provided to the multinational corporate customers. Large multinational companies first decide whether they will raise funds from the domestic market or from the foreign market. Multinational companies often take both

short-term and long-term loan facilities from the corporate banks. Small firms are keen to take short-term loans rather than long-term. Large companies raise funds through long-term finance so that they can finance long-term investments. Large business organisations are able to access to both secured and unsecured lending facilities. They can also access to an extensive range of other credit facilities including overdraft facilities.

Corporate banking also provides commitments and guarantees to their multinational corporate clients. The commitments refer to a service where a company gets commitment of receiving funds from the bank at a later date. This type of services includes overdraft facilities and provision of credit lines. The term guarantee refers to the underwritten obligations of a third party which is provided by a bank and also stands behind the risk of the transaction. Any default by the counterparty whose behalf the guarantee was written causes immediate loss to the bank. Corporate banks also offer a variety of tools to their corporate clients in order to manage their foreign exchange and interest rate risk.

2.4.1.12 Investment Banking

Different activities which are involved in different banking system that has been discussed earlier, also traditionally have been undertaken by investment banks. Investment banks focuses on the large firms and business organisations, rather than dealing with the retail customers. However, investment banks characteristics are quite similar to the commercial banks but there are some differences. The main role of an investment is to aid companies and governments to raise funds in the capital market. Investment banks helps their client in trading and investing in securities. They also provide other securities services such as; brokerage, financing services and securities lending etc.

The main difference between commercial banking and investment banking is that commercial banking focuses on deposit and lending business while the other concerned with securities underwriting and other business which is related to security. Commercial banks offer cash management, payments and credit facilities to the customers but, investment banks arrange different types of financing for their clients by issuing equity and debt to finance company extension.

2.4.1.13 Islamic Banking

Islamic banking has been growing in various part of the world in the recent years. Islamic banks operate their activities based on the non-interest principles. Islamic banking is a finance or banking activity that complies with the Islamic Law and operates through the development of Islamic economics. Their activities are guided by the Islamic Shariah Law which prohibits the interest or payment of riba, but it inspires the entrepreneurial activity. Any bank who wants to intend to offer Islamic Banking Services to the customers must comply with the Islamic Banking rules and regulations. Islamic banks do not charge any interest for their products and services. They aim to offer different profit-sharing-related products whereby depositors share in the risk of the bank's lending. Banks earn a return rather than interest and the borrowers repays the loan based on the profits which is generated from the project on which the loan was originally lent. There are various Islamic banks active in Bangladesh such as; Al-Arafah Islamic Bank Limited, First Security Islamic Bank Limited, ICB Islamic Bank Limited, Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited, Shahjalal Islami Bank Limited and Social Islami Bank Limited etc.

2.4.1.14 Central Banking

The main functions of any country's central bank are to control and manage monetary policy. Central banks focus on achieving price stability in order to prevent liquidity crises, situations of money market disorders and financial crises and to make sure the payment system functions smoothly. According to Dowd (1996), central bank can be defined as the financial institution of a country who is responsible for looking after the monetary system of a nation who aims to enhance economic growth without inflation. Central bank controls the issue of notes and coins of a country. Central bank has the authority to control the other banks' created credit-money.

Central bank is commended with the responsibilities of guiding and regulating a country's entire banking system. Central bank usually does not deal with the general public. Its main concern is to act fundamentally as the bank of the government and maintain deposit accounts of every other active banks within the country. All other banks seek guidance from the central bank whenever they face any difficulties. The central bank of a country is also known as the bank of the bankers. Central bank is responsible for recording government income and outflows. Government gets advises from its central bank on credit policies and monetary. It also helps the Government to decide interest rates for bank loans and deposits. Central bank controls the foreign exchange rates. Central bank is the only authority who issues the currency.

Central bank acts as the official agent for the government to deal with all its gold and foreign exchange matters. Government hold its reserve gold and foreign exchange at the central bank.

2.4.1.15 Specialised Banks

This is another type of banking. Specialised banks are those banks who pay attention to finance specialised economic as well as social activities. These banks are specialised for the overall development of a nation's economic sector. Specialise banks operate its activities in financing various economic, industrial and agricultural projects which design for socio-economic development of a specific area. These types of bank deals with different credit gadgets in the regulatory and financial market. Their main objective is to provide loans to individuals or legal bodies in order to contrivance different types of economic, industrial or agricultural projects for the development of the public. Grameen Bank of Bangladesh is a great example of specialised bank. Its main purpose is to develop the overall situation of financially unstable women by providing them small loans with low interest in return. It has been working to develop women power in the rural area of Bangladesh. There are few other specialised banks in Bangladesh such as; Bangladesh Krishi Bank, Bangladesh Development Bank and Rajshahi Krishi Unnayan Bank etc.

2.5 Banking in Bangladesh

Bangladesh joined the banking industry in 1971. One of the branches of the state bank of Pakistan was declared as the Central Bank of Bangladesh under special Act which was later named as the BB (BB, 2018). The Pubali Bank Limited and Uttara Bank Limited was renamed from the Mercantile Bank Limited and Eastern Banking Corporation Limited. Both of these banks were headquartered in Dhaka. At present, there are 4 government banks, 30 local private banks, 12 foreign banks, 7 specialised and 4 other banks are active in Bangladesh. There are around 5500 branches of different banks are operating their activities in Bangladesh. The banking system in Bangladesh has come into an established position after the government has nationalised all banks under the Presidents Order 26 in 1972. (BB, 2018)

The government has renamed all the banks after nationalising them. The national bank of Pakistan was renamed as Sonali Bank Limited, the United Bank and the Union Bank as the Janata bank Limited, Habib Bank as the Agrani Bank Limited and the Muslim Commercial

Bank as the Rupali Bank Limited. The BB has begun its activity as the central bank of Bangladesh since then.

2.6 Risks Involved in Banking

The main goal of any private bank is to maximise its shareholders' value. Returns are proportional to the risk taken for any public bank when the markets are efficient. Managers of small and unlisted bank always keen to maximise the shareholders' value by seeking highest returns for what they deem to be acceptable levels of risk. Banks have had to assume higher risks and manage and avoid losses. The increase pressure of maximising shareholders' value increases many potential risks in the banking sector. In order to bring efficiency in the banking industry, it is very crucial to define the most common risks in banking and to understand the importance of the interrelation among banking risks. The most common risks involved in banking are listed below:

2.6.1 Credit Risk

Saunders and Cornett (1999) stated that credit risk arise when the bank borrower or counterparty fail to meet the obligations in accordance with the agreed terms and conditions. Credit risk is involved in banks' lending activity and it is described as the risk of a loan not being repaid partly or in full. Credit risk is the risk of a decline in the credit-standing of a counterparty. Credit risks also can be developed from holding bonds and other securities. It is very crucial for the bank managers to minimise credit losses. This can be done by creating a portfolio of assets that diversifies the degree of credit risk. Higher expected return assets have a higher probability of credit risk. In contrast, low default risk assets are associated with low credit risk and low expected return. Bank must thoroughly investigate the borrowers' ability of repaying their loan.

2.6.2 Interest Rate Risk

Another significant risk involved with the banking industry is the interest rate risk. It is described as the price which relates to present claims on resources comparative to potential claims on resources. Borrowers pays the interest rate as a price in order to consume the resources instantly rather than in the future. Same as all other prices in the free market, interest rates are also developed based on the interaction of all supply and demand. As mentioned by

Wilson (1997), interest rate is the price which is developed by the collaboration of the supply and demand for future claims on resources.

Interest rate have a very decisive part in the banking system. A country's financial flows, the distribution of wealth, capital investment and the profitability of financial institutions can be manipulated by the interest rate. The risk of interest rates within the financial industry has increased significantly in the recent years.

2.6.3 Liquidity or Funding Risk

Liquid asset is the asset which can be turned into cash rapidly by avoiding any capital loss or interest penalty. Liquidity risk is the risk that arises due to lack of marketability of any investment that cannot be sold or bought instantly in order to prevent or minimise a loss. Liquidity risk is the risk that a bank or firm may not be able to meet short-term financial demands. Liquidity risk normally appears when company is not capable of converting a security or hard asset to cash without losing any capital or income during the process.

2.6.4 Foreign Exchange Risk

The importance of international activities in the form of foreign direct investment and foreign portfolio investment has increased severely because of the global market. Banks' actual earning from foreign investment may be different by changes in exchange rates. Foreign exchange rates often affected by the changes in the value of a country's currency. Casu et al. (2006) described exchange rate as a number of units of a country's national currency which is required to be capitulated in order to obtain one unit of a foreign national currency. Currency rate vary from country to country for example the US Dollar, British Pound, Bangladeshi Taka, Japanese Yen and Euro etc.

Financial institutions are often in risk of foreign exchange rate. The uncertainty of different countries political and economic condition makes the currency rate unstable. This increases the risk of foreign exchange rate. Due to the unstable condition, a country's currency value might increase or decrease. When the currency value goes down, it affects the financial organisations negatively. For example, right after the Brexit election in the UK, the value of British Pound went down significantly. Foreign exchange can be in different forms such as; cash, funds on credit card or bank deposits. Foreign exchange risk is the risk that exchange rate fluctuations

affect the value of a bank's assets, liabilities and off-balance sheet activities denominated in foreign currency.

2.6.5 Market Risk

Market or trading risk is the risk of losses in on and off-balance sheet positions arising from movements in market prices. Assets, liabilities and derivative products and relates to changes in interest rates, exchange rates and other asset prices are affected by the market risk. Market risk has increased significantly because of the declining traditional sources of income and increased modern conditions. Banks greater dependence on traditional income sources also increased the level of market risk ominously.

Heffernan (2005) has classified market risk as general or systematic market risk and unsystematic or specific market risk. Due to the change of macro factor such as; economic policy, systematic market risk arises by the movement in the prices of all market instruments. In contrast, unsystematic market risk arises where the price of one instrument moves out of line with similar instruments due to different events. Large and small banks perform different measurement techniques to assess the market risk. Large bank uses Value-at-Risk (VaR) to analyse the market risk which can affect the bank, while smaller conduct sensitivity analysis in order to measure market risk.

2.6.6 Country and Sovereign Risk

Country risk refers to the risk of a foreign country's social, economic, and political condition. A bank's financial and commercial interests are often affected by these factors. International lending always involves high risk, but it is usually safer to lend a foreign government than lending to a private corporation or borrower.

2.6 Training in Banking Sector

The banking sectors of a country play a very crucial role as the front-runner of the financial and commercial activities. Bank employees has to deal with various critical and confidential activities such as monetary policy, payments and market infrastructure, information system, corporate governance, bank notes, accounting and financial reporting etc. These activities require careful attention to be compliant with the regulations. Therefore, bank needs to be more focused to train and develop their employees so that they can handle the compliance regulations

effectively. Decenzo and Robins (2003) training helps an organisation to successfully implement changes and adapt its employees with the change. Training is vital because it increases an employee's ability, awareness, behaviour and approach. Buckley and Caple (2007) described training as the systematic approach of developing or increasing employees' skills and knowledge to enhance organisational effectiveness and performance. In other word, training is the methodical way of developing employees' skills and ability which helps to improve organisational performance and productivity.

The supreme objective of training and development is to increase employees' ability and productivity so that they can effectively complete the given task. It is very important that every organisation is cope up with training and development of their employees in order accomplish the desired goals and objectives. Armstrong (2002) discussed that training is the systematic development of an employees' knowledge, skill and attitudes which are fundamental elements to perform effectively and compete a given task.

Randhawa (2007) described training as the systematic approach of developing new and existing employees' skills and knowledge. Employees' must be multi-skilled and knowledgeable about their job. According to Towler et al. (2014), employees receive training from their organisation so that they will be able to perform their tasks effectively and meet organisational goals with success. Many has argued that employee training and development has become very crucial to the organisations as training and development enhances the organisational productivity and effectiveness. It is a proved fact that multi-skilled employees are vital asset to any organisation. Hackett (1997) has provided an important definition of training and development. He has defined training as the organisation's approach of educating their employees according to the company standard and efficiency.

2.6.1 Benchmarking Standard and Effectiveness

Benchmarking is very important for the success of training and development program of any organisation. Operational benchmarking can help the management to evaluate the effectiveness of their training and development program. Operational benchmarking helps to recognize the best practice model within the business. It also assists the organisation to compare the current organisational practices and aid to make future changes or suggestions to develop the existing practice and increase the efficiency.

Holloway (2007) stated that, benchmark standard is a model or reference which a company can use to compare their actual performance or productivity. Benchmarking is a procedure of measuring a company's performance, services and its processes. Benchmarking can be used to measure any existing program's productivity and effectiveness. According to Holloway (2007), there are four main types of benchmarking to measure performance or productivity: internal, external, performance and practice. It is very important to have the appropriate benchmarking model in practice.

Operational efficiency is a very crucial element for business organisations as it helps the company to develop quality and productivity by maximizing the effective use of its assets. Many authors have described operational effectiveness as necessity rather than a strategy. Operational effectiveness means being more productive on the same task than the main competitors. Operational effectiveness increases organisational effectiveness and productivity and help the organisation to remain competitive in the market.

2.7 Types of Training

Banking industry is the most significant sector of business industry. Training is equally important to achieve customer satisfaction as well as to operate all the activities smoothly. But Prasanna (2013) stated that bank needs to pay additional courtesy to adhere with the compliance regulations because they have deal with several activities which are very confidential. Every organisation has its own method or process of training. Every organisation designs training and development programme for their employees who can benefits both the employer and employees. Similarly, banks also have specific training and development programme for their employees. Public and commercial bank has their own separate way of employee training. Therefore, their employee training and development programme is different from each other. Training within the banking sector varies from bank to bank.

Armstrong (2010) stated that the perspective of an organisation is based on the needs and importance of the training that required for its employees. Every organisation has their own training policies which depends on the needs and significance of the training within the organisation. Different organisation takes different approaches of training their employees based on the needs and its viewpoint. Bank organizes the employee training and development programme according to organisational needs and objectives. Many authors have argued about the effectiveness of several training and development programme for the bank employees.

Many banks organize different types of training and development programme depending on the job role of their employees. For example, separate training course for managerial role, new employees, technical training and training for compliance department etc.

Noe (2010) mentioned that, employees are required to understand and adopt the service policy and internal procedures of their organisation. It is also essential for them to understand the entire operational system and also to share the knowledge in order to resourcefully use it to modify a product or service. All the human resource development activities are meant to either improve performance on the present job of the individual, train new skills for new job or new position in the future and general growth for both individuals and organisation so as to be able to meet organisation's current and future objectives. There are broadly two different methods that organisations may choose from for training and developing skills of its employees. These are on-the-job training given to organisational employees while conducting their regular work at the same working venues and off-the-job training involves taking employees away from their usual work environments and therefore all concentration is left out to the training. Examples of the on-the-job training include but are not limited to job rotations and transfers, coaching and/or mentoring. On the other hand, off-the-job training examples include conferences, role playing, and many more as explained below in detail.

Armstrong (2002) argues that on-the-job training may consist of teaching or coaching by more experienced people or trainers at the desk or at the bench. Different organisations are motivated to take on different training methods for a number of reasons for example; depending on the organisation's strategy, goals and resources available, depending on the needs identified at the time, and the target group to be trained which may include among others individual workers, groups, teams, department or the entire organisation. Some bank provides on the job training while others provide off the job training. Some business organisation found on-the-job training effective while others believe off the-job-training is more efficient than on the job training.

2.8 On-the-job Training

Business organisations are now concerned to get more results but doing less work. This made the on-the-job training very important, and companies are nowadays relying a lot on on-the-job training in order to speed up their activities and bring their employees up to the expected speed. Barron et al. (1989) mentioned that company spends over 150 hours on an average for

a newly joined employee during the first three months of employment. Companies are doing this at a considerable cost as they are expected to get more done with less human resource.

Today's rapidly shifting, and highly competitive business environment required new skills. Employers must ensure that their employees acquire new skills to cope up with the rapidly changing business environment. There are not enough qualified people on the job market, while the complex technology is demanding more well-trained employees. Furthermore, the number of young workers is surprisingly decreasing. It is expensive and time consuming to replace the under skilled employees. The most effective way to solve this by re-training the current employees and companies of modern day have identified that re-training can help them to close the gap between required and available skilled workers. Many authors have defined on-the-job training differently. Some have classified it as a structured way of training people, while others have described it as an unstructured training method.

Lawson (1997) described on-the-job training as a structured process which is conducted by the employers at the workplace to provide the required knowledge and skills to the employees to perform their job tasks. On-the-job training is the structured way of up skilling the employees to do the tasks in an effective way. On-the-job training is an ongoing process which is designed to assist the employees to gain greater competency and overcome any obstructions to improve their performance and productivity.

Training is continually conjuring to a mental image of group-based rather than on-the-job training or e-learning experiences for most people. This is moderately true in most of the major organisations as they significantly value employee training and enjoy training with high visibility. These major corporations have been efficiently incorporated with human resource management, job design, organisational structure design, organisational development and benefits and payment. Training includes a lot more than planned off-the-job learning practises. The importance of improving the on-the-job training is ominously increasing.

Lawson (1997) stated that on-the-job training approach enhances employees' skills and productivity for progression during their employment. This approach of training is very effective as it develops an employee's confidence and increases productiveness. On-the-job training refers to that approach of training where the trainees receive the training while doing their actual job. This type of training is usually conducted by a professional trainer or an experienced employee who works as the instructor during the training period.

On-the-job training prepares the trainee for their job quicker than any other approaches. On-the-job training can take place at any level can be used to train the newcomers as well as existing employees. This method of training can be effective to introduce the existing employees to a new system or technology. However, many researchers have argued that off-the-job training is more effectual in the banking sector.

2.8.1 Selecting the Trainers

The success of any training and development programme mostly depends on the effectiveness of the trainer. Therefore, it is very crucial to select the perfect trainers for a successful training programme. Most employers follow the process of peer training. They use the experienced employees to train the newcomers. In most cases it is a good option because it gives the opportunity to involve more people and share their knowledge and skills with each other's. Peer trainers are often more effective than supervisors, but it is certainly not the best method of on-the-job training. The main disadvantage of such peer trainers is that experienced person may know the job very well but may not be the best trainers. Also, the peer trainers may take the shortcuts and skip important information to get the training done quicker which will affect the new employees negatively as they will not receive proper training and will not be effective enough at their job. Effective trainer requires some special characteristics which an employer must identify before selecting the trainers (Kulkarni, 2013)

2.8.2 Job Competence

Employers can develop effective trainers. However, certain proficiencies should be requisites to their training skill development. The most important characteristics of being a good trainer is to be competent at the job place (Green, 2002). The trainer must know the job well and need to have an appropriate technical knowledge and experience in doing the job. But this does not guarantee of an effective trainer unless they have the other qualifications too (Kumar and Siddika, 2017).

2.8.3 Professionalism

The selected trainer must be confident enough and enthusiastic. He will be a role model to the trainee, so he must be professional (Kumar and Siddika 2017). The trainers' professionalism should be marked by high energy level, appearance, positive attitude and strong desire to contribute organisations' success. Trainer should be some who is more than eager to expand

his or her current job responsibilities and sees this additional consignment as an opportunity progress with his career (Athar et al., 2017). The trainers should believe in their own competence and determine that assurance without condescension (Buckley et al.,2007).

2.8.4 Communication and Interpersonal Skills

Excellent communication skill is the most crucial requirement for a successful trainer after job competency. The trainer must describe and explain the procedures and training notes clearly and in an effective way to the trainees. Trainer must be sensitive to all the trainees' body language (Buckley et al.,2007). It is also important to choose the trainers who demonstrate good interpersonal skills in various situations with the co-workers as well as people from outside the organisation. Trainer should be able to manage any conflict that may rise during the training without losing their cool by being friendly and genial.

2.8.5 Patience and Flexible

It is very important for a trainer to be patience and flexible. If a trainee is unable to pick up any topic at the first instance, the trainer must repeat or re-explain the topic. Trainers need to be able to explain a topic in different ways and identify which way is more effective for the trainees. Demonstrated ability to manage the workplace and workflow and to manage the time proficiently are trainers' crucial fundamentals.

Trainer should be able to demonstrate excellent qualities of innovation, creativity and initiative as the role model to the trainees. These traits are developed into the job and being passed to the trainers. The trainers should have a sense of commitment towards the training and take pride in the success of the training programme. He or she should have a positive team spirit in order to achieve success. This will help to create a strong and healthy working relationship among the trainers and trainees which helps them to develop their own network and intensifies the team conception (Decenzo, 2003).

2.8.6 Developing a Training Plan

On-the-job training focuses on individual tasks rather than focusing on the whole job. It is especially concerned with the individuals' behaviour, attitude, thoughts and decisions. The outcomes of an OJT focus on quality, timeliness cost and so forth. The primary step of

developing a training plan is analysing the job to categorise all the necessary steps or sub tasks of the job (Randhawa, 2007).

2.8.7 Analysing Job Tasks

Before developing a plan for an OJT, the organisation must analyse the job task and categorised into sub-tasks. Breaking large tasks into smaller tasks will help the trainees to understand the tasks easily and effectively (Noe, 2010). Subtasks familiarise the trainees to smaller incremental objectives. Sub tasks give an opportunity to the trainees to experience regular and several accomplishments along the way. Categorising a larger task into smaller subtasks also allows the trainers to explain the tasks more effectively and easily to the trainees. Analysing the job tasks and categorising them in to smaller sub-tasks is very important for the success of any OJT.

2.8.8 Setting Objectives

The next step is setting up objectives to achieve. It is very crucial because without any objectives, no training programme will be successful. The performance standard can be the base for training objectives. Training objectives should reflect the organisational goals and objectives. Training objectives must be set up in accordance with the organisations' expectations (Rothwell et al., 2004).

2.8.9 Designing Effective Training Activities

Success of any training and development programme very much depends on the effectiveness of the training activities. Training activities should inspire the learners to think for themselves and to be able to question and contemplate and take responsibility for their own training by being self-directed. When the trainees get a simulated experience of doing the job within a protected context, they will be emotionally involved within the training programme. Effective training activities help the learners to retain all the training information involve within the training process (Rothwell et al., 2004).

2.8.10 Conducting the Training

After all the crucial pre-training steps, organisations need to get prepared for conducting the training. It is very important to create a climate of trust and positive expectations for the training to be conducted. The learning climate is a crucial element especially for one-to-one OJT.

Normally the human beings are naturally motivated to learn but they need to be emotionally attached with the training programme. Wlodkowski (1993) mentioned that an adult's learning experience is very much affected by his or her emotion. Both the trainer and the trainee need to prepare themselves for the training. Training site, all the relevant training equipment and materials must be organised before the training programme begins.

Trainers need to be mentally prepared for the training experience. They should begin by familiarising themselves with the training and find out as much information about the trainees as they can beforehand. It is important for the trainers to identify who is the trainee, what does they need to know during the training, how much they already know about the job and what are the goals. Presenting the training to the trainees throughout the training programme is very important. An effective trainer uses a variety of attractive and effective methods to make sure interaction and communication with everyone.

2.9 Benefits of On-the-Job Training

One of the most effective benefits of on-the-job training is that it's actually reduces the unproductive breaking-in time of the newcomers. On-the-job training also helps to reduce unnecessary turnover and prevents the employees from anxiety. Employees often feel anxious when they are left to learn from unplanned methods because of not knowing how they are expected to do the tasks while they are at job. On-the-job training introduces the employees to their job role, and they can confidently learn how to complete their task and organisations' expectation from them. Employees can learn by doing the actual job through on-the-job training (Randhawa, 2007). Managers should make regular observation and provide feedback on their performance. The structure and framework of the on-the-job training usually depends on the nature of the tasks that the employees are expected to carry out. There will be situations when individual requires training, but it will not be possible to send the individual to a separate training programme (Lawson, 1997). On-the-job training will be the best option for those situations (Rothwell et al., 2004).

On-the-job training focuses on individual. Informal on-the-job training's prime concern is to meet the individuals' training needs. People who are responsible usually organises the informal on-the-job training according to individuals' training needs.

2.10 Off-the-job Training

Randhawa, (2007) described off-the-job training as the approach of training employees by conducting lectures, simulation, case studies and role playing etc. Many organisations often run different lectures, seminars or workshop away from the actual job for their employees to train and develop them before putting them into the real job. Rothwell and Kazanas (2004) discussed the importance and effectiveness of this type of training approach. They mentioned that off-the-job training approach is much effective in terms of providing training on complex subjects. Banking sector is very complex and involves in various activities which requires depth training to develop the bank employees' knowledge to make them qualified to do the job effectively.

Rothwell and Kazanas (2004) argued the effectiveness of various types of training specially for industrial training. As mentioned by them off-the-job training such as conferences and seminars, lectures and workshops provide extensive range of knowledge to the trainees which can be very expedient in the future. Off-the-job training allows the employees to pay full concentration on their training activities which is very crucial for the success of the training program. Arranging training programme in different location enables the trainees to focus on their training tasks without any distraction. However, Off-the-job training can be expensive, but it is beneficial for the organisation. It allows the trainees to obtain a wider range of knowledge and skills and enable them to be confident when they start their job. As the lecture or seminar and workshop are usually guided by experts or specialists, therefore the trainees get an extensive and depth understanding of the designated area. Several banks organise different lectures/seminars for their new employees as well as existing staffs. These seminars are usually led by expert lecturers who are highly qualified within the specific area.

Rothwell and Kazanas (2004) mentioned that off-the-job training can be effective for banking sector because it allows to train a large group at the same time. Banks can arrange one training session and include employees from different branches at the same time. Banks provide various off-the-job training to its employees including compliance training, process training, sales training, software application training and soft skills training etc. It is very important to measure the effectiveness of the training programme because it identifies whether the training programme is successful or not. Effectiveness of Off-the-job training can be measured by

evaluating participants' satisfaction, employee retention, employees' on-the-job performance and productivity and business impacts.

Most of the training specialists usually conduct an evaluation after their workshop or seminar. These evaluations include surveys and feedbacks which allows the participants to express their satisfaction level regarding the course content, course material, instructor, location and other conveniences. The training professionals use these feedbacks to arrange any adjustment into the training program or implement any changes to the program by changing course material, length of the course etc. Ideally, off-the-job training has long term impacts on employees' performance. It is very important to ensure the participants are actually getting help from the training program. Organisation must do that by aligning their program objectives to strategic aims. Successful off-the-job training program brings changes to the behaviour and performance of the employees, so it can be noticeable by the managers when they are back at work.

2.11 Training in BB

BB as the central bank of the country plays a crucial role to enhance smooth economic function, develop business friendly rules and protect the economy during critical period. BB pays enormous attention on training and development for its employees because in this current fast changing world it is very important to provide adequate training to the employees so that they can adapt with changes and keep themselves updated with the latest knowledge in the banking sector. BB has established a training academy in 1977 for the training of its employees named BB Training Academy (BBTA). BBTA provides almost 80 training programmes to build and develop confidence of their employees (BB, 2018).

The main objectives of the bank's training programme are to bring changes in understanding, knowledge, skills, abilities, attitude and behaviour of the employees. Positive change in these characteristics can help to improve the productivity and performance of their employees. The vision of BBTA is to attain excellence in imparting training, education and research with a view to develop the officials of BB and other stakeholders of the country continually in parallel with the central banks of the developing countries of the world with an advanced approach. BBTA mainly provide robust foundation training for the newly recruited Assistant Directors of BB. BBTA's prime ambition is to instruct training to the personnel of Central Bank and other financial institutions to make them equipped with the latest knowledge of economic, financial and banking development.

As a knowledge management centre of BB, BBTA publishes a journal titled 'Thoughts on Banking and Finance' which includes important information of financial arena. BBTA commits to upgrade and modernize training modules for the Associate Directors of the Bank and reach the global standard of training in the banking sector.

2.11.1 Training in BBTA

BBTA pursues the tasks of capacity building and human resource development to prepare disciplined, skilled, and knowledgeable executive directors for the central bank of Bangladesh. BBTA arranges two separate foundation courses for the directors: advanced foundation course and specialised foundation course. BBTA's training programme includes conferences, workshops, and seminars on several important topics of central banking, economics, banking and finance, financial sector development, human resources development and macroeconomic management. BBTA organises various advanced and specialised foundation training courses for the officers of BB as well as for the officers of Commercial Banks. BBTA also arranges different seminars, workshops and lecture sessions on several important topics related to the training programme. (BB, 2018)

2.11.2 Foundation Training

During 2015, two foundation courses for six months each were arranged at BBTA where 107 newly recruited Assistant Directors attended as participants. Besides passing the regular modules the trainees take part in cultural functions, debate, recitation, writing wall magazine, construction of trainee database, field visit, and study visit program around the country and also outside the country. Training Course, Seminar and Workshop During 2015 BBTA arranged 150 training courses, seminars and workshops in its own premises and at BB offices where 5904 officials attended from BB, Commercial banks, Non-bank- Financial Institutions, NGOs and Government Offices.

2.11.3 Other Training Courses

BB organise many different types of training courses for its employees. These training courses includes Bank and NBFIs Supervision, Core Risk Management, Risk Based Capital Adequacy according to BASEL-III, Stress Testing for Banks, Formulation and Implementation of Monetary Policy, Banking Laws and Regulation, Integrity and Anticorruption in financial Sector, Human Resources Management, Leadership, Team Building and Negotiation Skill, Financial Inclusion, Micro Credit and SME Financing, SME Credit Risk Management, Green

Banking and Environment Risk Management, Corporate Governance, Public Debt Management and Securities Markets, Agriculture Financing and Rural Development, Currency Management Payment and Settlement System, Loan Classification, Provisioning and Re-scheduling, Credit Derivatives, Detection, Disposal of Forged and Mutilated Notes, International Trade Financing, Foreign Exchange Transaction Reporting, Foreign Currency Account and Remittance, FC Accounts: Opening and Operational Procedures, Islamic Banking and Finance, Prevention of Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing, Financial Investigation to Combat Money Laundering and Counter the Financial of Terrorism, Training Course on Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP), E-Commerce and E-Banking, ICT Security Policy, Web Based Online System Software, Financial Stability Analysis, Money and Banking Data Reporting, Research Methodology, Understanding Economic Indicators, Financial Statement Analysis, National Budget and Central Banking Policy etc. (BB, 2018)

2.12 BB's Training Programme (Non-Financial and Non-technical)

The following figure shows all the important programs/areas which have significant impact on operational and managerial perspectives in banking sector. Every area has its own significance in banking sector. Such areas are essential parts of training of employees especially for senior managers who are responsible to run bank branches and have large span of control.

Research methodology	CSR of BB
Advance course on Leadership	Integrity and Anticorruption
Public private partnership	Prevention of fraud and forgery in banks
Core risk management	FDI and portfolio investment in Bangladesh
Training course on ER	HRM and development
Strategic planning and management	Manner and etiquette

Figure 1: Training programs of BB; Source: Designed by the Author

Below are the learning objectives and current course contents of BB's 12 non-technical and non-financial areas:

2.12.1 Research methodology

Appreciate the importance of conducting research, understand the research methodology and techniques, acquire knowledge on developing research proposals, designing research and data collection methods, acquire the fundamental knowledge in data processing methods. Improve their skills in analysing data and presenting results.

Introduction to research methodology, alternative research paradigms, problem identification, literature review and conceptualisation, specifying an econometric model in research, designing a questionnaire, conducting qualitative interviews, data collection and processing methods, estimating the Specified Model, common econometric issues in empirical research, diagnostics and remedies and preparing the research proposal.

2.12.2 FDI and Portfolio investment in Bangladesh

Policies, Importance and Significance of Inward Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Outward Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) of Bangladesh, Concepts and Definition of Foreign Direct Investment, Reporting Procedures of Inward FDI Returns and Outward FDI Returns, Workshop/Exercise on FDI, Policies, Importance and Significance of Medium and Long Term (MLT) Private Sector External Debt (PSED) of Bangladesh, Concepts and Definition of Private Sector External Debt, Reporting Procedures of MLT Private Sector External Debt, Reporting Procedures MLT Private Sector External Debt in RITs, Workshop/Exercise on MLT Private Sector External Debt, Concepts and Definition of Portfolio Investment, Policies, Importance, Significance Short Term Private Sector External Debt (PSED) and Portfolio Investment (PI) of Bangladesh, Reporting Procedures of Short Term Private Sector External Debt, Reporting Procedures Portfolio Investment (PI) Return Form, Reporting Procedures of Short Term Private Sector External Debt and Portfolio Investment Workshop/Exercise on Short Term Private Sector External Debt and PI returns

2.12.3 Manner and Etiquette

Work in a more professional manner. Understand his/her strengths and weaknesses and project the best outlook for the organisation Select the right grooming technique for professional outlook. Understand body language and its significant role in communication.

2.12.4 Prevention of fraud and forgery in banks

Information Systems Auditing for E-Banking, Risks and Security in Electronic Banking. Electronic Fraud Detection Techniques for Credit Card, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking How E-Banking Fraud effect the Banking Business and what should be done for Business Continuity.

2.12.5 Training course on ERP

To familiarize the participants with the Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP) software, to make the participants acquainted with SAP navigation different aspects HR and payroll module and MM module. Course Content, Implementation of ERP in BB, SAP Navigation: Various Info types and Action, Personnel Administration, Organisational and Training Management, Event Management, Payroll, Concept of Company Code, Cost Center, Profit Center and Chart of account, Creation and approval of purchasing service, Creation and approval of Purchasing Assets, Creation and approval of Purchasing Non-Stock Items and Billing process.

2.12.6 Integrity and Anticorruption

Enhanced knowledge and understanding of corruption and its social impact, have insight in the importance of integrity for well-functioning transparent financial institutions. Better understanding of how to implement anti-corruption strategies and Integrity policies. Identify instruments for increasing transparency and accountability. Good understanding of available resources on corruption/anti-corruption Course. Integrity and Corruption: An Overview Anticorruption Commission Act: 2004, Causes of Corruption: Personal, Social and Situational Cause. Measures for Prevention of Corruption: Personality Development, Motivation, Transparency and Accountability, Public Right, Public Money and Time, Corruption in BD Causes and Impact and A Strategic Approach to Prevent and Control Corruption in BD.

2.12.7 Advance course on Leadership

Familiarized with the basics of Leadership, Team Building and Negotiation Skill. Acquainted with the theories, models and organisational practices of Leadership. Team Building and Negotiation Skill, Leadership: Concept, Objectives, Traits and Types. Motivation and its importance in Leadership. Nature, Characteristics, Objectives and stages of Team Building Key to success: Leadership, Teamwork and Negotiation. Time Management and Stress Management, Team Behaviour and Group Dynamics, Negotiation: Different Styles and Skills Required, Grievance Handling, Intra-personal and Interpersonal Communication in Negotiation and Counselling of Human Resources.

2.12.8 Corporate Social Responsibility

Macro Prudential Aspects for Strengthening Financial Stability of our country TM. Discussion on Monetary Policy Stance TM. Need for Financial Stability for the smooth development of the Economy TM. Discussion on Corporate Social Responsibilities of Banks and NBFIs in Bangladesh. Discussion on Green Banking and Guidelines of Environment Risk Management.

2.12.9 Core risk Management

Present Scenario of ICT Use in the Banking Industry, ICT Risk Management-Definition of Risk, Different types of Risks for Banks, Causes of arising ICT Risks for Banks, Possible Impact of falling to mitigate ICT Risk, Mitigating ICT Risk, Overview of ICT Guidelines for Banks and FIs, ICT Security Management, ICT Operation Management, Physical Security, Information Security Standard, Software Development and Acquisition , Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery Plan Service Provider Management , ICT Hardware and Software usage and Disposal Policy. E-mail Policy and Mobile financial services for the Banks.

2.12.10 HRM

Leadership: Concept, Objectives, Traits and Types. Motivation and its importance in Leadership

Nature, Characteristics, Objectives, and stages of Team Building. Key to success: Leadership, Teamwork and Negotiation, Time Management and Stress Management, Team behaviour and Group Dynamics. Negotiation: Different Styles and Skills Required. Grievance Handling, Intra-personal and Interpersonal Communication in Negotiation and Counselling of Human Resources.

2.12.11 Strategic Planning

Introduction to SME Banking and Definition of SME, SME lending Policy, Credit Analysis Process. Non-Financial and Financial Analysis of Customer's Business (Capital and Ratio Analysis). Financial Analysis (Quiz), Financial Analysis (Cash Flow Analysis). Business Plan Analysis, Business Strategy and Relationship Management.

2.12.12 Public Private

ICT Security Management, ICT Risk Management, ICT Service Delivery Management. Infrastructure Security Management, Access Control of Information System. Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery Management. Acquisition and Development of Information

Systems. Alternative Delivery Channels (ADC), Security Management, Service Provider Management and Customer Education.

2.13 Theoretical analysis of the identified 12 non-technical and non-financial areas

The followings are the analysis of the identified 12 areas in the current training and development programs of BB. The literature was gathered to analyse the general accepted theories, models and knowledge regarding the identified areas. In order to do so, previous studies which includes journals and books were analysed in depth to get the key information regarding the identified areas. Such information helped the author to find the weaknesses in the current training and development programs of bank of Bangladesh. The significance and utilization of the following information in banking field is discussed below which enhance the worth of the following analysis and helped the author to design a new guideline to achieve the primary aim of this study.

2.13.1 Strategic Planning and Management

According to Manus and Graham (2003), in banking field, strategic planning and management act as an engine in organisations which keeps them moving in hardships and in intense competition at international and at national level. According to Aspara (2011), this is crucial for senior managers to equip themselves with all necessary skills by studying strategic planning and management in depth. It is necessary to study strategic area with practical examples by targeting core areas in strategic planning and management (Aspara, 2011).

Strategic planning refers to the advanced planning to deal with future issues by formulating effective strategies and practices whereas strategic management refers to the managing of issues which comes during the implementation of formulated strategies like managing resistances of employees and evaluation of formulated strategies. There are 3 essential pillars named as implementation pillar, managing resistance pillar and evaluation pillar. Every pillar is comprised of tools, theories and techniques which are essential to be known by senior managers. Furthermore, formulation of strategies is also a detail process which is comprised of several factors, steps and techniques. The following is the analysis of strategic planning and management which covers all essential information which must be known by senior manager in banking field (Belias, 2014).

Formulating a Strategy: Formulating strategy is to make or thinks that what the requirements to achieve a specific Goal are. The big business organisation mostly deals with the long-term goals. They defined requirements to achieve goals by implementing the constraints or the business rules. For example, the bank wants to increase interest rate per year that's why they designed a planning like make advertisement, offer clients to open a free account. If their strategy successful, the users of the banks increase.

Automatically, there interest rate increases per year. So, by keeping in mind this type of the strategy they design a formula, they can also take help or hire a person who is expert in the stats, give them a plan which should be implementing to work on the specific goal.

Implement your strategy: In this case, three strategies should be implemented to implement the strategy.

1. Elicitation: Elicitation is process in which we discover the system Requirements, planning, non-functional requirements, document analysis and the prototyping. This is the most important step to implement a strategy within an organisation. In this step, we have to learn about the new environment in which a new strategy is going to be implement. We use usage critic strategy and the product critic strategy
2. Specification: It deals with the representing and storing the collecting requirement data in a persistent a well-organised fashion.
3. Validation: Validation is telling us you have correct set of data now you are able to implement the strategy according to the requirements. It gives us the green signal about the new strategy to be launched.

Control: Now the system has launched, it is necessary to keep the system maintain. Now this work is done by different department in an organisation which is supervised by the head, leader or manager.

2.13.1.1 What is Strategic Culture?

In organisation regardless of sector, there are objectives which have to be achieved through various means. In fact, operational, managerial and strategic activities are solely based on the pre-defined objectives of organisation which reflects the motive of organisation. Objectives in any organisation act as a guideline for employees and are dominated by strategic culture. Strategic culture refers to the beliefs, norms, working attitude of employees and experiences of organisation. If strategic culture is not suitable then clear objectives could not be achieved even due to strategic cultural impact on employee's performances. At workplaces, culture can be moulded but it requires serious efforts by senior management as culture is developed by the

passage of time and it can also be changed but its time-consuming process. Several issues arise due to negative culture which dominates employee's behaviour. Moreover, employee's personal beliefs and experiences also contribute in overall culture whereas leaders also play role in shaping the culture. In fact, leaders are the primary actors in changing the culture and they also act as a primary factor in damaging the culture.

Robert, (2008) says in his book that formulation of policies, measures and strategies at workplaces influence the culture at workplace which must be changed by time to time to keep organisations in healthy condition otherwise inappropriate strategies may also jeopardize the existence of organisation. According to Solaja et al. (2016), changing strategic culture requires skilled leaders and managers which must possess necessary skills including techniques and strategies to change the culture without compromising the success of organisation. Indeed, resistances come when culture is being changed.

2.13.1.2 Types of culture

There are several types of culture which influence on organisation and senior managers must be skilled enough to change all the types of culture as per requirement. In societal type, culture is shaped by employees and the society in which it operates. When organisations hire employees, every employee brings a sort of personal beliefs, norms and expectations at workplace which impacts on the implementation of strategies and policies of organisations to a great extent. Abraham (2012) says that every employee has its own objectives and motivation which drives their behaviour at workplaces. For example, when an individual believes that work balance life is important then over time policy may affect the behaviour of such individuals. There are several techniques which are used by senior managers to assess societal culture at workplace which includes personal interviews, assessing changes in behaviour of employees by evaluating their performances and monitoring their behaviours secretly.

Another type is organisational type which is shaped by the strategies, policies and activities of senior managers at workplace. Employees develop some sort of behavioural norms by the passage of time due to several factors like leadership style and HR policies. Such behavioural norms develop over a period of time and can be changed but it requires serious efforts by senior managers. If senior managers are not skilled then formulation of strategies and policies may result in negative behavioural norms development among employees which give serious consequences. Indeed, development of HR policies against motivational factors of employees may result in negative behavioural norms which affect employee's performances. Hence, it is necessary for organisation to hire skilled employees on decision making positions otherwise it

may affect the organisational culture where employees are not motivated to perform their task properly. Contextual intelligence is significant in employees to perform well in keeping organisational healthy and effective (Ravasi et al., 2006).

Critical evaluation skill is necessary to develop contextual intelligence skill which comes after gaining experiences at decision making positions. Critical evaluation skills come by solving real problems and this exercise is necessary at senior level positions. According to Heffernan (2005), HR officials are responsible to hire the right person, but skills are groomed by the passage of time as professional development is essential part of leadership and managerial roles. In organisation, decision making is essential part of any department, process and individual but when we talk about organisational culture then only such policies and strategies related to employees directly and indirectly are significant in shaping organisational culture. So, every senior manager must be skilled enough to formulate or take such decisions which favour employees. At last, industrial type culture is shaped by company's policies and code of conducts which differ by sector to sector but doesn't impact on employees.

2.13.1.4 Essentials for formulation of strategies

According to Ravasi et al. (2006) decision making is crucial in organisation, but it is not necessary that every decision gives positive outcome as it is the skill of decision maker to make appropriate and efficient decision. According to Watson (2012) effective decision solely depends on the skills of decision maker who must be aware of the requirement of decision type. Incremental type strategies are made as per the market changes which create gaps and engender new requirements like innovations. Incremental strategies give desired outcome when they are designed by analysing the past or using benchmarking technique in which senior managers compare the strategies of rivals and their results. Incremental strategies have significant impact on overall organisations, so such strategies are designed after taking all stakeholders in confidence. Furthermore, decision makers must have analytical skills to make incremental strategies and in order to do so, using of analytical models and tools is necessary for decision makers in organisations.

Some strategies impact on organisational culture in which most of the strategies are related to HR whereas leadership styles and some strategies, followed by managers to handle workforce also impact on organisational culture. Senior managers must be skilled enough to choose appropriate leadership style and develop such policies which promote organisational culture instead of destabilizing the existing one (Abigail, 2012). According to Hassan (2013) senior managers must be skilled in using different techniques and methods like survey, one to one

interview, assessing employee's feedback through informal events and cultural audit to assess the culture before making such strategies.

2.13.1.5 Cultural Audit process

Cultural audit refers to the analysis of the culture before making any decision to change it. Culture in organisation play vital role in making companies successful and unsuccessful on long run and it must be audited by time to time as per needs. Cultural audit is a detailed process in which analytical models are helpful and 4 perspectives are considered while doing cultural audit. Such perspectives include competitive situation, business strategy, organisational structure as well as culture and leadership styles. It is mandatory for decision makers to understand the cultural audit process to keep it balanced. In fact, imbalanced culture doesn't give desired outcome and deteriorate the whole process of organisations which eventually liquidate organisations.

2.13.1.6 Strategic Models and Analytical models

There are several analytical and strategic models which are popular and are mostly used by strategist in businesses. Every model has its own usage and importance in strategic planning and management. Such models play vital role at the time of analysis and formulation of strategies as such models covers all important factors and perspectives. In banking fields, managers do analysis by using strategic analytical models like SWOT, PESTLE and Porters five forces. Strategic models are used to formulate strategies as per need and requirement of the situation. Appropriate usage of each model is essential to get the benefits otherwise it may deteriorate the whole process or make formulated strategy ineffective in dealing a particular issue. Contextual intelligence is required to practise analytical and strategically models.

According to Reigle (2001), employees at senior positions must know all analytical and strategic models to make efficient and effective decision. Every model doesn't cover all perspectives but covers essentials ones which must be used at a time as per need otherwise incomplete analysis would lead decision to failure. It is not necessary to use all models, but it is fact that decision makers must use different models as per need which covers the required areas for deciding.

Theoretical knowledge can be attained easily by studying the pros and cons of analytical and strategic models, but appropriate use can only be achieved by using such models in practical. It is quite common in giant firms to use assignment-based approach as part of training and development to give practical approach of using analytical and strategic models. (Hasan, 2013)

2.13.1.7 Four important theories related to strategist

Prescriptive Theory

This theory refers to the situations which are handled through prescribed solutions, designed by senior management in organisations. This theory believes that things or strategies must be defined clearly before any situation occurs, so management can respond instantly as per prescribed guideline. In strategic management, this theory is followed to avoid delays in decision making and control subordinate decision making at crucial stages by giving them clear guidance. This theory is opposed for many reasons which include ignorance of unexpected events, negate requirement of skilled employees to make effective decision and avoid risk taking by employees which suppress their confidence. Hence, this theory is important in daily decision-making process and advocate the requirement of training of problem-solving skills among senior management who are responsible to develop pre-define solutions (Pi and Huang, 2011).

Descriptive Theory

This theory is like prescription in the sense that senior management use this theory to develop solutions but in descriptive manner by explaining each factor separately and also take help by analysing the past incidents. The formulated solutions according to this theory cover multiple dimensions of single issue by covering all impacting factors. This theory advocates the need of problem solving plus research methodology skills for senior management to analyse the problem first before applying any solution.

Emergent Theory

This theory supports unusual events and continuous change management in order to make effective decision rather than sticking to on course of actions like descriptive and perspective. This theory is used by those organisations that operate in complex environment where market is not stable. This theory is used rarely by organisations but studied as one of the core theories of strategic management. Organisations use scenario-based approach to train employees which develop skills to deal with unusual events and make them capable at least to make efficient as well as effective decisions (Hamza, 2012).

Complexity Theory

This theory refers to unusual events but in the matter of factors instead do situations. This theory believes that management should be skilled enough to mould or alter strategies as per need by analysing the impact of different factors at the time of occurrence rather than relying on pre-define solutions like in descriptive theory. It is fact that sometimes factors behave in

different way due to other factors in different situations which makes complex for senior managers to pre-define the strategy to deal with such factors according to past situational analysis. Complex situation is managed by such employees who are skilled in solving scenario-based problems.

2.13.1.8 Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is a theory as well as a broad subject which covers several areas which includes cost efficiency and exploitation of resources. Knowledge management refers to the value adding in services and products through various means. Managing knowledge within organisation has become crucial for survival in harsh competition where things get changed frequently like changing in consumer's buying behaviour. Knowledge is further divided into two subgroup which are explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge is in written form like business intelligence which is utilized by all employees as per need in decision making.

Explicit knowledge is gathered through business software's and different strategies as well as practices which is useful for senior management in decision making. In fact, gathering business intelligence is a skill which is essential for management in organisation. Tacit knowledge is codified into employee's brain which is transferred through training and teaching. Employees have personal reservations in transferring their skills and knowledge into newcomers or unskilled employees, but it can manage tactically through effective strategies in which HR play vital role. (Hamza, 2012)

2.13.1.9 Resource Based View

This theory is known as RBV theory which says that companies must use such resources which cannot be imitated easily by rivals and adds value in quality of service or product. Resources could be tangible like labour and machinery and intangible like brand recognition. Companies do joint ventures and strategic alliance sometimes to exploit resources in other countries which also refer to RBV theory. RBV says that it is fact that resources are imitated but unique ones make difficult for rivals to imitate like Apple company uses its own mobile software's which cannot be imitated easily. RBV theory promotes innovation in technologies and strategies which needs skilled employees who are capable enough to think innovatively and bring uniqueness in services and products. Organisations use training courses to develop innovative skills which help employees to innovate as well as do incremental changes by analysing the market and consumer's behaviour.

2.13.1.10 Transaction Cost

This theory says that companies can become capable to provide quality service or product in low cost when they are capable enough to manage their transaction cost which includes marketing cost, distribution cost, operational cost, production cost and other cost. There are several business phenomena which are considered by organisation to achieve cost efficiency. Indeed, profit orientated organisation can only maintain quality in low cost when they get cost efficiency.

2.13.2 The Human Resource Management and the Development

Human Resource management is responsible to address employee's grievances and concern. There are several things that are managed by HR officials in organisations in which reward management is one of the core areas which has huge impact on overall performances of organisation regardless of sector (Thompson, 2002). The employees are the key advantage in the organisations in achieving authorized goals that are regularly associated with productivity (Teece, 2010).

Human resources are such a department that is responsible for all the things related to workers. Nowadays the development, growth, and training of individuals are also there. There are many roles and responsibilities of the human resource department in any sector. Bangladesh is a developing economy and each of its departments is working clearly in light of strategies. The key responsibilities of the banking sector are made clear. The human resource of financial institutions does its working in light of the key roles. Human resource is not a very old concept in Bangladesh, all the theories are not practiced yet. The research is still going on. However organisational performance can certainly be increased if there is an implementation of proper human resource strategies. The importance and benefit of HR are widely understood by now. Learning HR objectives will help to meet the objectives of worldwide research.

The banking industry of Bangladesh is not very developed yet, there are only 26 banks and 4 Islamic banks. Leasing companies, insurance companies, and commercial banks are very designed and decorative in their perspectives. The role of each financial institution is different in society. The central bank of Bangladesh i.e. BB is taking measures that each banking institution must know the role of HR in improving the performance of this sector. Financial institutions may guarantee the economic success of any country. Human capital can reduce the financial risks to the economy by applying their skills. Skilful human potential maximums return on investments, it finds ways to make more secure investments. Human resource departments of banking industry have different roles, it does contribute to organisational

development, performance conduct, maintain industrial competition and standards organizes training sessions, implement policies and supervise all kinds of implementation no matter it is in bottom level employees or upper management. Bangladesh is such a country where extended relationships based on family basis affect the recruitment process. There is an employee on a senior level which is very interrelated to one another in terms of families. Most of the workers are spontaneous, powerless, and less organized (Ali, 2011). Lack of institutional capacity has given way to a lot of other loopholes. Human skills, development, and training are ignored factors until now. A few years back the need for HR has been realized in the institutions and this has led to audio visual techniques of training. Another kind of training is also introduced which is known as vestibule training. The promotion criteria have been revised, now the promotional criteria are knowledge, skill, and ability instead of relationships. The performance appraisal criteria have been revised by the government, target fulfilling, and behaviour of employees are important determinants in appraisals. However organisational performance criteria are still lagging as there are a lot of chances of corruption in the banks. The system is neither transparency nor answerable unethical practices have been reduced in public banks, but HR of the private sector still lags in providing a proper ethical framework to the private sector. HR needs to focus on it (Aldridge, 2003).

The need for HR and development in the region is unavoidable especially in this sector because few attributes are required among employees to beat the international market. Banks's store sensitive information of people, there is valuable cash present with them. From executive to teller's whole financial institution staff must show a high level of integrity and trustworthiness. Applicant's screening can help to reduce the financial frauds and criminal backgrounds of people. Fierce competition and regal compliance require such a person on the executive post who can control all the happenings and who is well aware of all the happenings (Ho Han, 2017). In non-profit organisations, they seek care in which they receive remuneration commensurate with their obligations in the generally organisational execution (Armstrong, 2007)

To be honest, compensation is the essential point of every person who works, both in un-paid organisations and in the organisations with benefits. The reward management refers to managing the appropriate approaches, methods, and reward practices to attract potential competitors and inspire agents to avoid problems related to the staff turnover. Organisations must express a strong need for all immediate and lagging variables, while making reward management related guidelines. These factors have a tremendous impact on the reward management, as they make the reward framework successful.

The Business Drivers

Productivity

This driver promotes the feasibility and profitable use of the reward framework. Productivity is achieved by the employment of the right individuals because the determination outside the base of the individuals can endanger the companies' reward framework. The companies can acquire skills to meet the right expectations through a successful procurement process and powerful advertising. This driver ought not to be disregarded when planning reward approaches because the reward framework is for the right people to get what they deserve based on their participation. Recruitment skills or training is essential to hire the right people which include several techniques and methods like personality trait models.

Clear Vision

It could affect the execution or viability of the reward framework in companies. The companies must take on a number of clearly anticipated responsibilities and ensure that prospective employees understand them before hiring them in companies. Handwritten contracts with a direct job detail and a mental contract with the workers are necessary. If the employees do not fully understand their activities, the results of the evaluation of the performance are undoubtedly negative, which could affect the compensation arrangements (Armstrong, 2007). Job description is a term which used for clear vision business driver in companies which is also a skill which must be inherited in Hr officials otherwise companies have to train them to write clear JDs.

The relationship

It is an indication of the appropriateness of the compensation framework. The relationship between employer and workers is very important to the success of the reward structure. In general, a bad relationship leads to a fluctuation of the staff, although the reward structure is convincing. Companies need to build a strong partnership with employees about an important authority and fill in the gaps in correspondence between the employer and workers in developing a well-prepared workplace. Companies could express themselves through the organisation of occasional events as well as formal meetings where the employees do not hesitate to express their conclusions with the top management. Reducing communication gap is a skill which must be taught to all employees' especially to the senior management. Indeed, not every senior manager is equipped with such skills, but training may engender such skills in employees.

The objectives and significance of the reward intelligence

Reward intelligence increases in the rates of remuneration for new employment opportunities (Manus and Graham, 2003). It is practised for a particular recognition of the pay level or the explicit position. It also helps in the development of a compensation plan for the payment and the evaluation of capacity payments in the future will depend on the needs of the workforce. Reward intelligence is gathered by HR officials to inform the senior management in terms of the salary plan for enlisted or prospective employees and distinguish the salary range of the opponent as market models. For example, if the human resource officials have no idea what they are looking for, they would waste their time and money to get reward intelligence (Thomas, 2011).

The determinants of market compensation also play a significant role when reward intelligence is being gathered, in which the information is rewarded, through which organisations review or gain reliable rewards that identify the market or reference company based on size and Area. The management of companies is aware that they must assess the ability to moderation and visualization of goals before providing external or reliable personnel to collect rewarded knowledge (Thomas, 2011).

In addition, the determinants of the market payment rate could be size of the companies, the status, the range of companies and the capacity of companies play a central role in distinguishing the target market. The objective of collecting reward intelligence should be distinct and simple because the survey relies on it. The survey contains questions that are directly identified with the motivation behind the reward intelligence to compensate for the knowledge. For example, if the survey is about the level of monetary compensation paid to the employees by the rivals whereas the aim is to investigate the tax-free benefits offered by the adversaries then the collected data would be unusable (Manus and Graham, 2003).

There are various ways in which companies seek to reward intelligence that includes job alerts from various companies of comparable capacity and size, contributions from the present employee who has an aim to resign and salary surveys. Solid data is needed for a viable reward model that comes from trusted sources and contains general descriptions of third-party compensation and benchmarking practices. In addition, companies receive information from those employees who want to leave the company to discern the purpose of their departure. Of course, if employees want to leave the company at this time, there are some reasons to improve the salaries and benefits offered by their companies.

The total reward approaches

The reward system is based on procedures that increase the inspiration of agents and minimize the maintenance rate of workers. The reward technique must be placed to individual convincing elements that vary from worker to worker. To address the contrasts in the employees' Compelling Variables, this approach is practiced that is a combination of financial and non-monetary benefits. Workers must be involved if they find that the attractive structure is remunerated. The mentioned approach is identified with the entire class of the compensation strategy and there are some classifications of agreements as a fringe advantages strategy, payment execution strategy, motivated force mechanism, current momentum strategy, and approach based on competence and position agreement in the market. Such classifications are not part of this task (Armstrong, 2007).

Figure redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Armstrong, M. (2007) *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. 7th ed. London: Kogan Page.

Figure 2: Total Reward Model, Source: Armstrong, 2007

The organisational culture, business processes, and human asset techniques are critical to the total reward approach. Total Reward covers alternative perspectives, healthy work, performance, execution, recognition and enhancement, and career opportunities. These opinions are considered when creating complete reward approaches to attract and retain employees. It is not easy to create an attractive method of absolute reward because internal and external research is required before the distinctive component of the award is selected in a compensation strategy. Of course, the application of the Total Rewards Directive is a complex activity and a work force that can certainly solve the problems of all agents through tailored bonus packages (Armstrong, 2007).

Significant Principles

1st Principle: Reward strategies and practices must be based on business objectives, as it is very important to take advantage of the compensation framework. For SHRM, it is important to alert workers to their responsibilities and their contribution to achieving commercial goals. In fact, employees must understand the goals and objectives of the business so that they can analyse their efforts against predefined business goals (Armstrong, 2007). The SHRM needs to develop a clear vision through various forms, such as: a clear view of the season of recruiting new workers and advising employees in formal and informal meetings. If employees have no idea of the goals and objectives of the company, their performances may be judged inadequate.

2nd Principle: The reward approaches and practices should be aligned with the culture of a company, which is crucial for the long-term development of organisations. SHRM may develop such approaches to monitor skills from time to time and create future leaders that could create a positive impact on culture. It is the duty of HR officials to promote pay for performance culture by using such measures to assess the performances of employees according to the pre-set benchmarks. Equity principle is essential to keep the workforce motivated which says that targets must be achievable and distribution of responsibilities of employees must be on fair basis as well as equal.

3rd Principle: Maintaining competitive rates is necessary to retain employees and influence them time to time through reward intelligence. This principle is basically consistency principle in which reward system is improved consistently to keep the workforce motivated. In fact, rivals could easily attract employees of other companies through competitive rates and retention issues deteriorate overall company's performances. According to the regulation regarding working time, employees have to pay extra time to his employees for long working.

4th Principle: Rewarding people according to their participation is just as important to keep them motivated. For example, Tesco grants additional premiums to individuals who participate beyond their normal obligations and duties because occasionally when an individual person performs or shows more than the normal or required effort (Tesco, 2018). In such situations when any individual is rewarded for his or her contribution which is more than the obligation but he or she is rewarded as per pre-set rewards then such individual gets de motivated. In fact, rewards should be consistent with the contribution of employees. This rule refers to the

consistency in which SHRM should indicate consistency in awarding the award based on commitment and extra efforts (Biswas et al., 2013).

5th Principle: Fairness is essential to attract and persuade workers, with the value and commitment of all employees appreciated and exercised with little respect for position and prejudice. If employees feel that the reward system is not fair, and they are not being treated equally then such employees may get de motivated. There is also a law regarding the rule of decency, as envisaged by the Equality Act of 2010, both men as well as women receive the settlement payment for the similar work.

The Reward practices and policies' Implementation

The use of compensation practices and approaches depend on the detailed procedure, and any progress has value and should not be overlooked. The following are the key advances organisations need to make. First, organisations need to analyse the elements which might influence their approaches and reward practices that involve all internal as well as external components. Secondly, bring in confidence all stakeholders at the time of making compensation strategies and practices. Then, companies need to identify the prerequisites skills for achieving business goals. Companies need a reward intelligence to define compensation strategies and practices that must be achieved through reliable methods. If organisations are financially sound, they must carry out the survey which is important and must be designed in accordance with required skills to do job analysis (CIPD, 2018).

Organisations must submit a technical reward report, which is essential to bring the compensation system and plan of practices into a composite and essential structure to get it approved by senior management. This register covers all the justifications for the formulation of reward related strategies and policies by considering all the factors that impact on overall company's performances. This file contains all important data on reward related approaches and practices. Such data may include qualification criteria to ensure an explicit premium, an explicit benefit expenditure plan, and other basic benefits. Organisations should provide this report to employees so that they understand what they would get against their efforts and participations. Organisations need to make sure that each reward strategies and practices are in line with regulations and aligned with corporate objectives and social delivery. Organisations must make sure that all drivers of the organisation are available to confirm the smooth

implementation of agreements and remuneration practices. Undoubtedly, the inertia of key business drivers could influence the appropriateness of the compensation framework to achieve business objectives.

Finally, organisations must establish correspondence arrangements which from time to time communicate to all partners the results and appropriateness of the compensation approaches and practices. Investors will see the benefits of these reward strategies for them, even though supervisors recognize how to functionally update or implement these reward approaches and practices. From time to time, organisations must monitor and evaluate the appropriateness of compensation strategies to ensure that agreements and practices contribute to the development of companies and tradeshows (CIPD, 2018).

Line Managers' roles regarding reward guidelines and practices

It is worthwhile to refer here VROOM theory. This is usually used by supervisors to determine the pay for the practice, in which supervisors set goals to demonstrate the degree of hope of the company. This theory says that supervisors could motivate the workers by setting up the targets with high expectations which they can achieve in practical. Supervisors could set monetary and non-financial rewards based on the goals and level of engagement of the workers (Kuvass, 2009). The instrumental part gives burden to the employees to achieve the goals and to get the salaries pre-determined by the supervisors or line managers.

During the valence phase, employees get attracted towards the reward system, designed by the line managers if they find it attractive as per their motivational factors. If a person is attracted through training and development opportunity then line managers could not attract such person through bonus reward (Northouse, 2004). Line managers could utilize the Balanced Scorecard, which is a crucial part of HR in organisations which is comprised of different strategies related to different departments in organisations. Each department or we can say area in BSC is comprised of pre-set performance indicators in terms of objectives and required level of performance. Such indicators are known as KPIs which assist line managers in performance evaluation of employees. It was formed by Robert Kaplan and David Norton to help line managers communicate clear organisational goals to employees through the BSC.

Line managers could use Balanced score card which is comprised of business strategies and cover all necessary areas of organisations like finance and customer service. Each are having its own key performance indicators and they are pre-set indicators. Line manage could evaluate the performances of employees through those KPIs. It is developed by Robert Kaplan and

David Norton in 1992 to help line managers to communicate clear visions and goals of companies to employees through BSC (Norton, 2016).

Supervisors must do psychological contracts with newly appointed employees during the interview time and overwhelm newly hired workers to demonstrate their efforts and develop new skills by the passage of time. This is more of a composite contract and encourages workers to work according to the wishes of a supervisor.

Line managers need to give leverage and keep minimal control as a negligible consistency is essential for employee's learning. Line managers could also assist senior officials in identifying the new skills which are required to perform the new task or achieve the existing one. Such assistance makes senior officials capable to take decision to hire the right talent as per requirement and acquire useful information during reward intelligence phase. Line supervisors could use methods and hypothesis models of attributes such as the Myers model to differentiate hidden abilities and skills in employees. Such methods are useful for line managers to recommend those employees for non-monetary rewards like training and development as per their needs and seek approval from senior management with justification by showing the outcome of such methods (Baltoni, 2005).

Supervisors could produce an individual report on worker's performances against their duties and assigned tasks. Line managers develop job description which is comprised of the role and duties of employees and such report is handover to the employees at the time of hiring so they would know their responsibilities. Such report covers the weaknesses and strength of employees so that line managers could suggest senior management to provide necessary training to such employees who are not able to perform their duties efficiently (Norton, 2016).

Line managers are responsible to ensure friendly work environment which helps in reducing communication gaps among the employees and the senior management. It is necessary to create such environment as employees feel free to discuss their issues with the line managers, so such issues could be addressed on time. Line managers evaluate the quality of worker's work and suggest the senior management by time to time as line managers know better than the senior management and their suggestions are worthy for the senior management (Manus and Graham, 2003).

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Figure redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Armstrong, M. (2007) *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. 7th ed. London: Kogan Page.

Figure 3: VROOM Expectancy Theory; Source: Armstrong (2007)

2.13.3 Manner and Etiquettes

The importance of manners, conduct, policies, and etiquette cannot be ignored in the institution. The financial industry is a vulnerable one thus manner is adequately required in this sector. It deals with sensitive information as mentioned above due to which it requires different training of employees where they can depict high communication skills, etiquette, and manners. Bangladesh's financial institutions lack behind in global presence. There are fewer international banks present in the region due to which the cross-cultural manner issues are not yet met however to expand further it is inevitable to apply high manners and etiquettes (Ahmed, 2018). Most of the time, contemporary businesses do not follow all the manners they are supposed to follow. It is not just about courtesy and politeness, but it is about preparing about business meetings, representing the department at international level, organizing global and mutual meetings to enhance competitiveness, etc. greetings must not always be done culturally but in order to meet international delegations and international standards there is required such a training which help the individuals to meet global standards as well (Kour and Gakhar, 2015). Women often resist making the first-hand move thus such gestures which may show warm at one side may be causing irritability at the other. Thus, all staff members must learn communication skills and good manners to become more professional. Formal setups are required for this purpose and the head of the department must initiate the change not only in spoken but in overall manners. There is no space for absolute terms while performing your role

in a worthwhile organisation. The banking sector of Bangladesh is still in the learning phase, but it needs to have more attention to building relationships in Bangladesh the nonverbal cues are used (Hoffmann, 2014).

The verbal cues are not very much used to build relationships, especially in the business and banking sectors. The serious and silent environment is observed to show devotion and sincerity with the work. So is the case with the banking environment. The purpose of official etiquette is to give proper shape to some relationships. Manners are usually a happy and courteous way of doing things. The official language is Bengali and thus people do use this language while communicating with one another. Due to this language barrier, there is an issue to enhance working at a global level. The skills of people in communication are not developed enough. There is a benefit of developing communication skills to widen the scope of working.

There is a proper official schedule that must be made clear to all the people to avoid disturbances. There are office houses to meet customers whoever there are proper office hours to perform the official worker by workers (Bhuiyan et al., 2015). The workers of financial institutions have to act like a salesperson when it comes to attracting customers and they have to work as management as well to perform all official tasks related to paperwork, budgeting, etc. there are few busiest hours such as Friday afternoons because of arriving holidays. All such things must be made clear to staff and special instructions must be given for Friday and Monday as these are the busiest working days most of the time. Sometimes the etiquettes are even in written form i.e. policies and conduct. No matter it is a manner of dress or job interview all etiquettes are cleared (Ho Han, 2017).

In organisations, employees are internal customers which must be satisfied to make actual customer satisfy. In fact, unhappy employees don't give desired performances even if they are taught manners as a part of training (Chen et al., 2015). Manners and Etiquettes can be taught but cannot be forced as satisfaction of employees pay significant role in compelling employees to treat customers mannerly. Motivation is remarkable for the commitment of the employee and this is achieved by external as well as intrinsic elements. Those components vary employee to employee. This is one of the main responsibilities of human resource department to formulate such a reward system that keeps the employees motivated. Extrinsic factors are given high priority sometimes by employees as compared to intrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors include self-esteem and such factors which gives inner satisfaction to employees. There is need to assess the motivational level of each employee and understanding of intrinsic and extrinsic factors are necessary for HR officials as well as senior managers and leaders.

Taylor's theory believes that financial rewards are vital in keeping workers motivated as when employees receive compensation based on their contribution which refers to performance-based pay then it may cause and create complex issues between the employees and the employer when they cannot achieve the goals. Such employees could be handled through effective and tight control. The Taylor's theory sees employees as a production source (Kuvass, 2009).

The approach of Maslow states that each worker is motivated by external and internal elements. It is conceivable that the worker is simultaneously awakened by external factors and intrinsic factors. As per this method, the motivational factor is divided into:

- Self esteem
- Social need
- Psychological needs
- Safety needs

These classes are suitable as a violin and any employee price or offer requires an explicit classification in the pyramid. The authorities of human goods examine the inspirational elements of the people and put together a personalized package for all workers, which retains the entire remuneration mix.

As per Alton's Mayo approach, workers need rewards that will reliably lead them to do their best, even if they do not receive competitive payments. This experiment not only supports the perspective of trust, but also the empowerment, closeness, and sense of being appreciated at the workplace (Kuvass, 2009).

Figure 4: Maslow Model; Source: Kuvass, 2009

In earlier theories, Taylor was rejected because SHRM offered the need for a human connection to creation, although the Maslow and Alton are widely used. This is the duty of supervisors to differentiate between the persuasive variables of the employees and to train the top management so that they can create compensation arrangements and jobs according to these components.

Another example is that Famous airline prior to the 2003 Battle of Heathrow, the British airline was founded on the strength of the close relationship between business and employees. Of course, non-financial bonuses create a good relationship between the supervisor and the workers. Kellogg's follows Maslow's approach as it organize events frequently in every 3 to 4 months to bring the employees and the senior management close to each other to reduce communication gap and develop future leadership development by promoting knowledge sharing through informal events (Kelloggs, 2018). Tesco accepts that the reward, which is not associated with money, such as the possibility of development, requires substantial work to inspire the employees and authorized authoritarian execution. Tesco offers existing workers the opportunity to apply for a vacancy if they qualify to apply under Tesco's internal contracts (Tesco, 2018).

2.13.4 The Public Private Partnership

Public private partnership involves collaboration between public and a private sector agency that can be used to finance, operate and build projects such as mobile networks, bank, schools etc. Long term contractual relationship between private agency and the public sector (from 3 to 25 years). In public and private partnership, they both combined to achieve the solution of the complex problem not any simple problem. Public and private partnership brings value of money especially for the public sector company.

Managing resistances of employees

When organisations merge with other organisations or they do joint venture with other companies then it is obvious that resistance come from the employees that should be managed efficiently otherwise the initiative of starting new business or partnership fails (Abigail, 2012). It is one of the primary skills of senior management and first step towards the initiative of setting up new partnership or acquisition. Mergers and joint ventures also merge cultures of different organisations which create cultural issues. So, managing resistances through detailed

process is a first step to develop favourable working environment to practise other approaches like employee engagement.

Usually, Kottler model is practiced managing resistances which must be known by line managers and leaders to conduct successful managing resistance practice. First of all, line managers need to create urgency at workplace via formal meetings or notice boards to inform the employees regarding the future cultural changes by initiating new partnership or merging with other companies (Belias, 2014).

Organizing events or meeting is not good enough until the message is conveyed efficiently which is a skill in fact. This step enforces employees to start thinking in advance about the future changes which helps in making their minds. Secondly, make employees satisfied by convincing them that the initiative is in the favour of company's interest. Communication skills play vital role in convincing employees. Coalition is also depending on the communication skills in which line managers bring all senior employees in confidence who have good goodwill at workplaces.

There are few techniques, used by line managers to clear the vision of new initiatives like benchmarking and mapping method. At last, empowering employees to some extent so they can perform their task conveniently and this step is one of the steps of employee engagement. In banking sector, when banks merge with other banks or establish any new business unit with other banks then cultural issues come to a great extent. There are two most important areas which have direct and indirect impact on managing cultural issues which includes managing employees' resistances and engage employees (Desai, 2010)

Like everything else, employees are a key resource for every organisation and act as internal customers who must be satisfied to ensure quality in their service. Employee Engagement has been proved as a fundamental commercial phenomenon to achieve numerous benefits, including maintaining the employees, performing simple operational activities, achieve efficiency in performances as the engaged workforce knows the goals of organisation.

Hence, EE has become significant for the survival for organisations. There are three types of EE that are intellectual engagement, affective engagement, and social engagement. In intellectual, employees try to use their intellectual efforts in achieving the targets. In affective, employees keep positive remarks regarding the employer and are emotionally attached. In social, employees try to bring improvements in solutions and performances with mutual understanding with each other at workplace (Desai, 2010). It is necessary to train senior

manager regarding each EE type as each type has its own factors, process, methods and techniques which are practised by senior managers to engage the workforce. There are several concepts which seem like EE, but they are in reality. Such concepts are organisational commitment, employee's involvement, and job satisfaction. The difference must be known by senior managers, so they don't mingle them as they are all different in terms of meaning and impact (Attridge, 2009).

Job Satisfaction and Employee Engagement

Job satisfaction is considered first area which must be achieved in order to achieve EE. Companies need to find an attractive compensation framework based on convincing speculation and assessment of the person's inspirational components. In fact, each individual is motivated by different elements, although employee involvement is only possible if the employees are satisfied with their job (Abraham, 2012). For example, James work as a sales employee and his key motivational factors includes flexible hours and paid holidays, while actual working hours are tight, and the company does not pay for holidays. James works for this company because he is not getting a job anywhere else whereas his employer offers him some other non-monetary rewards but still, he is not satisfied.

Organisational Commitment and the Employee Engagement

The organisational commitment alludes to the behaviour of the employee towards the work and the employer, which influences the overall performances of organisations. Deployed employees routinely get to work, meet deadlines, and work hard to satisfy the company's desire, or we can say walk extra miles for company's satisfaction. Committed employees are considered valuable assets as well as loyal with their leaders, who compel them to stay long (Abraham, 2012). Organisational commitment covers employee behaviour and employer behaviour. In EE, employees work for themselves to satisfy their self-esteem and professional passion whereas in organisational commitment, the behaviour of employer play vital role in making employees loyal to some extent. Indeed, OC is necessary to achieve EE as misbehaviour of senior management and unfair treatment could result in retention of employees even when the reward system is attractive.

Engaged employees always seek opportunities in the market and leave the employer as soon as they get better options form the rivals whereas committed employees think hundreds of times to leave the employer due to commitment. As a matter of fact, only committed employees are

not useful for organisations until they become engaged. Moreover, engaged employees become committed but it is not easy for senior management to make them committed. Commitment of employees solely depend on their personal traits which make them committed and such traits includes giving high importance to loyalty (Normative commitment) and feel job insecurity (Continuance commitment). For example, a female speaker, working for a university creates opportunities and challenges in college because of his enthusiasm for such exercises. He is a devotee and keeps herself busy in researching new research topics, but she doesn't show interest in other university matters. In fact, she is engaged employees in fact and could leave the university once she gets a good opportunity as she loves her work but not loyal with her employer.

Employee Engagement and Employee Involvement

EE and EI are two different concepts but are indirectly interrelated as EI comes from EE but EI is advance concept of EE in which employees become caring regarding employer and always strive to serve better to avoid extra cost and loss. In EE, employees work for employer with passion but stick to the guideline and their obligations. In EE, employees strive for betterment but don't keep concern regarding consequences. We can say that in EI, employees act as shareholders. EI is achieved when there are some personal traits which enforce employees to involve themselves. For instance, when two employees are given the same task and specific time of 3 days to complete the task then involved employee could finish the task in 2 days because of involvement whereas engaged employee could finish the task on the specific time (Rogers, 2012).

The Key Drivers and the Employee Engagement Steps

Employees are an important resource for every organisation nowadays. Today it is a commercial phenomenon to achieve the effectiveness and profitability in intense competition. There are several factors in businesses which impact on overall performances of businesses and should be considered in order to avoid derail of business process and failure of strategies. Every external and internal factor has its own impact and role in driving EE which can be diagnosed through different methods and tools by line managers to create engagement environment.

➤ Organisational culture, Lucrative incentives and Support

According to Ramabadron et al. (1997), employees seek help or favour from their seniors on crucial stages especially as it is quite common at workplace. It is fact that support from senior's

management bring confidence in employees and enforce them to become engaged. Organisational culture is comprised of senior management behaviour, leadership styles, regulations and working environment which are paramount for EE at workplace. Lucrative incentive is also the key driver to drive employee's motivation and also an important component of reward system.

➤ **Total Reward System, the fair treatment and empowerment**

According to Sahu et al. (2018), total reward strategy is a key player in establishing engaged environment at workplace which includes work balance life concept, flexibility in working condition, recognition of good performance and future development opportunities. Designing reward strategy is detailed process and skill which must be taught to responsible official otherwise unattractive reward system results in loss of money and time. Prasana (2010) argued that even when companies have attractive reward system, if they don't treat their employees fairly, then employee engagement could not be possible. Empowerment is also a key driver, but it drives the motivation of selected employees who wants to be empowered. In fact, being empowered depends on the personal traits of employees but play key role in establishing engaged environment. According to Tahir et al. (2014), autonomy is similar to empowered, but it is practiced in broad aspect by giving free hand to some extent to every employee whereas empowerment is practiced in limited aspect by empowering only supervisors and experienced employees. Autonomy brings confidence in employee and makes them feel valued at workplace.

➤ **Meaningfulness of a job**

According to Krishnan (2011), meaningfulness of a job is extremely significant in order to make other drivers workable in which an employer makes its employees aware of the importance of their contributions. Employees must be aware as well as give value to the assigned task otherwise they don't engage themselves completely in the assigned task. Mapping strategy is one of the strategies which assist line managers to create value for the assigned work in which they show the importance of their contribution in achieving the objectives of companies through a picture.

➤ **Personal characteristics of employees:**

Involvement of employee is not in the hands of the manager who can make them satisfied through key success factors, but it is also achieved by the willingness and ability of the workers.

If in reality, an employee is not competent enough to achieve the objectives and to avail the opportunities benefit then senior management could not play any role (Popli, 2015). According to trait theory, human resource agencies should use the "trait theory tools" to determine the skills level as well as the capabilities of employees which are essential to do the work before hiring them. In fact, skills and capabilities of employees could ruin the entire reward system and gives negative consequences like failure of businesses. In practice, usage of tools, related to trait theory is a skill which must be known by HR officials (Srivastava and Bhatnagar, 2008).

➤ **Cooperation, Job design and transformational leadership style**

Job design is significant to keep the employees motivated and encourage them to keep themselves on track while providing quality performances. Job design tells the goals and gave clear vision to employees, so they can perform in certain direction to make their contribution in overall growth of companies. Besides job design, cooperation is also essential among employees and employer, so employees don't feel hesitation while expressing their personal views. Moreover, transformational leadership play extremely important role in engaging employees psychologically in their work, so they do better perform their task (Sahu et al., 2018).

Alignment of the worker engagement practices with organisational elements

Alignment of different elements of organisation like technology is essential to make the tools effective in achieving employee engagement. Such tools include Utrecht Work Engagement Scale, general survey and hybrid Survey. Alignment of different departments by selecting some officials from each department in organisation assist in the analyses of EE is beneficial as several minds are better than few ones. It is not necessary that only HR officials can analysis and share their views on EE practices but alignment of different experienced people from different department is necessary. Alignment of technical side is also significant like designing of a mobile app which is used to give feedbacks by the employees on EE practices. This is important for senior management to train their employees if they are not to align different organisational elements to get the maximum of EE tools and techniques. Furthermore, using of internet facility by creating internet group chatting place where employees could share their views. Alignment of leadership style and financial department is essential as sometimes suitable leadership style is required to make EE practices successful otherwise inappropriate leadership style could ruin all the efforts of HR. Sometime, EE practices require financial

support on large scale like organizing training and development for employees and formulating new non-monetary rewards (Ravasi et al., 2006).

Diagnostic tools for the measurement of employee engagement

➤ The General Surveys

General survey is costly option for organisations which is carried out by third party which could be any survey company. The most important thing in survey making is the formulation of the questions which should be formulated in accordance with the company's requirement. The length of the survey depends so the company's requirement and it could be done once in a year as it is costly, but the result can be used in future surveys. The limitation includes misleading potential to the analyst as sometimes people don't share their actual views. It is one of the core skills of HR officials (Jena, 2017).

➤ The Hybrid Questionnaire

This is similar to the general survey, but those surveys are explicitly structured in accordance with specific issues or requirements like employee performances in sales. Such surveys can be carried out several times as per need by organisations. Hybrid survey is also known as pulse survey that could be analysed only by psychometric in organisations. In fact, being psychometric is vital for the analyst to analyse the result as hybrid surveys are complex as compared to general survey (Purcell, 2010).

➤ Utrecht Work Engagement Scale

It was designed by Wilmer, who conducted the test with nine questions with a scale of nine which helped him to analyse the employee engagement. The questions are based on three classes that are listed below:

1. Vigor
2. Dedication
3. Absorption

It can be utilized both as a general and a pulse survey.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is from Ress, 2013. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 5: UWES Data Analysis

Source: Ress, 2013

➤ **Gallup Workplace Audit**

It is bit like Utrecht survey, but it focuses areas depends on the company's requirements. The survey is comprised of 12 questions which covers all important areas like absenteeism, profitability, and employee turnover. The questions are pre-set, and it could be carried out multiple times in a year as its not costly and usually done by companies themselves (Gopal, 2006).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Gopal, A. (2006) *Worker disengagement continues to cost Singapore*, *The Gallup Management Journal*. [Online] Available at: <http://gmj.gallup.com/content/default.aspx?ci=22720andpg=1>

Figure 6: Gallup Workplace Audit; Source: Gopal, 2006

➤ **Financial tool named as ROI:**

ROI stands for return on investment which not only assists in financial ratio analysis but also in analysis of employee engagement. Investment is a significant and core part of any business whether it is related to marketing, distribution or customer services. Engaged employees give superior performances which impact on overall profitability and performances of companies. It increases ROI ratio automatically when employees are engaged so such ratios could also be used to assess their level of engagement. Analysis of the financial ratios is a skill which must be known not only by finance professionals but also by HR and marketing employees (Prasanna, 2013).

➤ **Interviews**

This technique is used when any employees intend to leave the employer due to hidden facts and reasons which are analysed by HR officials through formal interview by asking them cross questions. The cross questions must be designed efficiently and are solely depends on the skills of HR officials or line managers.

➤ **Formal and informal weekly meetings'**

In order to gain insight into the hidden factors and reasons which enforce employees to leave, line managers and HR officials do formal and informal meetings in which they ask questions

related to motivational factors then analyse the hidden facts according to the replies of such employees.

➤ **The Focus Groups**

Focus groups refer to online software or website platforms where employees interact with each other including the senior management which gives insights regarding employee's mind to the senior management. Such insights are used during the analysis of employee engagement. Companies can hire specifically to monitor the focus groups otherwise it can be used or practised by any senior line manager to assess the level of such employees who work under their control.

2.13.5 Core Risk Management

Bank system is always been a risk. A big amount is always there, and every transaction is now based on internet. Now days due to the cyber-crimes, online bank robbery (hacking) is now very common in all over the world. Hundreds of banks have losses billions of dollars due to the online crimes in the banks. In 2003, 930\$ million were stolen from the BB. Some incidents happened in America, some are in Spain and there are too many incidents happen in rest of the world. So that's why we said that bank is always on the risk and this risk is so dangerous as it leads to the poverty level of the country. Now the question comes in the mind that how can we handle this type of risks in our business organisation or especially in the bank because people saved there their lifetime saving.

There are 4 main methods to manage the risks in the bank. This is so necessary otherwise due to cybercrimes there is always a risk. Following methods are recommended to solve the risks. Policy Guideline: Investment should be included industry and the business segments focus on the investment limit and the caps. Investment assessment should be included related industry, borrower, supplier, past performance as well as regularity and doubtful and bad and loss. Internal audit should perform their duty as per guideline.

Organisational structure and responsibilities: Organisational structure and responsibilities are designed that avoid conflict in an organisation. It can be said that there is a conflict manager or conflict management system in an organisation. Investment approval and investment authority should be a separated department. According to the organisation risk management and the investment administration the division must be perform separate duty.

Procedural Guideline: An organisational structure must perform the following steps:

Approval of the investment and any other funding investment should be done within the business dictionary power. Investment administration should ensure the proper and complete documentation of the investment paper. Banks should activate continuous monitoring system for the smooth operation of the accounts. Investment handler department should be done proper documentation and fulfil regulatory requirements.

2.13.6 Advanced course of Leadership

The true leader is he who always stand on the action and the stick to his principle, a business strategy, a unique product boosting plan, a unique product development roadmap, a well-mannered marketing campaign even when the rest of the world is criticising you that why you are not marching in the steps of a status quo. In other words, leaders are happy to zig while others are zag. The leader is who stand up in the front of the leader and defend his team and project work and show them to all who used to criticize him that nothing is impossible.”

Bank is one of the biggest organisations of a country and it is managed by a leader call “Manager”. Who handles all the stockholders, invest his money give people all functional and non-functional services The following qualities should be exhibit in the leader who is leading up in the front of the team.

According to Kotterman (2006), leader is one of the significant elements to make organisations successful especially in difficult times. Leaders are those who engage with employees and keep them motivated as well as inspire them to follow the defined path by senior management. In fact, leader is a part of senior management who act as a role model for employees. According to leaders act as a bridge between employees and employer by bringing employees on one platform and pursue them to work for a common goal instead do of different personal goals. Leadership is not a single word, but it is divided into several types and each type has its own benefits and impacts on organisations.

According to Rogers (2012), leaders are born with specific traits which make them a particular type of leader. Opposed born leader concept by referring trait leadership theory which says that indeed, leaders are born with specific traits, but some traits can be polished or improved by the passage of time which impact on overall leadership style of an individual.

It is fact that 3500 definitions have been introduced up till now, but few styles have been recognized as common types of leadership and each style is a detailed subject in itself.

According to Kotterman (2006), it is not necessary that the success of organisations depends on specific type of leadership as every type has its own impact and circumstances of

organisations play vital role in deciding the required type of leadership. He also said that in leadership development, leaders must know all the types of leadership style and the techniques which are used to engender required traits in employees. Indeed, every employee could not be a transformational leader. There are some set of traits in each type of leadership style which are essential to be held by an individual.

Boseman (2008) criticized that attributes are essential but they are useless until they are used in appropriate manner. He said that having attribute doesn't give guarantee effective leadership but using such attributes by a leader play significant role. According to Rogers (2012), leadership is comprised of three core areas that are WHO LEADERS ARE (characteristics, traits, motives), WHAT LEADERS KNOW (Skills and capabilities) and WHAT LEADERS DO (behaviours). Characteristics can be identified through psychometric test and other techniques at the time of hiring by HR department and this is the first step on which the future of organisation and future leadership development is based. Effective leaders ensure future leadership development in organisations and groom managerial staff to act in the absence of a leader. This phase is repetitive and could be practiced by line managers to identifying the traits of managerial staff for future leadership development. Line managers must be equipped with required skills to use relevant models of trait theory to identify the traits in employees. Skills and capabilities are the second most important area in leadership which is related to professional development of line managers. It is not necessary that if a line manager acquires good leadership traits then he or she must have a skill to act as a leader. Hence, identifying the traits is the most important to identify the required skills as skills depend on the traits of an individual. In reality, sometimes an individual is introvert then provision of training to equip that individual by presentation skills would result in wastage of time and money. Behavioural area of leadership is related to practical approach of leaders. Behavioural area is related part of performance evaluation which is the core area of HR department.

Leadership development is extremely crucial for long term sustenance as retention of employees may result in loss of skilled labour which must be replaced by another employee as hiring leaders is not a piece of cake. Organisations give high priority future development to deal with retention issues in competitive market. Leadership development is core area of transformational leadership style which is one of the advanced approaches of leadership styles. Furthermore, change management has become vital for survival for companies in which bring changes in leadership styles is essential for successful change management. Senior management must know all the leadership styles so they can switch upon demand or at least hire appropriate leader to meet the current demands (Solaja, 2016).

Moreover, trait theory is the first theory, developed to answer the questions related to leadership. This theory covers broad aspects of leadership whereas other leadership styles like transformational, participative, autocratic and transactional leadership style. Trait theory does not only support other leadership styles but also provide useful models to assess the characteristic and skills areas of leadership (as discussed above) (Rogers, 2012).

Trait theory was first developed to support the belief that leader is born with special traits but later this theory assists both concepts that are leaders are born, and they are also made depend so their traits. According to Grant (2011), we cannot ignore some of the traits at the time of hiring regardless of leadership styles as such traits are crucial for any leader and they must be present in leaders that are motivation, social intelligence, emotional intelligence, emotional stability, and cognitive abilities. According to Khan (2013), when management don't know the use of trait models and techniques then it may result in hiring inappropriate leaders and fails in future leadership development. In fact, usage of trait models as well as techniques must be a part of training and development programs of companies.

1. Gordon Allport's 's 4000 traits theory (1897–1967):

Gordon introduced a dictionary which is comprised of 4000 traits in 193. Such traits are divided into cardinal traits, central traits and secondary traits. In cardinal traits, leaders possess such traits which become trademark of leaders and they are recognized in public by such traits. Cardinal traits distinguish leaders among several and put everlasting impression on people even such traits could become developed or improved but first impression become last impression of leaders on public.

Central traits cannot be exposed or revealed instantly by leaders and they are the complex ones in future development of leaders. Central traits could be identified at the time of hiring through assessment techniques including trait theory techniques but needs time during the leadership development process in organisations. In fact, senior management needs to use trait theory models and techniques to reveal central traits in employees during leadership development process. Secondary traits solely depend on cardinal and central traits. Such traits could be developed by the passage of time but revealing of cardinal and central traits by using trait theory methods is necessary (Derue et al., 2011).

2. Raymond Cattell 's Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (1905–1998)

Raymond contributed to trait theory by developing a questionnaire which is based on 171 personality traits. Such traits cover the traits of all leadership styles which assist in assessing the hidden traits of employees. This questionnaire is a useful tool in leadership development which assists in analysing the traits of employees and identifying the reasons behind the poor

performances of employees. This questionnaire suggests that which type of assistance or skills are required to transform an individual. Such traits are central and secondary which can be developed over a period whereas cardinal could not be changed instantly.

3. Hans Eysenck 's Three Dimensions of Personality (1916–1997)

This is supplementary tool which doesn't give complete list of traits. This tool was developed by Hans with the aim to facilitate other traits methods. Han's model is comprised of three rubrics named as introversion/extraversion, neuroticism/emotional stability and psychoticism.

4. The Five-Factor Theory of Personality (The Big Five / OCEAN)

This theory is useful when it is practised with other trait theories otherwise it may give false result or insufficient information. This theory is well explained in the table which is comprised of 5 big traits with explanations at two ends. In future leadership development, this theory has significant role in assessing the leadership qualities in employees which support the decision regarding training and development of employees as a future leader (Five Traits, 2018).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a diagram of the 'Big 5 Personality Traits' and is available from Google. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 7: Big 5 Personality Trait; Source: Google

Robustness of trait theories must be known by senior managers to assess the qualities of employees properly. The table doesn't reveal hidden information as it only gives direction to assess the qualities whereas analysis requires in-depth knowledge regarding usage of trait theories and methods. In practical, there are limitations, or we can say criticism on trait theories which must be known by senior managers. Designing the questionnaire according to five factor theory is also comes in the set of skills, necessary for senior management to assess the

employees during future leadership development program (Lakshmi 2008). Another important tool named as LTQ must be known to assess the qualities in employees in terms of leadership qualities. This tool is kind of quiz, different from interviews in which every employee has to attempt the quiz independently (Stephens et al., 2015).

Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI-2):

Behavioural aspects are extremely significant in assessing the traits of employees. Senior management must be skilled enough to identify the traits by analysing the behaviour of employees individually. MMPI 2 tool was designed by Starke Hathaway and McKinley at University of Minnesota in 1943. The tool is comprised of 557 questions which assist in revealing the true personality of employees. This tool is complex amongst other tools which require training, or we can say practise to get the most out of it otherwise this tool may lead to.

Figure 8: Sample questions of MMPI2; Source: Google

The tool is divided into clinical scale which is actual test and validity scale area which helps to analyse the validity of the responses of recipients. It is quite common that sometimes recipients over reporting, gives false information or tick randomly. The clinical scale is divided into several categories and each category consists of several questions. This tool cannot be used by unskilled and untrained individual. Interpretation of the result is a complex process in which secondary factors, or we can say traits becomes highlighted after completing the test. Indeed, primary traits are impacted by secondary traits like confident individual may be affected by depression factor which could be managed but it may affect other traits until it is resolved.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a diagram of the Original Test Sample and is available from Google. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Figure 9: Original test sample; Source: Google

Myers-briggs Type Indicator

This instrument was developed by Isabel Briggs Myer, mother of Katherine Briggs. Isabel developed this instrument to support other trait methods in assessing the hidden qualities in employees. In this tool, total 93 questions are given which could be attempted online at any time by anyone. The questions are comprised of 4 major categories that are extrovert, introvert, sensing and intuition. Employees answer the questions in accordance with their experiences, feelings and knowledge which help senior management to reveal the true personality traits in accordance with Myer's tool (Myers, 2018).

Figure 10: Myers2; Source: Myers, 2018

Figure 11: Selective boxes; Source: Myer's 2018

2.13.7 Training course on ERP

In today's technology era, usage of advanced software in businesses in every sector has become crucial for survival in competition. Business software makes business processes easy especially by giving cutting edge over rivals in the shape of utilization of business intelligence which is

key to success in every sector. According to Philips (2014) Information technology plays pivotal role in bringing ease in doing businesses in many ways. Radical changes in market have changed the demand and need in management as well as technological tools for companies.

The history of ERP goes back to the previous 100 years. In 1913, an engineer developed a model called EOQ which is used more than 70 years. Now talk about the modern eras.

What Is ERP? ERP stands for the Enterprise Resource Planning. Enterprise Resource Planning is a type of software which is used in an organisation, bank and in other business fields to manage daily business activities such as accounting, project management, risk management and chain supply operations. A complete Enterprise Resource Planning package is including enterprise resource management, software that help plans, budget, predict and report on an organisational result. Enterprise Resource Planning basically a bridge between two business organisations which enables flow of data between them. So, they can communicate and fulfil their business requirements, functional requirements and non – functional requirements through Enterprise Resource Planning. Today ERP system is used to handle different type of business, their requirements. It is handling the business of all the types. For these businesses, ERP is necessary as the electricity for an industry.

The **Fundamental of** Enterprise Resource Planning is a single defined, data structure. Typically has a common database. This helps to tell us the information that we are gathering now days are normalized now. simply we can say that Enterprise Resource Planning is now a vehicle to integrate people, process and technology across modern enterprise.

For example, a company wants to make an airplane. Now the Enterprise Resource Planning will help them to know their pre-requirements, and requirements for every single process. Enterprise Resource Planning. ERP will help them to purchase the goods and also ensure the pay process regarding to the purchase by using clean and data connected to enterprise workflow and data process. The key principle for the ERP is the collection of the central data for the wide distribution. Instead of collecting data from all the databases, ERP bring chaos close to the user that can create, store and derived data from different processes through a common database. The real benefit is that everyone in the organisation is satisfied because of the accuracy of the data. Data integrity is always assured through the ERP.

We cannot ignore the impact of the ERP in the modern era as industry of all the sizes depends upon it. An ERP data and all the processes are corralled into ERP system, business can align

separate department for the improvement of the business flow. ERP is specific for all kind of the business let's talk about some of its main benefits.

- It generates every kind of the report, that's why it is the so important in improvement of the business insight through the real time protection
- It lowers the operation costs through streamline business processes and the best practice.
- It enhanced collaboration from user sharing data from user sharing data in contracts.
- Improve efficiency through the common user experience across many business functions and well defines business process
- Consistent infrastructure from the back office to the front office
- Higher user adaptation rate from the common user experience and design
- It reduces the risk and improve data integrity
- It lowers the management and the business cost through uniform and integrated system

According to Watson (2012), nowadays, companies need to give highly importance to these requirements as negligence may result in serious consequences for companies including failure of business. In addition, innovation has become crucial in relation with products, applications, technology and other business-related resources. These innovations need information in advance to predict the future consumer's demand. According to Kumar and Siddika (2013) and Lopez (2014), companies need information to make effective decision whether they are related to operational level or strategic level. The spreading of this information at all levels within organisation is necessary to get desired outcomes. Without knowledge sharing, no company can be successful. This knowledge sharing through technology refers to explicit knowledge. This knowledge management depends on information management and timely processing unintelligible data into understandable format so everyone within organisations can utilize this available data efficiently.

Moreover, information technology is extremely important role in gather, analyse and share this data within organisation. Utilization of business intelligence is extremely important for employees to gain the priceless benefits in terms of actionable knowledge which assist in any sort of decision making in organisations (Alton 2017).

Companies use software in each department, but integrated approach comes in advanced approach which reefs to ERP which stands for enterprise resources planning. ERP is a term which refers to the integration of all departments in a company. ERP coin the word of utilization of business intelligence which includes all business information including all

departments like personal administration, organisational management, strategic human resource management, marketing, sales, distribution, and manufacturing. In short, ERP related software provide central point where all information is stored which can be used by authorized employees only even when companies have large physical network.

According to Chau (2012) the competitiveness of organisations rely in many aspects in which advancement of technology is extremely important as nowadays strategic decision makers heavily rely on information technology to formulate and implement strategies including improvements in financial performance of organisations and other organisational management decisions. The information technology covered limited area i.e. gather and processing into understandable data but now it has become vast subject in itself as it has moved up to business intelligence which is refined and distilled integrated aspect in organisations. In fact, business intelligence is advanced level of information technology.

According to Watson (2012), information technology refers to all type internal and external information which is crucial to make effective organisational decisions. As seen in the figure 4, there are various sources of information, depends on the need and nature of businesses. According to Pots (1998) BI is superior level of knowledge which means actionable information about customers, market, products, technology, required material, competition and changing market needs.

Knowledge management and sharing is important no doubt, but they can give valuable information which acts as primary source of doing business in harsh competition whereas BI means the right analysis and interpretation of high quality of information for the usage by every employee easily specially by top management in decision making process.

BI seems new discipline for many organisations as information system discipline has been used for many years in limited context. In addition, use of BI doesn't give benefit all the time as it also results in losses of money if they are not used efficiently. Organisations need BI in order to be competitive instead of relying old traditional concepts of information technology. Knowledge management has two faces i.e. tacit knowledge which is related to human and explicit knowledge which is related to organisation. Explicit knowledge of organisation is related to information technology aspect. Organisations need to transform this explicit knowledge into BI to get actionable information which is crucial for survival in competitive market.

Figure 12: Role of information technology in information system

Source: Formulated by the Author

The BI itself doesn't guarantee improvement in performances as there are many other aspects that make BI fails in organisations. There is need to aware employees regarding those challenges and factors that make BI fails. The three stages of BI will help me to analyse BI in depth and it will help to analyse benefits of BI in organisation in relation with these 3 stages as at every stage BI benefits and usage are different. This data includes ETL (extract-transformation-Load), MIS, EIS, DSS, Data query, OLAP for converting integrating specific data, scorecard, dashboards, and search engines like Google, OLTP, data mining, web mining, No SQL and interactive visual tools (Wixom, 2011).

Informational Technology encompasses several areas which are significant for survival for companies and each area requires expertise like networking, software running, hardware management and cleaning of the data to get the required information (Chen, 2012). Explicit

knowledge is vested in the data storage system of companies which is attached to the business software like ERP. Tacit knowledge is an area related to knowledge management approach and cannot be archived easily. Data storage and utilization of the data must be known by non-technical staff in companies to exploit the business intelligence while making strategic decisions whereas other IT areas are the responsibility of technical staff.

Technology like ERP, SAP and CRM helps to gather data which is turned by means of different technology tools to transfer and convert into information. This information needs refinements which makes the information into knowledge. Knowledge has no worth until it is used efficiently. The usage of this knowledge efficiently refers to business intelligence. As we can see in the figure 12, data cleaning is a primary step in gaining business intelligence which is normally done by technical staff that restrict the potential of gathered information. Non-technical staff must be well trained to extract valuable information from the gathered data as per need then refine to achieve valuable knowledge. Indeed, non-technical staff has to rely on their own research rather than on technical staff which has limited view over different business areas like financial, marketing, material and HR.

2.13.8 Integrity and Anticorruption

Corruption is a common issue of every company and there are strict policies against corruption especially in giant companies. In order to keep the corruption, ration minimal, audit is one of the primary responsibilities of giant companies' especially public limited. Every department is responsible for specific duties and operations which create opportunities for negative employees to do corruption when senior employees are also involved in theft. Indeed, subordinates are not allowed to interfere in the decision of senior employees. Business ethics is one of the primary areas of business in which every employee must perform ethically according to the international standards. Companies with strong ethical guideline are less vulnerable to corruption than with no guideline but it does not guarantee that ethical guideline keeps the employees on straight path (OECD, 2015).

The Bangladeshi Anti-Corruption Commission is useful for establishing the entity that can charge the corruption laws through investigation. It has issued with arresting the warrant. It has lodged the cases against corrupt individuals, which include public officials as a whole. There are some active practices during the mandate of the caretaker government in Bangladesh that

can help the business and banking industries in filling with the cases against the number of top political leaders. It provides a number of cases that are significantly dropping the elections of the alliance government. The BBs are using integrity practices in the banking industry by establishing the BEC for directing the oversight of the presidential and parliamentary elections. It helps in appointing the non-party caretaker for the government that was credited for the delivery of the national and international commended elections in Bangladesh. It helps in preparing the digital voters in the credibility of the new leadership and appointing under the federal government in remaining the open question for transparent international Bangladesh. It helps in providing the media outlets for obtaining the license of secondary considerations. The business industries can use it for introducing the restrictive with electronic and on-line media policy. (Kabir et al., 2020)

Good governance can be considered as one of the focal areas of the partnership with Bangladesh. It is beneficial for highlighting the needs for reforms in the judiciary and the police. It is helpful for the banking and business industries in establishing the governance institutions, like the forming of an office of the Ombudsman and a service centre for the Human Rights Commission. It is beneficial for providing better service delivery for getting stronger local governance and better equipment for the oversight bodies. It is beneficial for the media industry as well as private TV, radio, and online services within Bangladesh. The media is seen as rapid growth within the country that provides a number of coverages with free and vibrant political pressures. It seems beneficial for international donors to recognize the importance of good governance in order to get success of the Millennium Development Goals and poverty alleviation programs in the entire business industry of Bangladesh. The banking industry also seems in getting significant improvement in Bangladesh with an increase in a number of social sectors like gender discrimination in education or reduction of childhood mortality rates. The anti-corruption department plans for providing benefits to the donors in suspending the assistance and corruption within the ground (Islam et al., 2017).

Internal audit is being conducted by companies to keep strict control over corruption level and integration is practised to increase the span of control of internal auditors. Financial audit is a primary responsibility of companies but there are several types of audit which must be practised to lower down the level of corruption or eradicate the chances of corporate. Corruption doesn't impact on finance of companies as there are several types of corruption which slow down the operations of companies and also affect performances of companies. In reality, non-financial

corruption results in heavy pay off as compared to financial corruption which can be traced out in financial audits. Companies rely on their code of conducts and expect from employee to follow but in actual, enforcement is significant to make them practised. Enforcement is only possible when investigators in companies are neutral like external finance auditors. It is necessary for companies to keep their employee up to date regarding anti-corruption act to avoid any penalties by external auditors in case of non-practise of new rules and acts (KPMG, 2011).

The importance of integrity and anti-corruption in Bangladesh is seen with overcoming several gaps and weaknesses in the institutional framework of Bangladesh. The standard and essential difference in Bangladesh's integrity system is considered as the absence of an Ombudsman. It is seen that the Bangladeshi Constitution provides a provision that can encourage the development of an Office of the Ombudsman after the failure of implementation of the successive governments.

Additionally, the political considerations are used for providing the systematic influence of the anti-corruption agendas within the country. The existing legislation of Bangladesh and the familiar entities are used for offering harass political opponents and providing the recent developments that risk paralyzing with the anti-corruption system. It gives importance in establishing the budget transparencies with the government in providing the public information, which is better for financial and budgeting activities. It is essential for both banking and business industries in managing and maintaining their financing all year long. It can be compared with the poor neighbourhood with the International Budget Partnership and Bangladesh's budget transparencies that have improved the business industry in 2008.

In corporate world, innovative instruments are being used to control over corporate corruption which are crucial for transparency and accountability as theoretical understanding is not enough to control corruption at workplaces. Innovative instruments are common tools of compliance department which play neutral role in companies. In practise, compliance department exist in some companies only who give high priority to integrity and anticorruption. It is mandatory for compliance department to act independently under the direct supervision of the owner or board of directors as they are the primary stakeholders who give high priority to anti-corruption (KPMG, 2011).

Business process engineering is one of the core areas of compliance which act as an engine or source of operational activities. In every department, a specific duty like HR duty is to hire is based on a specific process to conduct proper hiring. Corruption in business processes

jeopardise the whole performances of companies including all departments. Employees do corruption in processes due to several reasons like incapability to perform well or lack of core knowledge regarding their duties, to facilitates someone and due to lack of interest and time-consuming duties. Business process engineering is not a strategic option or approach but a detailed strategic topic to control corruption. Business process engineering is a fundamental duty of compliance department and no international standard of business law emphasis on is conduction of business process engineering but its healthy practise to control over business process corruption which doesn't only result in financial loss but also affect the performances (OECD, 2015).

Due to retention of employees, newly hired employees must be evaluated in terms of business process engineering by time to time by companies through compliance department to keep internal check on them. Internal check helps in minimizing the chances of corruption. Business process engineering is also used to redesign and manage existing strategies and operations to bring efficiency in operations. There are several tools and techniques which can be used during BPE to facilitate the process and get the desired outcome. Such tools include use of KPIs key performance indicators and benchmarking with rivals and code of conduct and general operational procedures. It is not necessary that amendments in processes must be done in accordance with some written code of conducts and manuals in companies as BPE is ongoing process and completely depends on the sole discretion of decision makers to bring change in exiting process to ensure efficiency and effectiveness (OECD, 2015).

In order to prevent theft or control corruption level in business processes, compliance staff needs to evaluate the knowledge and practices of employees and compare with the pre-set procedures by companies to identify the corruption if any. Nowadays in every organisation whether it is bank or private FMCG firm, technology has become vital for survival and for smooth business. In every department, there is a use of technology like attendance machine in administration department to monitor the attendance level which is then pass on to HR department for payroll function (OECD, 2015).

Corruption in IT may result in serious financial loss as well as disturb the performance of every department even when corruption is occurred in one department. In fact, IT corruption deteriorates the whole business process. IT audit comes in non-financial audit which not only bring efficiency in smooth operations but also safeguard companies against theft, cyber-crime and internal corruption. IT plays key role in financial institutions to safeguard the important data of clients and any weakness in IT system may result in heavy loss like theft credit card information and unauthorized access of intruders to critical matters. IT audit is essential to

ensure that the infrastructure of IT in companies is protecting the assets and critical perspectives like critical information in effective manner. Normally, compliance functions can be performed responsible senior employees of a particular department and companies may also use teamwork by putting senior employee from each department in a team to conduct BPE.

2.13.9 Research methodology

It is a systematic, and we also say that it is the theoretical analysis too applied to the any field of study and anywhere you want to apply it. Its body is the theoretical analysis which includes body and the methods related to the field of knowledge and the study. We think that methodology is the set of the things that provide us the solution of research purpose but in fact it is not. Methodology actually provides us the set of methods, but not solution, which is applicable to the specific problems, to a specific case. Now comes on the Research, it was better to understood first what the Methodology was, now comes to another point that is research, the concept of the question came into being for the purpose to provide information for those whose are going to come in this filed. For example, nowadays we can find symptoms of cancer on internet this is all due to the research (Creswell et al., 2003).

For research purpose, men use his tool of experience. Man can make the experience in any field through research. Research gives a man experience and the knowledge. Let me tell you a logical thing is experience helps us in making hypothesis which is mainly based upon the common-sense knowledge. That's why wise people said, "don't make any judgment on the spot or on any point". Hence result hypothesis come into being or its formulation can be done by using Experience and Authority (Creswell et al., 2003).

Let's come on the definition of the Research Methodology Definition we can say that it is the systematic technique mostly used in the Research, the means of this in simple words it is a guide to research and how it is conducted. It simplifies, describe and justifies methods. Provide us the knowledge about the tool which we are using. It guided us to develop a critical and scientific attitude. The most important factor and benefit of it is that it's provide us knowledge and the, give us ability to learn and give us sense to think critically (Gilbert et al., 2008).

The word researcher methodology encompasses several perspectives, used to find the solution for a problem and assist researchers in getting desired result. Research methodology must be known by every individual, but it is more important for such employees who are responsible to navigate businesses in hard times. Research methodology teaches to conduct the research in a right manner so the result could be reliable as well as valid. Research methodology tells the procedure to conduct the research in a systematic manner which saves time as well as cost. In

research methodology, critical evaluation is a core skill to conduct detail meaningful analysis to get the solution.

Researchers need to select appropriate research methods and philosophy to keep the research on the right path. Research methodology is a skill which comes through practise instead of theoretical knowledge in corporate sector. In easy words, using the right methodology in accordance with the identified problems or purpose of the research is important in corporate sector. Designing the questionnaire is also the primary skill to conduct meaningful research in which designing appropriate as well as effective questions to get a useful data as the analysis section is solely depends on the chosen questions to conduct primary research (Gilbert et al., 2008).

Research methodology must be taught with case study approach to give practical touch to the learners. Case study approach is usually used in business schools to give practical understanding regarding tools, theories and techniques which are essential in corporate world. Case studies are based on real issues of the corporate world which needs to be solved by employees as benchmarking approach. Benchmarking is used to compare the issues and strategies of rivals in particular conditions and such particular conditions are discussed in detail in case studies which give insight into the issues of a company on which the case study was written (Hoque et al., 2017).

Case study approach equips researchers to formulate practically possible and useful solutions as per the real problems. In research methodology, the selection of appropriate research methods, strategies and philosophies don't give desired outcome until the researcher use sophisticated analytical tools along with research methodology. Research proposal is a first step towards research in which research methodology is used whereas analytical part is advanced level in order to get the solution of the identified issues. In research proposal, researchers identify the issues and define the path to reach the conclusion whereas in analytical part, different evaluation tools hep researchers to get the secondary data.

Primary data is obtained through questionnaire, but secondary data can only be obtained through secondary sources, using different analytical tools to get the relevant as well as useful data. Analytical tools are not strategic by nature but provide guidance through which data has to be collected to get the useful findings which assist researchers to get the desired outcome of the research. In companies, employees must know the relevant analytical tools to assess the situation of a company. It is also necessary to use the right analytical tool as per need which refers to contextual intelligence. In research methodology, literature review section is solely

based on secondary data but when researches are based on case studies, analytical tools are essential to get the relevant data (Creswell et al., 2003).

2.13.10 FDI and portfolio investment in Bangladesh (Critically Analysed)

FDI refers to foreign direct investment which takes place by multinational companies and individuals to gain benefits in new place in terms of profitability and utilization of other resources. There are several theories related to FDI which defines the purpose of investments, but entrepreneurship is significant to make investment valuable otherwise investment may result in failures.

Bangladesh is getting skyrocketing investments from foreign places these days. Foreign investors of different regions are coming forward to invest in the place. As compare to 2017 there is a 67 percent increase in the FDI. This is done not only to protect the domestic business, but it is also done to improve the skills of nature people. FDI also generate employment. The purpose of making such policies that attract FDI is not only to benefit the local business but to generate employment and skills of people. FDI creates an environment of learning. there are various steps that the government has taken to let the FDI coming in. the flows of FDI has significantly increased leading to the better infrastructure of the country is specifically few sectors including textile. It is a record of FDI that the government has set in recent years. The US government has made plenty of investment in Bangladesh. The political stability is also behind the FDI (Abdin, 2015).

There are a lot of benefits that Bangladesh is enjoying from FDI. Increased FDI is a source of development. An industry where FDI comes previously flourishing and their contribution to GDP also improves. The local producers also improve their quality of working to meet the foreign industries in the industry. Thus, local producers also become alert, and the quality of producers is increased than ever before. Easy international trade also takes place. There are few privileges which are present to bilateral nations, they can enjoy good foreign relations and they can have better access to resources, Bangladesh can also make good relations with plenty of countries by attention them for FDI. The international firms may come to explore the reserves, and this will benefit both the firm and the host country. The disparity between revenues and costs will be decreased. Tax incentives are also there. Bangladesh may give tax evasions to local producers as well as the result of international producers. Thus, there are a lot of opportunities that FDI is creating in Bangladesh right now. One-fourth of the global FDI of

the US is coming directly to Bangladesh (Abdin, 2015). It was almost impossible to meet the socio-economic objectives of the country before; however, the country is quite close to meet those objectives thus benefits and uses of FDI cannot be ignored in this very region. the trends of FDI are certainly towards small enterprises (Ullah and Yasmeen, 2014).

there are different advances that the legislature has taken to give the FDI a chance to come in. the progressions of FDI have fundamentally expanded prompting better foundation of the nation in explicitly couple of segments including material. It is a record of FDI that the legislature has set in the ongoing year. The US government has made a lot of interest in Bangladesh. The political soundness is likewise behind the FDI.

There are a ton of advantages that Bangladesh is getting a charge out of from FDI. Expanded FDI is a wellspring of advancement. A venture where FDI comes already prospering and their commitment to GDP additionally improves. The nearby makers additionally improve their nature of attempting to meet the remote enterprises in the business. In this manner, neighbourhood makers additionally become caution and the nature of makers is expanded than at any time in recent memory. A simple global exchange likewise happens. There are not many benefits which are available to reciprocal countries, they can appreciate great remote relations and they can have better access to assets, Bangladesh can likewise make great relations with a lot of nations by consideration them for FDI.

Entrepreneurship refers to the business idea based on incremental changes or innovation to fulfil the weaknesses and gaps in the market. Innovation is not an idea or one step process to implement. Innovation is basically a set of skills which are essential to get the position in the market when there is a pool of rivals. In the area of innovation, MVIS was introduced to assist entrepreneurs which is detailed process based on several steps. MVIS is advanced approach and entrepreneurs must be skilled din using MVIS to make a strong portfolio investment (Hasan, 2013).

The first step presented for MVIS is one of the most remarkable steps. Going wrong on the very first step has led many companies and organisations into bankruptcy since this is where the innovations pick up directions. The organisations starting or say, preparing to bring innovations in their companies must be aware of two things. That is, it must have a structure and it must have a direction. How companies should begin is by realizing that innovations are needed for longer term but also for the shorter term. This companies do this, by mapping out where the need to be in future and what is the current position. The gap between the two positions is clear to show companies how much of innovation is needed in the short term and how much for the longer term. In other words, as described in this model, innovations can be

divided into two branches; either as core innovations and new growth or as those that are simply innovations in existing products, service or business line and those that come about through entering new markets and new products (Cooper and Edgett, 2010).

Companies better understand that companies should be innovating along both the lines. There should be core innovations as well as new growth. Core innovations are those that reap quicker returns while new growth innovations take typically five years to reap returns and determine their success and scalability. The size of the gap between current and future goals makes it easy to realize what balance companies should have for both the types of innovations to reach their future objectives (Vacek et al., 2010). The Minimum Viable Innovation System outlines clearly how companies should begin to innovate. At least some of them might feel too over pressured and confused as to where to begin and how to sort out innovations. The step one essentially explains the term innovation itself and broadly categorizing innovations into the two categories which clearly explains what type of innovations organisations should pursue and how.

However, the process as explained step by step has one shortfall. There is no guideline to identify between core innovations and new growth innovations. Among the many ideas, the executives might come across, there is a chance that they end up confused in separating between core innovations and new growth. For example, a change in product might be suggested as core innovation but the product modification might be altogether to serve a new customer group. Some ideas have a very minor division between the two categories and so it may get difficult

However, easy the process might seem, another difficulty that executives face is when determining the gap between the present and future goals. The future plans are outlined for the overall organisation by the top leadership and correspond to the vision and mission of the organisation. The present position has to be mapped out and there are several easy models and analysis tools that help executives do that, but difficulty is to accurately map out the distance between the two positions for the organisation. As easy as it may seem, such gaps cannot and do not identify in numbers rather have to be mapped out in terms of short-term goals, objectives and milestones to achieve step by step. Also, accuracy is the topmost concern since, in between the organisation has to plan for core innovations while working on new growth. This gap will determine how many of such innovation strategies or plans can the organisation work on, hence, accurately figuring out the gap becomes most important while there are no guidelines mentioned for it.

Step 2: Similar to any strategic decision, the organisations have to consider the organisations competencies and weaknesses along with the opportunities and failures that the market is

offering. Then there is industry, competitor, and supplier analysis; all this to get a complete picture. According to Scott, Duncan, and Siren, instead of engaging the whole organisation and elongating the process, it is better to choose a dozen executives which are capable enough to conduct market survey which again can be done by having discussion with employees and exploring options and chances.

After a deep analysis with the customers, these people are then required to decide and choose a selected number of strategic innovation choices which shall further be considered. The difficult part is how to decide between different strategic choices. For this, it is important for those executives to be always think in terms of bringing a revolutionary breakthrough innovation and begin by setting the future goals and then work all the way backwards. There should be constant effort to come up with new growth innovation while working on core innovations

This team must have creative inspiration involved in process and always attempt to drive innovation from alternative and unusual sources. And most importantly, at the core of everything, there must lay the objective to serve customer needs.

Besides, underlying rules for innovation must always be kept in mind, that the opportunities must have strategic alignment with company's overall mission and objectives. The resources are limited and so options to explore are such that can maximize the return on them. The options should also be varied enough for the company to be exploring a range of opportunities but linked to the core business (Vacek et al., 2010).

According to the model, the chosen executives are involved in the strategic decision making and have the task of coming up with innovation alternatives by studying market and the customers. While the positive aspect of the entire process is that it has reduced redundancy and following the steps assures innovation for organisation with least resources and time and within all that is available.

However, practically things may not look so simple especially when market survey is done. Whenever the strategy is being developed, it is usual for the companies to conduct market and stakeholder analysis. The company performs its own internal analysis along with analysis of its existing businesses. For huge organisations, these processes take more time, resources and efforts than usual since neither their own existence is limited nor is the market and customer segment. The process then suggests having a few executives conduct meetings with key consumer or consumer groups to generate innovation ideas with them by discussing needs and unmet demands.

But, for a company that's large enough to have more than a couple of SBUs and each having a different consumer segment, the process will normally take longer than usual. The executives brainstorm the ideas; develop a framework for these ideas to be later presented to the top management for further decision making and development. For all this to be done, most organisations will end up consuming more time than needed. Those conducting innovation activities for the first time will obviously slack because of inexperience.

Also, this step lacks details or proposals as to how executives should conduct meetings with the key consumer groups so as to make sure that the discussion is focused on innovations and ideas that are developed relate to both core as well as new growth innovations. Such meetings and discussions usually require a moderator to reap results and are not conducted with the ease by organisations executives with which they are mentioned in MVIS (Palmer and Kaplan, n.d.).

Step3: As much as it is important to apply the right methods and choose the right type of strategies and innovation fit between present and future goals, it is equally important to have the right kind of team to work on the innovation developments. Sometimes, companies feel that their employees are not innovative enough and so go through the hassle of hiring specialist. Instead, to bring innovation in a very short time and at a fast pace, there should be rules and practices inducted in organisations to bring the best of innovation from amongst the existing employees especially the team appointed for viewing strategic options and conducting all market preliminaries for the process.

It is important the team should be selected carefully; those involved should be key executives and have the right kind of information. Spirit of innovation is much needed in every member of the team, be it only a two-person team. Then there are characteristics of an effective team that should be there such as having effective communication, clarity of goals, mindset to innovate and the ability to realize failures and move on looking for new options.

The team should be proactive when looking for gaps in markets and pick up the opportunities that have remained untapped. The commitment and willingness should be high in the team members with the ability to explore every possibility and take each one of them as a possible start up. The team members should be freed of their other work in organisation, so they have complete concentration.

This step focuses on team building and effective innovation building strategies. Now there can be two types of innovation practices that can be inducted in organisations. This is done by having such organisational cultures and creative processes that allows employees to think out

of bounds and have workshops and trainings, having employees participate in decision making or at the least have free access and communication between different levels of management. Another type of innovation practice is those that are put into place according to the need of the organisation such as gathering a bunch of executives and focusing their minds on the need to innovate or choosing only those that are innovative. This is a bit of a passive approach and so the preference of organisations should be on to build innovative capacity in their employees rather than to select those who have it already or might have them through some short hand rules.

While executives develop innovative ideas with consumer groups and have more than a few alternatives, it is important that through careful evaluation a few are handpicked and should have all the focus. The executives might make the mistake of picking more than a few projects to work on or have their focus on all of them. This can be the biggest blunder.

For this process to work, only a few worthy ideas have to be selected and further developed. There should be either process or some kind of analysis to determine the right kind of ideas. Not all alternatives can be developed and grown before they are to be selected, they have to be screened and selected before they are further pursued in the organisation. There should be guidelines for executives to do that correctly because companies experiencing innovations for the first time might fall into this trap.

Step 4: While there should be small team set up to move the innovation process forward, it is also important to have a surveillance team besides the innovation team which is responsible for heading or conducting routine and timely check up on the pre-existing team. Teams often get distracted or tangled especially when it comes to new growth projects. A team of top leaders will help in setting the team on the right track as well as turning the innovation efforts in the right direction (Coenen et al., 2012). The most important task that this surveillance team has is choosing the right direction for future of the organisation. Although it is a traditional method, but any innovation and strategic effort should be structured, and the performance monitoring processes should be applied. There should be goals long and short term and there should be performance measurement which should keep the activities organized. Working haphazardly without any structure and priorities is most likely to fail.

Top leadership is also to make sure that the group selected has consultation and participation from every member and any shortfalls should be immediately altered. It also becomes the duty of the leadership to induce and sustain innovative practices within companies which itself is

enough to drive constant innovation leading to core innovations. It is difficult to move organisations in motivation, towards a single goal in a constantly changing environment and that is exactly the challenge that leadership can combat by having the right culture and values within organisations. Some organisations also tend to go with traditional methods of having trainings and developments and though these are necessary, there should also be underlying practices that drive innovation from within employees (Cooper and Edgett, 2010).

This is important since it explains the need and importance of having guides and mentors in the form of leaders in the organisation and the need is even more so when there is innovation process at work. Everything the leaders do becomes all the more sensitive when it is innovation that the employees are working on since they need more of inspiration, guidance and creativity. It is natural for employees to be led into wrong directions when working on ideas. A simple idea may seem different when developed into a full-grown structural project. Either the employer has been in wrong direction hence changing the idea or might feel confused once it has turned out to be opposite. It is also natural that employees get tangled into these many ideas or when coming up with these ideas during meetings, they may end up in wrong directions about core and new growth innovations. There can be many such cases where the team can go wrong or end up with a dead end. Therefore leaders and mentors are needed. In MVIS, it is proposed that the organisations also have a shepherding team for the bunch of executives working over innovation ideas.

Besides being there for putting the employees in the right direction and being there for monitoring the performance of their innovation teams, the top management should also keep injecting creativity the entire time the employees are working with the consumer groups or at developing an idea. The leaders, however, should be clear on two things. First, there should be group of selected leaders for shepherding and not everyone interrupting the process and secondly, that there can be different methods to build creativity. For innovation building, leaders should opt for more interactive and participative methods rather than traditional passively training methods.

The article very briefly describes an innovation start up process for any organisation that is working towards having an innovation mechanism. The main aim behind having this process is to have innovation introduced in companies that have ever experienced it before in an easy and less daunting manner or guide those that are already attempting innovation but only to be fruitless. The process eliminates all the redundant steps and cut shorts steps that otherwise extend taking up a lot of company resources and time.

Along with the process, the authors have also listed advice to better understand the process. While there are some effective strategies and useful steps in the process, also briefing out how the entire process should begin. The process while being effective and shortage, also has useful detailing which will help small organisations better able to work on it such as the number of days, each process would take, given its effectiveness is maintained.

To sum up the entire process, the advice is important to consider. For those considering this process, as up to authors, it is significant that the entire process is utilized while not leaving out any step. Since it is an innovation driving system designed, the essential part of any system is its structure, and it cannot be expected of any mechanism to work until unless the whole system is implemented. For any kind of change or system redesigning the organisations face and introduce, it is made necessary for them to follow and implement the entire process. However, there can be two sides to consider. Although, organisations can pick up any strategy from the entire process to induct in their innovation processes, but it should be without any expectation to receive the results promised by the MVIS.

For example, some company might find the market and customer survey process as explained in the process and easy and think about implementing it into their organisation. This can be done but not the other way around. Also, although it is structured, no two organisations are same and so it should be made obvious for each organisation to adjust the process into their own functions and organisational structures and there should be space enough for modifying the process without losing the essence. The process along with the advice has its focal point on the employees. The main engine that will drive the process is most obviously the employees/personnel as is the right approach and not just for this innovation process, but employees make up the most essential part of strategy and change driven organisations.

However, discussing personnel should not only focus on the executives or employees working in teams but also on having the right leadership and top management as well as HR personnel working towards getting the right employees for the company as well as developing those employees for the best of organisational need. As much as the innovation must come from within employees and that this process also makes it prerequisite to have employees which are dedicated towards bringing innovation to the company, it is also true that innovation streaks soon run out of employees if not put under the environment. Companies should have their internal culture, leadership and processes that allow employees to be involved in decision making, suggestions, workshops and empowerment sessions. Hence no doubt that personnel of any company would be essential in bringing innovation but all the organisational personnel,

from all levels and departments should be covered under this umbrella and their efforts scrutinized and not just the key executive group.

The last piece of advice is although not part of process implementation, however, implication is immensely important and applies to all strategic decision making that takes place inside organisations. It is usual to expect success but not failures and so in organisations too, successes are celebrated and expected more than the failures are discussed. However, both the approaches are wrong. Failure is always inevitable and more so in the form of obstacles as the process begins. With friction, the executives getting hold of the process, this is bound to happen, which usually demoralizes the employees. Target can never be achieved in the first attempt. This should be clearly communicated with the working groups by the leaders. Employees out of fear or denial do not accept the failure of their decisions or ideas and so keep wasting resources on failing projects. It holds true that zombie or dead projects be left aside and not waste resources on them but only after careful evaluation and discussion with the leaders.

Organisational culture and communication be such that allows employees and leaders to easily interact over failures to come up with solutions. Sometimes, the worthiest projects are put aside simply because employees stuck at any point fear discussing with the leaders and so push the project aside. Also, companies should not only work on their failures but also failures of other companies since they are a source of inspiration, ideas and problem solving. There is no harm in celebrating success, it should be appreciated since it motivates employees, but failures give a new life to ideas.

2.13.11 Prevention of Fraud and Forgery in Banks

Fraud is a key term which is used for any exploitation, theft or using one's assets or personal information to gain personal interest. In banking field, forgery is normally done by intruders who break the system and steal important information like bank card details. Forgery is an advanced level of theft and cannot be done by normal people. Banks develops policies and guidelines to prevent fraud and forgery, but sometimes ineffective guideline could result in forgery and fraud. Fraud is normally used for internal theft, done by employees to use or exploit bank's assets for their personal gains. IT is core area of banking field like e banking, ERP, servers and automated systems like automatic door locks for highly confidential places where unauthorized access is not allowed. IT audit is used to prevent fraud and forgery in companies regardless of sector to assess the level of security and it is crucial for companies to do IT audit similarly like financial audit every year.

IT audit is type of internal audit and could be done either by company's employees or third-party audit companies. IT audit is usually done by compliance department who acts as neutral department and keep an eagle over all departments of organisations. Furthermore, IT audit is a part of compliance but IT officials must be trained enough to prevent forgery in banks and frauds by developing secure IT systems and assess by time to time to identify the weaknesses and the requirements for new inclusions.

There are a lot of ways, uses, and benefits of reducing fraudulent activities in the banking sector. The bank frauds are not only unethical, but these are considered as severe crimes. This is about illegal transactions of money, when people assets are involved, it makes the matter quite sensitive and severe, credit card frauds are also there which is called skimming. Identity theft is also very common fraud which may occur in financial institutions. It is very important to avoid frauds to have credibility and strong investment situations. Investors would not believe in financial institutions leading to low savings and low investments. According to economic rules, the savings lead to investments, once the saving rate decreased in the bank due to fraudulent activities there will be an impact on the economic investment rate of the country. Without investment, there is no scope of infrastructure development. It often happens that bank staff to facilitate customers lead to such checks which are utilized without proper authorization, bank information is also changed, and cheques are made even when the payee knows about insufficient funds in the account. Moreover, false invoices are also a kind of fraud. These frauds have a large margin of errors or ill intentions. Such activities make the financial position of the country and financial institutions weak enough to be trusted. There is an economic impact of forgery such as no foreign investors come to do business as they do not trust financial institutions (Faruk, 2015).

Being a developing country there are no laws related to electronic fraud in Bangladesh yet. If fraud occurs through the internet there is very little chance of finding the culprit. The evolution of the internet has caused challenges for security as well. Customers must be ignored about measures and preventions to save their authorization. Fake websites are also involved in fraudulent activities. There are benefits of retaliating to bank frauds. First of all, there are a lot of chances of attracting more FDI.

Controlling fraud means the waste, abuse, improper payments, and money laundering all things are controlled. There are some issues such as terrorist financing and cybersecurity which are related to the criminal act. If fraud rings are sophisticated increased, then there is no chance of such activities which may lead to other illegal activities. Institutions must prepare their risk profile to avoid financial risks related fraud. The uses of fraud detection technology have

widely increased worldwide. However, Bangladesh is lack behind in this aspect. It is not a technical country and expiring technologies are also not beneficial for its balance of payments leading to severe threats. Vector machines are required to be imported followed by self-organizing maps, logistic regression and many such measures that can measure an instant change in any financial institution and its balance. Artificial intelligence is very much used nowadays, the unknown fraud risks hinder the growth of development. It does not allow countries to enjoy the benefits of financial institutions fully. Faruk, 2015)

It regularly happens that bank's staff to office clients who lead to such checks which are used without appropriate approval, bank data are additionally changed, and checks are made notwithstanding when the payee thinks about deficient assets in the record. Besides, false solicitations are additionally sort of cheats. These fakes have a huge edge of mistakes or sick aims. Such exercises make the budgetary situation of nation and money related organisations frail enough to be trusted. There is a monetary effect of falsification, for example, no outside speculators come to work together as they don't confide in money related foundations.

2.13.12 Corporate Social Responsibility

The importance of CSR of BB in business and banking can be calculated with the institutional steps of the monitoring of the business activities. It helps the banks in providing extra efforts on discharging social responsibilities as well. The business and banking industry can take its advantages of bringing positive changes within the society by delivering extra shots of the government. It seems essential in prioritizing the discharging of the responsibilities within community. The Board of Directors of the Bank can take various steps in fulfilling the CSR resources within the banking industry. It helps in the system of reporting with providing some CSR initiative in modest ways.

It can be helpful in giving the supplements for preparing the annual financial reports. Eventually, it helps in developing the full-blown comprehensive report that is expected and available in the public domains for the perusal of the stakeholders. For BBs, it is essential to adopt the voluntary management of CSR, not the mandatory. It is helpful in monitoring the CSR adoption and performances with financial institutions with providing additional dimensions of the management performances (Masud et.al, 2018).

The CSR is used within the BBs in providing help to both governmental and non-governmental organisations. It helps in addressing the social-justice issues like poverty alleviations and human rights within the country. It seems in the market and the government in providing

necessary facilities to the community services and compelling the NGOs and other organisations in playing a significant role in societal development. It used in contributing to the debate of the poverty in examining the banks and assisting with the financial inclusions as well. It helps in attributing management in motivating the engagement of CSR with external pressure from the stakeholders. It provides the question of sustainability with approving such approach. It is related to examining the CSR issues in focusing the high disclosure levels. It helps in acknowledging the contribution of the banks for CSR and providing intrinsic factors for the main drivers of CSR practices of the banks. It helps in providing alternative perspectives that can explain the social forces behind the CSR activities. It is used by the agents in structuring and other resources. It reveals that the banks in Bangladesh can use social practices while implementing CSR in explaining the deeply rooted with social context and externally driven sources (Masud et.al, 2018).

The CSR is beneficial for the banks of Bangladesh in providing various incentives and administrative building of the development of the countries. It seems helpful for the business and banking industry in promoting the socially responsible behaviour within the business and a good number of financial institutions as well. It helps in providing positive responses towards the society that can help in employee empowerment, social practices, safeguarding the environment etc. Some of the banks in Bangladesh are among the pioneer in the banking industry, which can protect the interest of the stakeholders. It is beneficial for the business industries in developing the roles that can save the environment and playing a vital role in the workplace (Hoque et.al, 2017).

CSR provides some satisfactory results in developing the business industries as well. It helps in overcoming the lack of awareness, weak enforcement of existing laws, and inadequate pressure of the civil society with interest groups. In Bangladesh, most of the banks are using CSR with considering several occasional charity and promotional activities. CSR is beneficial for the business industry in finding the society, nature, and ethics as the central part of the strategy that can improve the competitive position of the organisations. It is beneficial to strengthening competitiveness and losing the risks of the existing market shares in the present market.

Profit companies operate within society to provide amenities, facilities and fulfil the demands of consumers to gain profitability but in return those companies also give back to society in terms of charity works and welfare events. Such events and works are known as corporate social responsibility and green environment is also comes under CSR activities in which companies consider low carbon emission products. Corporate social responsibility is also used

as a strategy to develop brands and there is no restriction on the nature of companies who could use CSR strategies. CSR is considered as moral obligation on companies and no such law bind companies to compulsory use CSR. CSR activities require strategic level of thinking to gain cost efficiency with higher impact. Cost efficiency only comes when decision makers regarding CSR strategies are expert in strategic management perspective (Hoque et.al, 2017).

2.14 Evaluating the Effectiveness of Training

Training and development programme for the employees has become extremely important element of every organisation's human resource management in the recent days. Training and development help the organisations to increase productivity and efficiency of their employees' performance. It is also important for the organisations to measure or evaluate the effectiveness of training and development programme. There is various model of evaluating the effectiveness of employee training and development programme in practice.

2.14.1 Kirkpatrick Model

One of the most used and worldwide recognized models is the four level Kirkpatrick Model. This model evaluates both formal and informal training methods and then measures them against four different levels of standards: reaction, learning, behaviour and results.

Reaction is the first level of standard or criteria of the Kirkpatrick model. This criterion measures the engagement of the employees in the training programme. It also examines if the training programme is constructive or not and whether it is relevant to the job. This criterion mainly used as post training survey by asking the participants to rate the training programme and reveal their experience. (Alvarez et. Al, 2004)

The second level of criteria of this model is **Learning**. This criterion focuses on the learning of every participants and examine whether they are gaining the necessary and relevant knowledge, skills, attitude, commitment, and confidence. Both formal and informal methods

can be used to measure the learning. There are different ways of assessing the and identifying the accuracy of learning such as exams or interviews.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Bates, R. (2004) A critical analysis of evaluation practice: the Kirkpatrick model and the principle of beneficence. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, Volume 4, p. 341 -347.

Figure 13: Kirkpatrick's Model of Evaluation, [Source: Bates, 2004].

Behaviour is the third and the most important level of standard in Kirkpatrick Model. This level evaluates the impact of the training and development programme on the employees and whether the employees are applying the knowledge into their job role. This level is very crucial as examining the behaviour helps to identify if the training programme has been effective and the participants were able to fully understand the learning objectives. Behaviour evaluation also helps to understand if the skills and knowledge taught during the training programme are realistically and logically possible to apply in the actual job role. It often reveals any issues or obstacles that may affect employees' performance at workplace.

Final step of the Kirkpatrick's model is measuring **Results**. This level of criteria measures the learning outcomes versus the organisation's actual business outcomes. Unnotably, Kirkpatrick's model is the most popular and widely used evaluation model. This model has made significant and valuable contributions to training evaluation. This model has helped many organisations to evaluate their training and development program and increase effectiveness. The model has raised awareness of the significant of measuring effectiveness of training and development programme. (Bates, 2004)

2.14 Conceptual Framework

Figure 14: Conceptual Framework

Source: Designed by the Author

Explanation

BB aimed to professionally develop its employees through training programs, based on non-technical and technical perspectives. The main purpose of this thesis is to investigate the effectiveness of training programs of BB by collecting responses via questionnaire and interviews regarding the training programs from those people who are currently working in BB on managerial positions and knowledge workers who possess relevant knowledge regarding the non-technical programs. Non-technical programs were chosen because of relevancy with business administration. It is obvious that only effective programs will pour skills into

employees whereas ineffective could result in wasting of money and time. The designed programs are given in conclusion chapter as guidance for BB to make its ineffective programs effective to achieve the desired outcome.

2.15 Training for Compliance Regulations

Compliance risk has become the most important enduring concern for financial institutions especially for banks. Effective compliance training strategy has become imperious for the banking organisations. A sound and effective training program is banks' first line of defence in order to ensure its compliance program is meeting the regulations and avoids civil liability. Abdullah (2009) mentioned that business regulations normally absorbed to the organisations. Compliance regulations are developed to control the organisations by the laws and guidelines. Boseman (2008) described compliance training as the systematic process of providing training on compliance regulations. Compliance training gives in depth knowledge on laws and regulations as well as company policy and educates the employees to follow the compliance regulations on their everyday job activities. It is crucial for any banks to ensure that they are maintaining an effective and stable compliance function. Compliance training must understand the risk of bank's culture and strengths along with prospective weaknesses. Many banks provide specific courses for compliance regulations training so that the employees can be capable to follow the compliance regulations commendably.

2.16 Significance of Compliance Training for Banks

Ravasi (2006) mentioned that it is very crucial for the banks to practice the compliance regulations efficiently. Any organisation must follow the compliance regulations and therefore it is very important to design an effective training programme in regards with the compliance regulations. Compliance training programme helps the organisation to ensure all its employees are well-trained to understand the principles, expectations and responsibilities to the organisation. Compliance training enables the employees to deal the compliance regulations confidently.

For any financial organisation, especially banks must follow the legal laws and regulations. Failure to be compliant will affect the bank negatively. Compliance training confirms uniformity across the organisation and helps with legal compliance. Andaleeb et al. (2014) stated that there are many risks within the banking sector including information management, money laundering and loan/credit etc. These risks can be reduced through effective compliance

training and ensuring an appropriate compliance practice in the bank. Any little mistake can lead to a breach of the law and banks can be fined; hence it is very crucial for the banks to implement an effective compliance training programme to ensure that their employees are following the regulations.

Andaleeb and Rashid (2006) also said that compliance department or body within organisations regardless of sector as there are rules and regulations whether it is related to IT or administration in every organisation which have to be followed consistently for smooth operations and to ensure safety as well as security at a workplace. It is fact that sometimes companies face failures or losses due to negligence of employees and corruption. Compliance plays vital role in dealing with such negligence and corruption by auditing time to time. Audit is not only related to financial matters but there are several types of non-financial audits like IT audit and business process reengineering audit.

Business process reengineering audit refers to the improvements in business processes for betterment and to ensure efficiency in operational activities. BPR is practiced by line managers in every department in organisations and also specifically done by compliance department if there is any. BPR audit can be done by only those who have necessary knowledge to conduct as it requires specific skills to carryout for effective outcome. In order to conduct effective IT audit and BPR audit, procedure of conducting the audit must be known by a compliance manager. Moreover, sometimes organisations include compliance as a part of training and development to develop necessary skills of internal audit in their employees. Organisations conduct non-financial audits for their own sake whereas financial audit is a legal requirement for giant firms (Athar et al., 2015).

Compliance training helps the organisation to understand and obey the legal obligations which must be followed. Compliance training obliges the persistence of instructing the employees on the compliance laws and regulations that are pertained to their organisations or specific job. It provides the legal framework to the organisations which helps them to enhance the relationship of employees and employers. Compliance training became a top priority to most of the business organisations as it assists them to meet the legal criteria and morals. Importance of compliance training especially in the banking sector has become extremely important in the modern world of business. Compliance training helps the employers to encourage a better workplace culture. Employers can unsure that the employees are well trained to understands the company's expectations, standards and responsibilities towards the customers and organisation.

Employees can be more confident at their work by receiving adequate training from the organisation. They will take the obligations more seriously and understand their roles much effectively. This will result in developing a better workplace culture as a whole.

Today's highly competitive world of business is constantly and rapidly changing. Effective compliance training often helps the organisations to keep pace with rapidly changing business environment. It is very important for the banking institutions to keep up to date with the latest changes in compliance regulations. One of the major significant of compliance training is that it increases the business competence and productivity. Banks must develop an effective framework and create effective training in regards with compliance regulations that can help their employees to act within the instructed framework. Effective compliance training enhances confidence of the employees which helps them to avoid costly errors that could affect the banks significantly by costing hefty penalties and other legal consents. Compliance training also assures the standardisation and uniformity of an organisation. Compliance training helps the organisation to adhere to all the compliance procedures which assists them to ensure greater pellucidity within the organisation. Banking institution constantly handles highly sensitive information including customer's personal data. Various process of banking institutions such as production process, information management, customer relationship and product or service delivery etc. poses high risk to the organisation. Effectively managed and organised compliance training and proper trained employees can help the bank to minimise the risk. Effective compliance training ominously helps the organisation to reduce the risk of compliance regulations (Andaleeb and Rashid, 2006).

2.17 Summary of the Literature Review

This chapter gathered all the relevant important fundamental knowledge and information which are very crucial for this study. This chapter attempted to provide a basic idea of the banking industry in Bangladesh and banking in general. This chapter also demonstrated the difference between traditional and modern banking and the way banking has changed significantly in the recent past. This helped to identify the needs and importance of having updated and modern training and development programme for bank employees. Various theory was used in this chapter to identify the weaknesses and to provide recommendations on how to increase or develop the programme as well as how to motivate the employees. This chapter also helped to answer two research questions and directed the study to formulate guidelines for effective training and development programme for BB.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The main purpose of this chapter is to introduce the research methodology for this study. This chapter is extremely vital for the success of this study as it defines which approach will this research study be taking. This chapter provides a clear idea about the research philosophy in general. This chapter also indicates the research design, data collection method, research population, sampling method, sample size, data analysis, reliability and validity. This chapter discusses about survey design, data measurement and data strategy. This chapter also provide clear justification for any chosen research method.

3.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy plays vital role in research as it defines the path on which the whole research methodology is based. Research philosophies are the primary thing to be chosen in order to select research designs, strategies and methods to conduct a research. There are 4 types of philosophies which are widely used in research that are positivism, realism, interpretivism and pragmatism. In positivisms, there is no human involvement in constructing new views and facts as it purely depends on the factual data instead of constructivism through human involvement in the research and assess their beliefs as well as perceptions. The sources of positivism philosophy can be books, journals, articles, all kind of secondary sources and it supports testing hypothesis which is deductive in nature. Positivism philosophy makes the outcome of thesis reliable for future referencing by other authors. The outcome, based on positivism philosophy cannot be challenged in terms of theories, models and justifications that authors give to defend their research outcomes. Indeed, such outcomes could be used in new research for improvements in previous research outcomes. Such outcome could be the formulation of new guideline, recommendations, action plan, new model, or new theory.

Realism philosophy gives high importance to human beliefs and perceptions instead of existing facts. In realism, researchers do research in accordance with the realities and beliefs of recipients through observations and experiments. Realism is inductive in nature and those inductive results are based on personal beliefs of recipients which exist at the time of conducting the research that could be experiments and observations. Realism supports formation of new knowledge that could be challenged. This philosophy is ideal in medical

research in which the responses of recipients keep importance and consider in the main research while developing the conclusion. There are some limitations of this philosophy that includes time factor as well as situational factor. Such limitations compel researchers to not to choose this philosophy in business related research as such factors dominates the responses of recipients which needs to be critically analysed rather than to be considered as it is. (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017)

Interpretivism is similar to positivism that supports inductive as well as deductive in which researchers interpret the outcome of interviewers. During interviews, hidden facts and reasons are revealed which help in the conclusion of research which could be deductive (hypothesis) or inductive (new knowledge but based on existing literature). Interpretivism only provides logical reasoning and justifications which could be new, but we cannot consider it as a new knowledge as we do in realism philosophies. In addition, pragmatism philosophy supports interview method whereas survey is supported by positivism philosophy which could be used to perform hypothesis test or to gather primary data, related to existing literature. This philosophy is ideal to induce new knowledge by analysing the responses of recipients through interviews or experiments. This philosophy enhances the critical evaluation skills of the researcher and develop new research skills which are helpful in finding the solution of any sort of problems.

This research is basically based on pragmatism philosophy which refers to positivism and interpretivism. Both philosophies were chosen to perform this research in which the survey is related to positivism and interviews are related to interpretivism. Positivism philosophy helped in gathering secondary sources and designing the questionnaire as well as the interview questions. Interpretivism philosophy was chosen in accordance with interview method whereas positivism was chosen to support the research outcome and make the research outcome reliable. The major reason behind choosing of this philosophy is to make the outcome strong enough for future reference as the outcome will be based on quantitative as well as qualitative. Pragmatism philosophy is useful when there is an element of responsibility is involved in studies. The outcome based on pragmatism philosophy cannot be challenged and can be sued as complete referencing source by other researchers or users. Indeed, the researchers which are based on positivism also cannot be challenged but the outcome could not be used by users with confidence.

Therefore, positivism philosophy is the core philosophy for the research outcome as well as it supports survey method. Interpretivism philosophy is supportive philosophy to get the primary data from interviews to read the mind of recipients which helped the author in revealing hidden

facts and personal opinions of recipients which cannot be expressed in terms of survey questions. Positivism philosophy supports the guideline as the secondary qualitative data is already acknowledged like relevant studies regarding the chosen 19 areas in this research. This philosophy also assisted the author in developing the grounds in literature review section as the outcome of this thesis is completely new by nature, so no supporting or authentic data was available on internet which was directly related to the new guideline.

The author gathered the relevant data in pieces according to the identified 12 areas and banking industry in Bangladesh which helped the author to form the new guideline for BB. This guideline can be used by any bank in Bangladesh and also as a role model by other banks in other countries. This philosophy was chosen with intention to enhance the credibility of the outcome and of course responsibility was also the primary element as the whole research is on Central BB.

3.2 Research designs

Research design tells the procedure to collect the data which can be primary and secondary. Research design should be chosen in accordance with the objectives of the research as the wrong selection may jeopardize the credibility of research.

3.2.1 Exploratory design

Exploratory design helps researchers in gathering secondary data and also in testing hypothesis which is deductive in nature. This design helps researchers in performing of inductive as well as deductive research in which they test theories and gather all useful information which is reliable and acknowledged. Exploratory design is the primary design of positivism philosophy and makes the research outcome reliable which is based on existing literature. This design was chosen when the researcher has low level of knowledge regarding the chosen topic. This research design is used in gathering secondary data which is already available on internet or any physical form like books, journals, official reports, newspaper, and other record forms. This design is used to reveal hidden facts, figures, incidents, and previous studies.

In this study, this design was chosen to collect secondary data in accordance with positivism philosophy which is the core philosophy for this study. The interview questions and the survey questions are based on exploratory design. This design helped the author to study the existing manual of central BB which helped the author in identifying non-technical and non-financial areas of training and development programs of BB. This design helped in exploring the facts and developing incremental as well as innovative changes in existing guideline of BB. Those changes can be considered as a new guideline of training and development (primary aim).

3.2.2 Survey design

Survey design is a sub design of descriptive research design which is used to gather quantitative data. The other art of descriptive research design is longitudinal design in which existing research reports are used to analyse the facts and figures. This design is useful to gather primary data for hypothesis purpose and also for informational analysis. This design helps in gathering quantifiable data which enhance the information of the author and help in identifying the findings. Such findings can be used in the outcome. Such findings could be informative or hypothetical result. The survey design was selected to gather quantitative data to perform frequency distribution SPSS which helped in the formulation of new guideline for BB. (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017)

3.2.3 Case study design

This design is useful in gathering specific information and drawing a solution which is specifically related to the actual issues. This design gives in depth insights into the issues and keep the focus of researchers on specific path during research. The case of BB was selected as a case study for this study in which issues were identified and other relevant information was aggregated. In addition, in depth analysis of training and development programs of Bangladesh helped in identifying non-financial and non-technical business areas. The following are the identified areas which are the primary areas, covered in the outcome with innovative as well as incremental changes.

Research methodology How important is the practical application of research methodology studies through case study approach? Is it important to add other important evaluation tools in general research methodology?	CSR of BB Is it important to teach strategic management skills long with CSR course?
Advance course on Leadership	Management Information System MIS

<p>Is it important to teach leadership courses through case study approach?</p> <p>How important is to add practical application of evaluation tools and techniques with advance leadership theoretical course?</p>	<p>Is it important to teach all advanced software and technologies in MIS course practically?</p>
<p>Public private partnership</p> <p>Are strategies related to managing resistances of employees important in managing cultural difference course?</p> <p>Is it important to teach managing change course with real examples?</p>	<p>Prevention of fraud and forgery in banks</p> <p>How important is IT audit skills to prevent fraud and forgery in banks?</p>
<p>Core risk management</p> <p>Is it important to teach physical security as part of core risk management?</p> <p>How important is to integrate internal compliance with operational risk management?</p>	<p>FDI and portfolio investment in Bangladesh</p> <p>Is it important to include entrepreneurship course in portfolio investment program?</p>
<p>Training course on ERP</p> <p>How important is the expertise of utilization of business intelligence for ERP users?</p>	<p>HRM and development</p> <p>Is it important to teach reward management in detail along with HRM course?</p>

How important is the expertise of utilization of business intelligence for ERP users?	
Strategic planning and management	Manner and etiquette Is motivation of employees important to deliver quality service to customers and to perform well? Is it important for senior managers to evaluate the behaviour and performances of employees?

3.3 Research Approach

Research approach defines the primary path of the research. Research approach reflects the outcome this study and there are two types of approaches that are inductive approach and deductive approach. This thesis is purely inductive by nature in which the new formulation of the guideline is completely new and contributes to existing relevant studies. Deductive strategy used to test theories or models through hypothesis test. The outcome of this study is based on new research and no hypothesis was chosen for this study which eliminated the option of deductive approach. The outcome of this study is flexible and based on personal study as well as critical evaluation of the problems in this study.

Inductive strategy helped to draw a solution which is in the form of new guideline of training and development of BB which is based on existing literature and primary information. The outcome of this thesis is based on pragmatism philosophy and on in-depth analysis which increased the confidence level of the researcher and enhanced personal learning. Inductive strategy was chosen to draw a solution, based on logical reasoning after detailed analysis of the aggregated data.

3.4 Data Strategy

Research strategy plays vital role in collecting the data as strategy defines the complexities of the data collection for researchers. Qualitative strategy is used to get existing relevant secondary knowledge through case studies as well as previous research. Qualitative is also used to get primary knowledge through interviews. Quantitative strategy is used to get quantifiable data for hypothesis and other SPSS methods like frequency distribution method. Quantitative

data is gathered through surveys and through longitudinal research design in which the data is extracted from official research reports. In this study both strategies were selected in which case study design and interviews are qualitative in nature whereas survey design (subcategory of descriptive design) is related quantitative strategy. No hypothesis was selected but the survey data was used to do frequency distribution test which helped the author in the formulation of a new guideline. The gathered data through the survey was measured to assess the effectiveness and importance of specific area in banking industry as a part of training and development process

3.5 Data collection

The outcome of the thesis is based on secondary and primary data in which secondary data was obtained through relevant journals, articles, books and the manual of training and development of BB. The primary data was obtained through interviews and survey method in Bangladesh. The following are the links of the survey.

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/TP2QMJQ>

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/MWCYVZC>

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/XK6VL59>

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/62SRYFX>

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/K5BHF3W3>

3.6 Data Measurement

There is no hypothesis test in this research, but Likert scale was used to gather quantitative data through questionnaire. The SPSS method named as frequency distribution method was used in the analysis of quantitative data. The Likert scale is based on ranges from 1 to 5 which shows the degree of importance of particular question. The recipients replied through that likert Scale and their responses was transferred on Microsoft excel for frequency distribution analysis. The main requirement was to analyse the degree of importance of identified 12 areas (case study design) related to training and development which helped in the formulation of new guideline.

The primary data was extremely important, gathered from different people who are employed in different banks as those banks are following the guideline of BB. It was necessary to gather data from the employees of those banks as critical information is codified in their brains which can be obtained only through questionnaire method. The obtained critical information helped in the formulation of a new guideline. The following is the example of data measurement.

Training and Development areas of BB	Very important	Important	neutral	not important	extremely unimportant
Question 1	1	2	3	4	5

3.7 Research Population

Research population was chosen differently for interview method and survey method. For interviews, the recipients belonged to BB and currently they are working on senior positions. There was no age restriction, department restriction and gender restriction as the targeted population was cross sectional but knowledge workers. Those targeted population knows about the training and development program of BB. BB has 10 offices in different cities and only the targeted population works in Chittagong office. It was feasible for me to reach the office of BB in Chittagong after facing failure in Khulna during the pilot project. The total population is 3981 in ten offices in which 450 are working in Chittagong office (BB, 2018). Only 40 was selected as a total population due to the accessibility issues and interest issues of recipients. The targeted recipients belonged to the social network of the author's cousin which helped the author to access 40 employees. The sample size was 36 in which 38 recipients were interviewed. Among 38, only 36 interviews were considered fully completed and included in the data analysis.

In the survey, the population was targeted through purposive sampling and snowball sampling. In purposive sampling, only particular group of people was targeted who possessed expert knowledge regarding training and development programs. Moreover, personal network was contacted in Bangladesh to reach maximum number of employees who works in different banks. In snowball sampling, the interested recipients requested other knowledge workers of banks which helped in covering large population. The research population of the survey was selected according to the accessibility issues in Bangladesh that was 200. The sample size has

been achieved which is 131 and only 155 recipients has been targeted within allotted timeframe for collecting the survey data.

3.8 Sampling Method

For this study, different sampling methods were chosen for the interviews and the survey. For interview method, convenience sampling method was chosen in which only available and interested employees were targeted through personal contact (mentioned above). For survey method, purposive sampling was used to target knowledge workers, working in different banks and snowball sampling was chosen to reach maximum number of employees with ease in which recipients forward the survey links to relevant people in their social network. The interview questions were designed in accordance with the gathered literature. The survey questions were also designed in accordance with literature whereas survey monkey website was utilized to design the whole survey. In order to reach maximum number of employees in different bank, personal social network of the author in Bangladesh helped. The online link was provided which created ease for the recipients in filling the questionnaire.

3.9 Sample Size

According to the given formula of sampling, the calculation of sampling size is given below:

$$\text{Sample Size} = (Z\text{-score})^2 * \text{Standard deviation} * (1\text{-StdDev}) / (\text{margin of error})^2$$

Where, Z score for 95 % confidence level is 1.96 when deviation is 0.5

Confidence Level	Margin of Error	Calculated value according confidence level, margin of error and standard deviation	Population size	Calculation of sample size for the survey
95%	5%	384	200	$384 * 200 / 384 + 200 - 1 =$ $76800 / 583 = 131$ Sample size
This is widely used for normal range of population	This is widely used for normal range of population	This value is driven value through original formula		

Confidence level	Margin of error	Calculated value according confidence level, margin of error and standard deviation	Population size	Calculation of sample size for the interviews
95% This is widely used for normal	5% This is widely used for normal	384 This value is driven value through original	40	$384 * 40 / 384 + 40 - 1 = 15360 / 423 = 36$ is the sampling size.
range of population	range of population	formula		

3.10 Data Analysis

The literature covered all relevant existing previous studies regarding the identified 12 areas of training and development programs of BB. In fact, each area was studied in accordance with the innovative changes and incremental changes in existing actual training and development program of BB. Moreover, the literature also includes all the processes, steps of implementation, important factors and practical knowledge of using the identified areas. For instance, in the Environmental risk management which refers to green environment, all the relevant journals were analysed about the practices and implementation process of green environment. It helped in the comparison of the actual training and development program of Bangladesh with the existing gathered literature which revealed additional things. Those identified things could be added in a new guideline to make the actual training and development programs more effective.

The literature also includes fundamentals of banking field and advanced knowledge which revealed paramount factors and requirement of specific skills to perform specific task in banking field. That relevant literature to banking field helped in incremental and innovative changes in training and development program of BB. The aggregated literature was critically analysed which helped in the formulation of a new guideline and research questions for the interviews as well as for the survey. The primary data was obtained through the interviews and the survey which were analysed and compared with the gathered literature which assisted in the formulation of a new guideline (Primary Aim).

The purpose of performing the interviews and the survey was to analyse the effectiveness of the actual training and development programs of BB and importance of identified 12 areas (mentioned above) in the training and development process in banking industry. The targeted

knowledge workers in the collection of primary data are working in different banks including BB. Those knowledge workers know the requirements of specific skills to perform daily task by managerial and operational staff. Their responses were analysed to do require changes in the programs of BB as their responses revealed the facts about the training and development program of BB which helped during the formulation of a new guideline

The primary data obtained from the survey was analysed on Microsoft Excel through frequency distribution method. That SPSS method is useful in identifying the most important factor or variable through frequency of responses. In frequency SPSS method, the option on likert scale which was rated above 30 %, considered in the data analysis whereas all the rated options, below 30 % were excluded.

3.11 Pilot Project

The pilot project was done in Bangladesh to check the feasibility of the sampling method and data measurement plan. The pilot project also helped in assessing time requirement to access and take interviews. The pilot project was done in Khulna which was failed in fact. During the pilot project, the author tried to access recipients through convenience sampling technique during office hours without using any personal contact. As a consequence, majority of the recipients refused to give interviews. The total population for the pilot project was 10 in which the sample size was 9 according to the sample size formula when the confidence level was 95 %. The author failed in achieving the sampling size in Khulna which compelled the author to use personal contacts in Dhaka to achieve the actual sample size for the research.

3.12 Validity and Reliability

The secondary data was collected through relevant journals, business articles and official reports of BB which makes the critical evaluation of secondary data, valid and reliable. The research questions of the survey and the interviews were based on relevant accumulated literature which makes the result of the survey and the interviews, reliable as well as valid. The selected philosophies for this study make this thesis valid as well as reliable. Moreover, valid in the sense that the primary data was obtained from knowledge workers whereas reliable in the sense that the research questions were designed from the gathered literature by following exploratory design method. Exploratory design is qualitative in nature which supports existing relevant studies which are already acknowledged in academic field like SWOT model (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

3.13 Ethical issues

3.13.1 Confidentiality and Anonymity

The positions and name of the recipients were kept confidential by giving them specific coding on interviewed papers whereas their identities and obtained information were not mentioned in the gathered data. Their anonymity was kept by closing off the tracking IP addresses option on survey monkey website during the conduction of the survey. In addition, all the gathered data from the survey and the interviews were destroyed after transferring the data into Microsoft excel.

3.13.2 Access issues

Several access issues were experienced during this research. The first issue came during the collection of secondary data which is comprised of relevant journals as they were not easily available on internet. So, after some intense research, the relevant journals and articles were obtained through different libraries. Moreover, no access issue came in searching for the actual manual of training and development programs of BB as it is easily available on its website. Furthermore, the major issue came during the pilot project in which majority of the recipients in Khulna office of BB refused to participate in this study. In fact, the pilot project was failed so in order to achieve the objective of taking interviews, the author used personal contacts in Chittagong office. No access issue was experienced during the whole session of interviews of knowledge workers of BB in Dhaka. At last, no access issue came in accessing the recipients for conducting the survey as the distribution was done through snowball sampling in which personal contacts assisted.

3.13.3 Autonomy

The recipients for conducting the interviews could skip any question if they don't want to answer. The recipients of the survey could perform the survey conveniently according to their busy schedule, but they were not allowed to skip the questions.

3.14 Limitation

There is an involvement of biased data in this thesis which was obtained through survey and interview methods. The detail of the programs of training and development manual of BB is general and authentic so there is no limitation is involved in the collection of secondary data. The obtained program list is basically designed by BB for all the banks in Bangladesh which imposed limitation on its scope. Even, due to this limitation, it can be used as a benchmark by other banks in different countries.

3.15 Knowledge Contribution and Managerial contribution

There is no pinpoint research has been done on this topic so this research will contribute in existing literature relevant to the identified 12 areas in training and development programs of BB. This research in fact, investigated each identified area in depth by studying the relevant models, theories, implementation steps and factors which could enhance the knowledge of readers and provide convenience to readers to study all of them at one place. For instance, readers could get all the necessary information regarding HRM and leadership at one place. The outcome is based on pragmatism philosophy which covers positivism as well as interpretivism philosophy so the outcome can be used with confidence by users.

The managerial contribution of this study is exclusive as the formulated guidelines in this research can be used by BB to bring improvements in its training and development programs. As the guideline covers all important information regarding the identified non-technical as well non-financial areas of the actual manual of BB which is not only helpful for BB in bringing improvements in its program but also enhance the knowledge of readers specifically to the 12 identified areas. It can also be used by other banks in different countries to use it as a benchmark. The managerial contribution also includes the usefulness of the guideline for educational as well as professional institution to use it as a guideline in designing the courses related to the identified 12 areas.

3.16 Summary of Research Methodology

This chapter successfully achieved its main aim of outlining the research method used in this study to answer the research questions. This chapter discussed the research procedure, data strategy, data collection, participants and interview questions outlined the details of how this research study was conducted and who has participated in the study. This thesis is purely inductive by nature which helped the researcher to formulate completely new guidelines and contributes in existing relevant studies. A mixture of both qualitative and quantitative data was used to successfully collect the data for this study. Convenience and purposive sampling were used for data sampling. The primary data was obtained through the interviews and the survey which were analysed and compared with the gathered literature which assisted in the formulation of a new guideline which is the primary aim of this research study. The purpose of performing the interviews and the survey was to analyse the effectiveness of the actual training and development programs of BB and importance of identified 12 areas in the training and development process in banking industry which will be discussed in the next chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Introduction

The main goal of this chapter is to provide the study outcomes and demonstrate that the methodology described in the previous chapter was followed. This chapter is based on the analysis and findings of primary research and secondary research which gives direction to this thesis. The researcher used the findings to conclude and to formulate the guideline which is the main aim of this research. The primary data was collected through various means in which majority data was collected directly from the officials who are working on senior positions in different banks in Bangladesh [see *Appendix 2 to 6*]. The professional website named as LinkedIn was also used to approach knowledge workers [see *Appendix 7*]. The questionnaire and actual training programs of BB were sent via email to knowledge workers [see *Appendix 8*] who works on senior positions [see *Appendix 1*] in BB used their personal contacts to get the questionnaire filled online. The interviews of knowledge workers [see *Appendix 10*] were also analysed. During the interviews, 22 out of 38 said that the training programs of BB are not effective whereas 16 talked in the favour. Fortunately, the sample size for interviews was achieved and 36 interviews were considered. The researcher excluded uncompleted interviews and considers data of completed interviews along with survey result.

The sample size for survey was achieved successfully and all the questions in the survey are considered for the analysis. The original snaps of survey monkey are adhered in the following analysis, on which the survey was designed so the recipients can fill with ease anytime and anywhere. The recipients started filling the survey in April and required number of responses was achieved in Sep 2019 as shown in the figure 14. The followings are the detail analyses of each question of the survey and gathered literature on all 12 non-technical programs of BB.

Figure 15: Response volume month wise; Source: Survey monkey

4.1 Analysis of all non-technical and non-financial programs

4.1.1 Prevention of fraud and forgery in banks

BB has designed forgery and fraud related course in terms of forgery in banks and ignore fraud. Fraud is considered as internal theft by employees in terms of finance as well as operational. Indeed, Security risk in e banking, credit card details, Mobile banking and internet banking are in the interest of consumers, but we cannot ignore internal fraud which is not in the interest of banks. There is need to add training regarding fraud like techniques to prevent, policies and measures which make IT system secure at banks. In fact, every department feels safe in terms of internal theft including administrative controls like fraud in attendance matters by manipulating the attendance system.

How important are IT audit skills to prevent fraud and forgery in banks?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 16: IT Audit skills; Source: Survey Monkey

Majority rated Audit skills important to prevent fraud and forgery in bank whereas majority believes that the current program of BB is ineffective as shown in the figure 16. There is need to revise the program by adding training programs related to IT which includes measures, techniques and methods. The current program is not good enough to make the employees expert to prevent fraud as the current program is focused on forgery but indeed, for forgery, IT expertise is required. The current program is just focused on e-banking and other online banking security whereas if the system is weak from inside, forgery could be happened as well as fraud. In fact, fraud leads to forgery attempts.

Is this course effective enough to teach necessary skills to prevent fraud in banks as compared to risk management course?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 17: Prevent fraud program; Source: Survey monkey

4.1.2 FDI and Portfolio Investment in Bangladesh

Majority rated entrepreneurship course important for investment program of BB which is not included in the course. Majority also rated innovation skills important for portfolio investment in Bangladesh. Entrepreneurship is not a single line definition and innovation skills cannot be learned quickly as it requires in-depth training and knowledge which must be included in the current course.

Is it important to include entrepreneurship course in portfolio investment program?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 18: Entrepreneurship; Source: Survey Monkey

BB covers regarding FDI only which is not enough as in reality, inward FDI has been investing in Bangladesh for a long time and those inward FDI have already business plans. There is need to train bank's employees to give business plans to inward FDI. The course was designed in accordance to the service provider as BB provide services to inward FDI like debt. This course is focused on the provision of quality service to those inward FDI's like reporting skills. This course must revise by adding entrepreneurship and innovation areas that enhance the skills of employees so banks could also do partnership business with inward FDI with confidence. When we talk about entrepreneurship, innovation is a crucial part of this areas and MVIS is an advanced approach related to innovation. In fact, MVIS is being debated nowadays to use it as a tool or method to learn innovation. MVIS is a detail process in fact that teaches how to do innovation.

How effective is innovation skills training along with portfolio investment program?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 19: Innovation skills; Source: Survey Monkey

14.1.3 Human Resource Management and Development

Majority recipients gave high priority to reward management as shown in the figure 19 and confirmed that the program of HRM of BB is not effective. We are not taking minority in the analysis as reward management is not a part of the current course so may be in fact, the program is not effective as majority rated reward management as important area for development whereas on another handful of them also said that the current program is effective.

So, here we are considering reward management as an important area and it should be included in the course. Reward management is comprised of several things that must be taught in the course and related methods as well as techniques must be taught in depth in the revised training program. HRM course seems dynamic that covers necessary things, but they are in general. Indeed, all the areas in this course are necessary for employees regardless of sector but several things are missing that should not be. This course is more focused on team building and communication skills but without teaching reward management, communication among employees could not be developed.

Is it important to teach reward management in detail along with HRM course?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 20: Reward management; Source: Survey Monkey

HRM course must include reward management refers to managing the appropriate approaches, methods, and reward practices to attract potential competitors and inspire agents to avoid problems related to the staff turnover. This course must also include training on the formulation of reward strategies and practices which are based on business drivers. The course must also include reward intelligence as a part of reward management. It is practiced for a particular recognition of the pay level or the explicit position. It also helps in the development of a compensation plan for the payment and the evaluation of capacity payments in the future will depend on the needs of the workforce. In reward management course, total reward approach is a significant part which requires practical training to give sound knowledge to get the most out of this approach. In fact, practical knowledge must be included in this course as theoretical understanding could not give clear understanding to the employees.

How effective is HRM course of Central Bangladesh bank?

Answered: 155

Skipped: 0

Figure 21: HRM program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

Furthermore, reward management principles must be taught along with other approaches otherwise the employees would not be able to fully utilise the potential of reward management. Indeed, principles are the guideline to stay on the right track at the time of practicing reward management. Implementation of reward management is also significant part of reward management which must be taught as a separate part of this course. The course must include the roles of line managers which teaches them about necessary tools and measures like balance score card and psychological contracts to implement reward management successfully.

4.1.4 Integrity and Anticorruption

Compliance important was rated as highly important for the integrity and corruption course but in actual it is not included in the course. Compliance is not a single method but a broad area which is comprised of several perspectives that should be taught in the course. The detailed list is discussed in the conclusion chapter. Most of the recipients believes that the current course is not effective and should be revised in order to train employees properly to fight against corruption.

This course of BB seems effective in all direction as it covers all the areas which are relevant to compliance system. This course talks about transparency and accountability along with all the measures, strategies and policies that could help employees in banking field to prevent corruption. One thing should be included in this course that is BPR. Business process reengineering is one of the core areas of compliance which act as an engine or source of operational activities. In every department, a specific duty like HR duty is to hire is based on a specific process to conduct proper hiring.

Is compliance department essential to deal with corruption at workplace ?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 22: Compliance; Source: Survey Monkey

Corruption in business processes jeopardizes the whole performances of companies including all departments. Employees do corruption in processes due to several reasons like incapability to perform well or lack of core knowledge regarding their duties, to facilitates someone and due to lack of interest and time-consuming duties. Business process reengineering is not a strategic option or approach but a detailed strategic topic to control corruption. Business process engineering is a fundamental duty of compliance department and no international standard of business law emphasis on is conduction of business process engineering but its

healthy practice to control over business process corruption which doesn't only result in financial loss but also affect the performances.

How effective is integrity and anti corruption course of Central Bangladesh Bank?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 23: Anticorruption program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.5 Strategic Planning and Management

Most of the recipients rated strategic models and tools essential for strategic planning course which are not included in the program, designed by BB. Majority recipients also rated value management approach essential which is not a new concept in strategic management. In fact, the current course of BB is believed to be ineffective in terms of course contents. Strategic management cannot be learned without becoming expert in the use of strategic models and tools. There are several models as well as tools and all of them should be added in the course.

How important is to learn all strategic models and tools for strategist?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 24: Strategic Models and tools; Source: Survey Monkey

If we look at strategic planning course, BB has designed the course in broad sense without focusing on fundamental. This course is highly focused on analysis which comes in soft skills and strategist need fundamental as well as advanced knowledge of tools and techniques to do better analysis. If we consider business analysis and business strategy course, then employees must know the use of strategic tools and techniques. There is need to add all the 3 essential pillars named as implementation pillar, managing resistance pillar and evaluation pillar. Every pillar is comprised of tools, theories and techniques which are essential to be known by senior managers. Furthermore, formulation of strategies is also a detail process which is comprised of several factors, steps and techniques. The following is the analysis of strategic planning and management which covers all essential information which must be known by senior manager in banking field. There should be a detail course on strategic culture which develop skills in employees to assess the strategic culture and change according to the needs. The course designed by BB named as business strategy includes overall strategies which are more focused on business development rather than change management i.e. strategic culture. Formulation of policies, strategies and techniques to control over employee's behaviour must be included in the course. The course must include types of culture as in banking field, there are several types of culture and senior management should be skilled to manage all of them. The course must include solving case studies which develop contextual intelligence in employees. Moreover,

types of strategies must be taught in strategic planning course as appropriate as well as effective strategies must be made to get better output.

To what extent this is important for employees to become expert in value management besides strategic planning and management?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 25: Value Management; Source: Survey Monkey

Furthermore, decision makers must have analytical skills to make incremental strategies and in order to do so, using of analytical models and tools is necessary for decision makers in organisations. Senior managers must be skilled enough to choose appropriate leadership style and develop such policies which promote organisational culture instead of destabilizing the existing one. The course must also include different techniques and methods like survey, one to one interview, assessing employee's feedback through informal events and cultural audit to assess the culture before making such strategies.

How effective is strategic planning and management course of central Bangladesh bank to make employees experts?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 1

Figure 26: Strategic program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

Cultural audit must be included in strategic culture course as it is a detailed process in which analytical models are helpful and 4 perspectives are considered while doing cultural audit. Such perspectives include competitive situation, business strategy, organisational structure as well as culture and leadership styles. It is mandatory for decision makers to understand the cultural audit process to keep it balanced. Besides all, strategic models, and analytical tools along with their right usage are significant to be taught in strategic planning course. Strategic planning must also include course of strategic theories named as prescriptive, descriptive, emergent, complexity, adsorptive, knowledge management, Resource based view and transaction cost which gives understanding to the employees in the formation of strategies.

As we know that, due to globalisation, business has become complex and difficult for companies to survive in intense competition especially in international market. Globalization affected all sectors regardless of size and nature of business including banking sector. Such effects are related to several perspectives including money exchange, customer's demands, customer's preferences, supplier power, market opportunities and threats and technological advancements. In fact, without strategic stance, no company or bank can survive even run smoothly. There are several phenomena's that are considered by organisations regardless of sector to create value for customers and business.

The value for business comes by cost efficiency and value for customers comes by quality product or service by utilizing available resources and capabilities. So, value management must be taught along with strategic planning that gives clear understanding to the employees to use the right phenomena which could work better to achieve the desired objectives.

4.1.6 Training Course on ERP

Utilisation of business intelligence was rated almost equally by the recipient as shown in figure 23. Practical application of ERP was rated as highly important. The current course is focused on general concepts and ignored business intelligence. There are several things that come under business intelligence like cleaning of the data and converting information into actionable knowledge. The rating regarding effectiveness of ERP program, designed by BB is not being considered due to equal number of ratings as half said it was effective and half of them said it was not effective. Here, the most important is to consider high ratings regarding business intelligence as it was rated as highly important by the recipients.

How important is the expertise of utilization of business intelligence for ERP users?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 27: Business Intelligence; Source: Survey Monkey

ERP is software and the course, designed by BB is primarily focused on familiarisation and implementation instead of utilization in various ways to get the most of it. BB's course covers

payroll and marketing module only whereas ERP is used for several departments including collecting business intelligence. In fact, in marketing business intelligence play pivotal role in bringing effectiveness in marketing related decision making. ERP gives control over business matters like organisational management, event management if any, training management and personal administration which are covered in BB's course.

How important is to teach ERP practically to employees?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 28: ERP practical application; Source: Survey Monkey

The course also covers billing area and small area of supply chain management that is purchasing. This course includes business intelligence gathering, using and cleaning of the data. In fact, companies need information to make effective decision whether they are related to organisational management or event management. ERP gives static information which is raw by nature and can be used as it is like in purchasing matters, fulfilling event's requirements and provide control over employee's lunch to administration.

Is training course on ERP of central Bangladesh effective for practical purpose?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 29: ERP program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

In order to get the best of the collected information is to use it as business intelligence which requires skills of converting information into actionable knowledge. BB should include the training on business intelligence. The spreading of this information at all levels within organisation is necessary to get desired outcomes. Without knowledge sharing, no company can be successful. This knowledge sharing through technology refers to explicit knowledge. This knowledge management depends on information management and timely processing raw data into understandable format so everyone within organisations can utilize this available data efficiently. Business intelligence is divided into three major areas which must be taught separately in depth in the new course. Data cleaning is a primary step in gaining business intelligence which is normally done by technical staff that restricts the potential of gathered information. Non-technical staff must be well trained to extract valuable information from the gathered data as per need then refine to achieve valuable knowledge. Indeed, non-technical staff has to rely on their own research rather than on technical staff which has limited view over different business areas like financial, marketing, material and HR.

4.1.7 Manner and Etiquette

In the course of manner, motivation of employees and evaluation of employee’s behaviour by senior managers were given high recommended status by the recipients. The current program was also rated effective as shown in the figure 29, so we can take this in another way by considering motivation of employees and evaluation techniques to evaluate employee’s behaviour as additions the course which will make the current course more effective. Indeed, according to the recipients the current course is effective enough to teach manners so we cannot ignore such ratings as the recipients were expert in banking field. According to the researcher, this course seems short as it doesn’t cover motivation which is extremely important for businesses regardless of the sector. Motivated employees are key assets for any company and only satisfied employees perform in professional manner and please customers.

Is motivation of employees important to deliver quality service to customers and to perform well?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 30: Motivation of employees; Source: Survey Monkey

This course must be revised in order to make it effective. Manners and Etiquettes can be taught but cannot be forced as satisfaction of employees pay significant role in compelling employees to treat customers mannerly. Motivation is remarkable for the commitment of the employee and this is achieved by external as well as intrinsic elements. This course must include all the motivational theories to give clear understanding to senior management to keep the lower staff motivated.

Is it important for senior managers to evaluate the behavior and performances of employees?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 31: Evaluation of behaviours; Source: Survey Monkey

Is course of manner and etiquette of Central Bangladesh bank effective?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 32: Manner program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.8 Core Risk Management

Physical security and internal compliance were considered important for banks' employees. Majority were agreed that the current program of BB is ineffective as shown in the figure 32 and it should be revised. The current course seems effective as it covers almost all the important areas that have been discussed in literature review but practically practical application of compliance like IT audit training and business process reengineering audit are not included in the current course. If we see at physical security, it is a part of compliance system. This course can be used in delivering complete knowledge regarding compliance.

Is it important to teach physical security as a part of core risk management?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 33: Physical security; Source: Survey Monkey

How important is to integrate internal compliance with operational risk management?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 34: Internal compliance; Source: Survey Monkey

Compliance plays vital role in dealing with such negligence and corruption by doing audit time to time. Audit is not only related to financial matters but there are several types of non-financial audits like IT audit and business process reengineering audit. This course needs to be revised little bit by adding IT audit and business process reengineering audit along with other risk management areas. Business process reengineering audit refers to the improvements in business processes for betterment and to ensure efficiency in operational activities. BPR is practiced by line managers in every department in organisations and also specifically done by compliance department if there is any. BPR audit can be done by only those who have necessary knowledge to conduct as it requires specific skills to carryout for effective outcome. In order to conduct effective IT audit and BPR audit, procedure of conducting the audit must be known by a compliance manager. However, the current course is effective one to deliver quality knowledge regarding core risk management.

How effective is course on risk management of central Bangladesh Bank ?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 35: Core risk program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.9 Corporate Social Responsibility

This course seems effective as it is comprised of guidelines of environment risk management which covers all the measures regarding CSR. According to the recipients, strategic management skills are highly important for CSR course as shown in the figure 33 whereas half of the recipients said that the program of BB is effective whereas half of them said it is ineffective.

Is it important to teach strategic management skills long with CSR course?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 36: Strategic management skills; Source: Survey Monkey

This course also includes general discussion on CSR of banks which help in forming the base for those who are not familiar with CSR. The current course also includes green banking, but discussion is not good enough to practically train employees who would carry out CSR activities successfully. Strategic management skills must be injected in this course to make this course fully effective. Strategic management assists decision makers to formulate effective CSR strategies which are crucial to gain cost efficiency with great impact.

How effective is CSR course of central Bangladesh bank ?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 37: CSR program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.10 Research Methodology

The recipients endorsed that the importance of case study approach in research methodology course is undeniable and it adds value as it gives practical application of solving real issues through research methodology. The evaluation tools were also given importance by the recipients whereas the current program of BB was considered as ineffective by majority and effective by minority. Indeed, the current program is comprised of several important things, but we cannot negate that case study approach and evaluation tools must be taught along with other areas.

How important is the practical application of research methodology studies through case study approach ?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 38: Case study approach; Source: Survey Monkey

BB carefully designed the course that covers almost everything, but no practical application was discussed in the entire course. Practical application is another issue but indeed, this course covers all the necessary areas of research methodology. It covers techniques and analysis methods which are compulsory to do research on an issue. This course seems effective, but evaluation tools and case study approach are not included and they are extremely significant to give practical training. In fact, theoretical knowledge is not just enough to engender research methodology skill sin employees. Case study approach engenders problem solving skills and those cases are based on real issue of banks. Moreover, evaluation tools are related to strategic ones and in banking field, those tools are necessary to do the right analysis that is why they must be included in this course.

Is it important to add other important evaluation tools in general research methodology ?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 39: Evaluation tools; Source: Survey Monkey

Case study approach equips researchers to formulate practically possible and useful solutions as per the real problems. In research methodology, the selection of appropriate research methods, strategies and philosophies don't give desired outcome until the researcher use sophisticated analytical tools along with research methodology. Research proposal is a first step towards research in which research methodology is used whereas analytical part is advanced level to get the solution of the identified issues. In research proposal, researchers identify the issues and define the path to reach the conclusion whereas in analytical part, different evaluation tools help researchers to get the secondary data. In banking field, employees must know the relevant analytical tools to assess the situation of a bank.

It is also necessary to use the right analytical tool as per need which refers to contextual intelligence. In research methodology, literature review section is solely based on secondary data but when research is based on case studies, analytical tools are essential to get the relevant data.

Is the research methodology program of central Bangladesh bank effective ?

. Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 39: Research methodology program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.11 Advance course of Leadership

The recipients agreed that the current course is effective enough but indeed some areas are missing like case study approach and evaluation tools which were given importance by the recipients. Some of the courses are similar as mentioned in HRM courses like team building and negotiation. Leadership course is based on general concept and focused on familiarisation rather than practical approach. Let suppose that the theories include Trait theory, but no practical application of trait theory is included in this course which makes this course highly ineffective and need to be revised. Leadership development, leaders must know all the types of leadership style and the techniques which are used to engender required traits in employees. Indeed, every employee could not be a transformational leader. There are some set of traits in each type of leadership style which are essential to be held by an individual.

Is it important to teach leadership courses through case study approach?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 1

Figure 40: Case study approach in leadership; Source: Survey Monkey

How important is to add practical application of evaluation tools and techniques with advance leadership theoretical course?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 41: Evaluation tools and techniques; Source: Survey Monkey

Characteristics can be identified through psychometric test and other techniques at the time of hiring by HR department and this is the first step on which the future of organisation and future leadership development is based. Effective leaders ensure future leadership development in organisations and groom managerial staff to act in the absence of a leader. This phase is repetitive and could be practiced by line managers to identifying the traits of managerial staff for future leadership development. Line managers must be equipped with required skills to use relevant models of trait theory to identify the traits in employees. Skills and capabilities are the second most important area in leadership which is related to professional development of line managers. It is not necessary that if a line manager acquires good leadership traits then he or she must have a skill to act as a leader. Hence, identifying the traits is the most important to identify the required skills as skills depend on the traits of an individual. The following are the methods that should be taught I the course that make the course effective.

1. Gordon Allport's 's 4000 traits theory (1897–1967):
2. Raymond Cattell 's Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (1905–1998)
3. Hans Eysenck's Three Dimensions of Personality (1916–1997)
4. The Five-Factor Theory of Personality (The Big Five / OCEAN)
5. Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI-2):
6. Myers-briggs Type Indicator:

Is advance course of leadership of central Bangladesh bank effective?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 42: Leadership program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

4.1.12 Public Private Partnership

Managing resistance of employees was given high importance as it comes indeed when two companies or banks started joint venture. Employee engagement was not given much importance because majority did not consider it at all which may be due to lack of knowledge or they were not sure that employee engagement could play role in public private partnerships. After all, the current program was rated ineffective by the majority and this is good enough to support the concept of employee engagement. The gathered literature supports the concept of employee engagement that how it helps bank in managing resistance as well as engage employees to develop peaceful working environment.

Are strategies related to managing resistances of employees important in managing cultural difference course?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 43: Managing resistances of employees; Source: Survey Monkey

Is it important to teach employee engagement course with real examples?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 44: Employee Engagement; Source: Survey Monkey

The current course includes all the areas which are relevant to operational activities as well as managerial to some extent like security management, Security Management, Risk Management, Acquisition and Development of Information Systems and Service Provider Management. Indeed, when bank merge with other banks, those areas must be managed in order for smooth operations, but we cannot deny the importance of employee engagement as employees are primary asset and role players in public private partnerships. In fact, employees carry out operational activities and if banks fail in managing their employees then public private partnership becomes unsuccessful. When organisations merge with other organisations or they do joint venture with other companies then it is obvious that resistance come from the employees that should be managed efficiently otherwise the initiative of starting new business or partnership fails. It is one of the primary skills of senior management and first step towards the initiative of setting up new partnership or acquisition. Mergers and joint ventures also merge cultures of different organisations which create cultural issues. So, managing resistances through detailed process is a first step to develop favourable working environment to practice other approaches like employee engagement. Managing cultural issues come in public private partnership like managing employee’s resistances and engagement of employees.

Is the course on public private partnership of central Bangladesh bank effective?

Answered: 155 Skipped: 0

Figure 45: Public private program of BB; Source: Survey Monkey

The new course must include all the types of employee engagement that are intellectual engagement, affective engagement and social engagement. It is necessary to train senior

manager regarding each EE type as each type has its own factors, process, methods and techniques which are practiced by senior managers to engage the workforce. Alignment of employee engagement practices must also be included in the course as this skill is necessary to avail the full potential of EE. This is important for senior management to train their employees if they are not to align different organisational elements to get the maximum of EE tools and techniques. Diagnostic tools are paramount areas in EE which includes general surveys, hybrid questionnaire, Utrecht EE scale, Gallup workplace audit, financial ROI, interview techniques and focus group method. EE is a lengthy course, but it is necessary to make public private partnerships.

4.1.13 Summary of Chapter Four

The goal of this chapter was to critically analyse the collected data which was gathered through survey questionnaire and interviews during the data collection process. This chapter has discussed the data collected through survey monkey (attached as figures). This chapter has critically analysed the 12 identified non-technical areas of BB's training and development programme which will later help to provide recommendation and develop policy guidelines to enhance the training and development programme of the BB. The following chapter will be focusing on a case study of Citibank India, which is like the selected topic and can be helpful in identifying effective solutions for the study.

CHAPTER FIVE: CASE STUDY

5.1 Background of the Case

The case is highly effective to understand the need of training and development programs at banks. This case is based on Citibank of India, written by Dr Poornima Luthra and Adina Wong at the Singapore Management University. This case was developed with the help of Singapore Human Capital Leadership Institute (HCLI). HCLI is an independent national institute spearheaded by the Singapore's Ministry of Manpower and Economic Development Board, with the Singapore Management University as a strategic partner. The case starts from Citibank conference on leadership and development in which Sarah Roberts, Head of Citigroup Asia Pacific, and Anuranjita Kumar, Chief Human Resource Officer (CHRO) of Citigroup South Asia discussed the need of leadership nurturing for banking sector. They discussed the ways that helps in nurturing future leaders as it was proven that Citibank has nurtured several leaders in past but now there is need to bring improvements in the ways. Sarah and Kumar interviewed experienced Citibank employees and experienced leaders who have been working with Citibank for last 20 years and some have worked with different banks in past. They mentioned that culture play vital role in shaping leaders as they worked in performance driven culture where every employee strived hard for betterment of the bank. This case advocates the role of culture in shaping leaders. Citibank hires directly from local best business schools as it believes on talent hunt and give high priority to talented workforce.

According to the interviewees, the hired young ones were eager to perform well and are also willing to enhance their skills through international working exposures. Citibank's official admitted that the culture promoted knowledge sharing environment where employees learn from each other through formal and informal meetings. Cross functional teams were also encouraged. The interviewed persons admitted that strong mentors are required for employees so they could deal with their personal weaknesses and issues even those employees interact with each other but still mentorship is necessary. There is a huge difference between the era of 80's and modern era which has made essential for all banks to keep their training and development up to date and bring improvements were necessary by time to time.

5.2 Identified Weaknesses

1. Citigroup believes on stretching employee's talent and revealed hidden weaknesses and strength by putting extra load of work to evaluate the individual's potential.

2. Job rotation is compulsory which creates issues for employees as every individual is not adaptive. Job rotation on frequent basis brings issues as cultural difference play vital role in making things worse if the differences are not managed properly. It also creates issues for employees individually as sometimes an individual doesn't feel comfort in new working environment where communication issues come as a first issue which bring discomfort in the employees.
3. Job rotation in terms of business is wise is also practices in Citi group in which every skilled individual is posted in different areas by time to time as a management trainee which requires leadership qualities otherwise average person could not be able to perform well in all areas where he or she is posted.
4. Citigroup was used to hire from top business schools in India which shows that majority employees in Citigroup was hired on school basis rather than intelligence basis. One interviewee told that Citigroup claim that it is university of leadership who believes on hiring the right candidate but from top businesses schools. If it is really a university of leadership then hiring from top business school seems opposite to what it claims.
5. Training programs only belongs to line of business aspects only like operations, technology and consume banking. Citigroup doesn't provide training programs like fraud and forgery and compliance training.
6. Citigroup forcedly implement job rotation approach in which every individual must be worked under the supervision of two senior managers in two different cities within a period of two years after joining. This seems irrational approach as very individual must be evaluated first according to the assigned task during their rotation period as every individual could not perform in every department. Citigroup must assess the degree of expertise, skills and knowledge before assigning the task and must not rotate less capable employees until they become skilled.
7. In Citigroup, training programs for employees are managed by line managers. Such programs must be managed by expert HR officials.
8. People, who join Citigroup from the middle, face issues of cultural changes, complex working environment and policies like job rotation even they are provided support from the senior management.
9. Citigroup has no such program that motivates employees to strive hard bring improvement in their skills and the knowledge.

10. Citigroup only practice performance management process twice in a year in which employees must attend the sessions with their direct supervisors.

5.3 Case Brief

This case was designed with the help of ex and current employees of Citigroup who have worked at higher positions in Citi Bank [see **Appendix 11**]. The interviewees shared some facts of Citigroup which are valuable and reflect a change in the current training and development programs of Citi group. One interviewee revealed that Citigroup believes on stretching employee's talent and revealed hidden weaknesses and strength by putting extra load of work to evaluate the individual's potential. The amount of load varies between to 20 to 40 percent of actual work. Citigroup provides support if it needed but after putting pressure on individuals to evaluate their tolerance and expertise level.

One interviewee said they multi-cultural issue comes in Citigroup as people from different countries also work in India as a part of job rotation which bring cultural issues. According to Head of Strategy and Chief Administrative Officer, Franchise Risk and Strategy, Citigroup said that Performance driven approach is used in which employees are evaluated by time to time to give them promotion or bonuses according to their performances. Teamwork is encouraged and workload is common in Citi group when employees are required to work in night shifts but teamwork approach is used rather than putting load on individuals.

One interviewee said that Citigroup believes on job rotation and exposure as they send its employees abroad in international branches to provide them opportunities to learn new skills. It also rotates employees in India to aid other employees in terms of new skills and expertise. One interviewee said that Citigroup operates in complex market in India where diversification, incremental changes in existing products and introducing new products are essential for survival. Citigroup believes on entrepreneur approach and to active this purpose, Citigroup encourage creativity in employees to think beyond average to bring innovativeness in the banking products.

Head of Operations and Technology (And), Citibank South Asia, pointed out that Indians in Citigroup are more willing to go abroad for international exposure and for saving purpose as due to currency differences, Indian employees want to save money. The Management Associate (MA) programme that Citibank India had instituted in the late 80's and the early 90's, Citigroup was used to hire from top business schools in India which shows that majority employees in Citigroup was hired on school basis rather than intelligence basis.

Citigroup practices leadership program for senior management only to polish their skills whereas management trainee program is separate for new joiners which is based on business aspect only. New induction program is practiced at country level whereas leadership program is practiced at international level. Citigroup designed only one induction program, for all regardless of the country whereas leadership program was designed in accordance with a leadership aspect for all nationalities who are rotated as a part of their job country wise. Citigroup gives high priority to training and development of employees and even in bad financial situations Citi group keeps the budget for training and development programs high. Citigroup uses three E approach which refers to exposure, experience, and education. The first two E develops skills and leadership qualities in the employees whereas education refers to the ways of learning like on job training session, off the job training, workshops, and seminars. Citigroup only practice performance management process twice in a year in which employees must attend the sessions with their direct supervisors.

Citigroup forcedly implement job rotation approach in which every individual must be worked under the supervision of two senior managers in two different cities within a period of two years after joining. In Citigroup, training programs for employees are managed by line managers. People, who join Citi group from the middle, face issues of cultural changes, complex working environment and policies like job rotation. One of the interviewees said that Citigroup could only design program and encourage the employees, but it cannot force anyone to become skilled as it solely depends so the will of the employee which comes when they realize the need of becoming expert for their own interest like career development. Citigroup has no such program that motivates employees to strive hard bring improvement in their skills and the knowledge. It is concluded that change has been realised by few interviewees as an important thing to be done immediately in Citigroup regarding training and development aspects. Citigroup brought change in management trainee programs in which now employees must go through operations and technology aspects instead of 2 years (Citibank, 2020).

5.4 Practicing Theories by Citigroup (Training development)

According to Simons and Roberson (2003) in **Soft** HR theory **and Hard** HR theory, Hard theory treated employees as a worker only and control through strict policies. Soft theory treated employees as an asset and believe on teamwork. Citigroup is practicing soft model no

doubt but still there are some flaws like Citigroup put pressure on employees by engaging them in assignments in their first 2 years of employment and put pressure more than their capabilities to test their limits. Citigroup must put pressure after giving them required training through developed training programs. According to Shah et al (2003) Human relation theory strongly believes on strong relation with employees and gives high priority to the workforce to avoid retention issues. Citigroup is practicing Human relation theory as it believes on retention of employees and develop strong relation no doubt through rewarding system including growth chances within organisation based on their performances. Citigroup practices job rotation policies to promote knowledge sharing environment where employees learn new skills. According to Jackson (2003) system theory believes that to bring efficiency in the working environment and to achieve desired goals, strict policies are essential to control the employee. Citigroup is also controlling employees along with the soft theory as mentioned above which seems a flaw or we can say application of two different theories at a time. Citigroup is also practicing Japanese school of thought by giving growth opportunities to its employees to avoid retention issues which seems rational approach no doubt but still there is a space for more improvement by following Behavioural school of thought in relation with the developed training and development programs. According to Thompson et al. (2006) Behavioural school of thought believes on the behaviour of employees which may change by time to time and successful implementation of designed strategies can only be possible by manipulating the behaviour of employees. As mentioned above under the heading of identified problems, Citigroup has no such program to motivate them to strive hard to learn new skills.

5.5 Models and Theories (Literature review)

1. Resource based approach: This model believes that workforce is a valuable asset to gain competitive advantage among the pool of rivals and every individual must be treated as a valuable asset instead of focusing on particular level like senior management. Resources are of several types like physical resources, financial resources and workforce. Companies move in a new market due to those resources if they are not available in the current market or region.
2. Bureaucracy Weber's approach: This theory believes that employees must be given task or duty according to his or her capabilities as every individual cannot perform well in every department (Grant, 2002).

5.6 The matching model

Matching model is based on the belief that selection of the employees must be made in accordance with their capabilities and characteristics which have serious consequences on performances of the employees (See figure-46). Appraisal system identifies the hidden weaknesses in employees which must be rectify or strengthen their capabilities through development programs and keep them motivated through effective reward management which directly impacts on the performances of employees. Appraisal system also helps to identify that what essential things motivate the employees then companies can bring improvements in their strategies and policies. It is necessary to give task to employees according to their skills and capabilities to get expected desired performances (Grant, 2002).

Figure 46: Matching model

Source: Formulated by the author, adapted from (Grant, 2002).

5.7 Harvard HR model

HR policies must be designed in accordance with the stakeholder's interest which could be any like investors, employees, suppliers, and society. There are many situational factors which have directly impact on overall consequences of designed strategies and stakeholder's interest. Situational factors may include law, employees' characteristics, current market and competitor's strategies. HRM officials must design even reward system and development programs in accordance with the situational factors like market's requirement and law to make workforce competitive enough to deliver quality service.

The Harvard Framework

Figure 47: Harvard HRM framework

Source: Source: Formulated by the author, adapted from (Grant, 2002).

5.8 Benchmarking model

Benchmarking is a detailed process based on few steps that help companies to stay competitive among the rivals in which companies do compare its processes, strategies, and policies with the companies of the same sector. Benchmarking model is useful in bring improvements in the current strategies, policies and processes which keep companies up to date (Ramabadron et al., 1997).

Figure 48: Benchmarking model

Source: Adapted from (Ramabadron et al., 1997).

5.9 Hofstede's cultural model

1. Power distance index: High power distance index refers to the bureaucracy leadership style where employees must show high respect to high ranks and authority whereas low power distance index refers to decentralized decision-making structure where every employee has some powers and authority.
2. Individualism versus collectivism: Individualism refers to the personal goals and personal interest of employees whereas collectivism refers to teamwork and well-being of the group instead of individualism.

Figure 49: Hofstede's cultural model

Source: Adapted from (Hofstede et al., 2010).

3. Uncertainty Avoidance Index: High uncertainty refers to low tolerance for uncertainty and strict rules are used to control thing whereas in low uncertainty refers to high tolerance is exercised which promotes risk taking environment.
4. Masculinity versus Femininity: Masculinity refers to traditional approach of handling matters in companies through strict rules, focus on achievement and treat employees as a resource to achieve the outcome whereas in femininity, companies focus on nurturing and treat employees as valuable assets.
5. Long term orientation versus short term orientation: Long term focus on future and believe on long term success whereas short term focuses on quick results (Hofstede et al., 2010).

5.10 Solutions for the identified weaknesses

Citigroup is practicing soft model no doubt but still there are some flaws like Citigroup put pressure on employees by engaging them in assignments in their first 2 years of employment and also put pressure more than their capabilities to test their limits. Citigroup must put pressure after giving them required training through developed training programs. Bureaucracy Weber's approach must be exercised by Citigroup by assigning assignments according to their capabilities instead of putting every individual in every department. Indeed, every individual has its own capability and skills which could be polished but should not be put forcedly in

every department during the period of two years. If we see in matching model, selection must be made before assessing the capabilities of employees and suitable training programs must be provided to the needy ones after appraisal of the employee's performances. Citigroup is practicing Human relation theory as it believes on retention of employees and develop strong relation no doubt through rewarding system including growth chances within organisation based on their performances. Citigroup must give equal opportunity to all employees as per the case brief, Citigroup design separate training programs for senior management and low-level staff. Citigroup gives two years training to low level staff for the first two periods but only related to operational and technology matters. Low level staff are the ones who directly interacts with customers and are involved in day-to-day operations so at least they must be given compliance training, forgery training, Integrity and Anticorruption training and research methodology training. Those programs would create great impact on the performances of employees at low level and it is the right of them when Citigroup claim that it believes on human relation school aspect. Citigroup practices job rotation approach to promote knowledge sharing in which it sends the employees to other branches under the supervision of different bosses and every individual must work under two different bosses. Citigroup must give Manner and etiquette training before rotating. Citigroup is also practicing Japanese school of thought by giving growth opportunities to its employees to avoid retention issues but behavioural school of thought in relation with the developed training and development programs must be exercised. Citigroup must develop a separate motivation program in which career counselling and showing the positive direction to the employees towards their goals.

Job rotation is compulsory which creates issues for employees as every individual is not adaptive. Job rotation on frequent basis brings issues as cultural difference play vital role in making things worse if the differences are not managed properly. It also creates issues for employees individually as sometimes an individual doesn't feel comfort in new working environment where communication issues come as a first issue which bring discomfort in the employees. Citigroup must provide training to lower staff regarding communication, Manner and etiquette and ERP training as it would bring confidence in lower staff when they become knowledge workers so they could adjust in competitive environment especially in international job rotation period.

Citigroup was used to hire from top business schools in India which shows that majority employees in Citigroup was hired on school basis rather than intelligence basis. One

interviewee told that Citigroup claim that it is university of leadership who believes on hiring the right candidate but from top businesses schools. If it is really a university of leadership then hiring from top business school seems opposite to what it claims actually. Citigroup could hire potential candidates and provide leadership training to them later along with other courses like research methodology training and strategic planning training. It is not necessary that an individual who pass out from top business school possess the same potential and capabilities as possess by other average individual who pass out for ordinary university.

In Citigroup, training programs for employees are managed by line managers. Such programs must be managed by expert HR officials. If Citigroup wants to manage through line managers, then line managers must be given adequate HRM training through effective HRM training and development programs. Harvard HRM model and resource-based approach must be considered by Citigroup by providing advanced training courses to low level employees as well along with the senior management as it would create long term impacts on overall working environment of Citigroup. Indeed, the most common issue is cultural issue and in order to avoid cultural issues, every employee must be trained enough to adjust in any environment whether it is local that is India or international exposure.

5.11 Recommendations

In Hofstede cultural model, Citigroup must change its short-term orientation into long term orientation and collectivism into individualism. Citigroup doesn't give importance to advanced training programs for lower staff as it uses separate program for senior management whereas only operational and technology related training is given to lower staff. Citigroup is more focused on teamwork and doesn't give importance to individualism which must be changed. In Citigroup, employees are employed in different departments and attend bi sessions with the current supervisor. Citigroup must focus on individualism and HR officials must conduct counselling sessions instead of supervisors to assess their skills and weaknesses then design or give necessary training where he or she lacks behind.

5.12 Action plan

Benchmarking must be exercised in which Citigroup must go through benchmarking with similar banks regardless of country and collect the data of them in order to analyse their current training and development programs. Citigroup can benchmark with BB and can use the proposed guideline, formulated for BB.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above analysis, it has been concluded that some of the programs are completely ineffective as per survey and some are effective but still, they could be better by adding the proposed areas, given in the guideline below. Only some of the non-technical programs were considered in order to keep the research narrow and focused. The following are the analyses on the achievement of the objectives of this research.

6.1 Objective 1:

Objective 1 has successfully been achieved by analysing some of the current non-technical programs of BB and by collecting useful literature on the identified 12 non-technical areas. The researcher experienced no issue in accessing the secondary sources to collect the literature as in general, the sources on the identified 12 non-technical areas are available in the form of journals, books and relevant business articles. The researcher covered all necessary areas of each of the identified 12 programs by assessing their importance and benefit for banking field. Indeed, the literature on their importance and benefits justify themselves that if they are not included in the current programs of BB and such programs need to be revised to become effective to pour useful knowledge into employees. The finding also showed that in many questions regarding the effectiveness of the programs of BB, many recipients accept the effectiveness of few programs but still they also agreed that many things are also important which are not included in the current programs.

6.2 Objective 2:

The objective has also been achieved successfully as per the predesigned sample size but still the limitation of total population opens door for further research. The survey confirms that few of the identified on technical programs of BB are effective where rest of them are ineffective. The survey was carefully designed according to the identified literature which helped the researcher to confirm the importance of gathered literature through expert's opinions. In future research, the questions could be changed or enhanced as per the identified non-technical areas as there are several non-technical areas which were chosen to keep the research narrow and focused. Sample factor is a limitation in the survey as limited sample was chosen due to time as well accessibility issues.

6.3 Objective 3:

This objective or we can say the primary aim has successfully been achieved as per the requirements. The findings of the analysis above show that few of the non-technical areas are effective but still they need improvements in terms of addition in the current course. This objective is based on inductive approach in which the designed guideline is new and induced from the secondary as well as the primary data. The guideline could be used by banks in any country including BB to bring improvements in their training programs. Indeed, the future of banks depends on skilled employees and training session occur heavy cost to the banks. In case of ineffective training programs, banks bear loss of money and loss of time. The recipients confirmed that all of the business areas as mentioned in the survey are important and those areas are not included in the current programs of BB. The researcher designed the guideline according to those areas which are already discussed in the literature.

The guideline is comprised of important perspectives of each business area (identified 12 areas/programs) which must be studied through relevant sources by banks in future at the time of induction of the proposed guideline in the current programs of BB.

6.3.1 Policy Recommendations and Guidelines

The main objective of this thesis was to provide guidelines and policy recommendations for BB's training and development program so that it can be improved. Guidelines and policy recommendations for the 12 identified areas of BB's training and development program has been discussed below:

6.3.1.1 Guidelines to Prevent Fraud and Forgery in Banks

Lack of effective techniques to prevent fraud and forgery is a concern for BB. It is very important to add proper training which can help the bank to prevent fraud and measures which make IT system secure at banks. In fact, every department feels safe in terms of internal theft including administrative controls like fraud in attendance matters by manipulating the attendance system. In depth analysis of IT related operations is very important. Employees must be aware about IT related issues and compliance matters which help in keeping check and balance over IT official.

Banks must train front line staff like cashiers, chief accountant, and operation manager to monitor transactions on daily basis at the time to closure. Indeed, keeping an eye help in identifying frauds and suspicious activities before it is looked down by compliance or external audit later. Indeed, external audit impose penalties upon negligence. Monitoring transaction is

not just checking the activities, but it is a skill which requires practice and awareness about the necessary things to be looked during the monitoring. Special session must be done to create awareness among the trainees regarding frauds and forgery types. This is most beneficial type which gives information only which could be utilized in other areas like whistle blowing programs.

Whistle blowing is a significant program to prevent fraud and forgery in banks. Whistle blowing program is for all shareholders including customers, investors, and vendors to keep informed the higher management regarding any fraudulent activity related to banks. Whistle blowing is not just a program but a significant part of banking sector which must be implemented properly. Implementation is based on reporting procedures, keeping privacy of reporters and execution efficiently after getting complaints. It all requires training and high intellectual level of executors or we can say relevant officials. This is normally carried out by compliance department, but it is not necessary.

Employees should be trained how to analyse data and store confidential information securely. Teaching critical security controls like inspection of involved department who uses IT services, input and output controls, process and interface controls can be vital. Teaching IT components is very essential and non-technical staffs must be taught regarding IT components. Employees should be trained how to create and analyse IT audit report. It can be done by compliance but reporting in a piece from every department could be beneficial where banks have several branches. There should be a procedure for lodging and handling complaints and maintaining strict confidentiality. Developing process maps that helps the auditor to understand the flow of information and IT services. Finally, bank must take disciplinary actions against deliberate false complaints.

6.3.1.2 Guidelines for FDI and Portfolio Investment in Bangladesh

Entrepreneurship is not a single line definition and innovation skills cannot be learned quickly as it requires in-depth training and knowledge which must be included in the current course. BB covers regarding FDI only which is not enough as in reality, inward FDI has been investing in Bangladesh for a long time and those inward FDI have already business plans. There is need to train bank's employees to give business plans to inward FDI. This course is focused on the provision of quality service to those inward FDIs like reporting skills. This course must be

revised by adding entrepreneurship and innovation areas that enhance the skills of employees so banks could also do partnership business with inward FDI with confidence.

Guidelines:

Include Minimum Viable Innovation system and its related all steps/ MVIS approach in the training course. It is a modern approach of innovation topic. Banks do several businesses besides providing banking services to their customers like investing in foreign exchange, do joint venture with local and international companies. Training program must include entrepreneurship basics training and teach the employees different types, factors, determinants and market research skills. Focus on developing effective business and marketing plan. Provide training on blue ocean approach which helps to do innovation in a systematic way which is comprised on several essential steps and techniques.

6.3.1.3 Human Resource Management and Development

Reward management is comprised of several things that must be taught in the course and related methods as well as techniques must be taught in depth in the revised training program. HRM course seems dynamic that covers necessary things, but they are in general. Indeed, all the areas in this course are necessary for employees regardless of sector but several things are missing that should not be. The current course is more focused on team building and communication skills but without teaching reward management, communication among employees could not be developed.

Guidelines:

Different theories like VROOM theory, Balanced Score Card, making psychological contracts, using trait theory models like Myers briggs, developing self-assessment reports on employees can be included in the training course. This will help the employees understand the course better and apply in practice. Teaching fundamentals of reward management and reward intelligence gathering methods: survey, job alters market online research, benchmarking with rivals can be beneficial. Developing total reward approach: In reward management course, total reward approach is a significant part which requires practical training to give sound knowledge to get the most out of this approach. In fact, practical knowledge must be included in this course as theoretical understanding could not give clear understanding to the employees.

Reward management principles must be taught along with other approaches otherwise the employees would not be able to fully utilize the potential of reward management. Indeed, principles are the guideline to stay on the right track at the time of practicing reward management.

Implementation of reward management is also significant part of reward management which must be taught as a separate part of this course. The course must include the roles of line managers which teaches them about necessary tools and measures. The implementation steps analyse the internal as well as external factors, aligning all stakeholder's technique, survey methods for assessing company's requirement, developing technical reward report. Teach business drivers regarding reward management

Teach retention strategies through case study method by covering rivals' retention strategies and effective retention strategies by most renowned companies like Uni lever. It is necessary to cover companies other than banks as retention strategies could be applicable regardless of the sector. Developing retention plan according to the employee's motivations as motivation level is different of every employee so developing a plan carefully cold help in retention issues in banks.

HR official must be taught about training types and delivering methods so they could better develop training programs for other employees. Such programs are routinely training and depend on the need to do so. In every department, changes occur like change in technology requires training program which must be developed efficiently so the employees become familiar with the new technology.

Personality assessment tools must be taught as they are very significant in recruitment and selection process. Employees must practise the tools as theoretical knowledge is not good enough. Labour laws of Bangladesh must be included in the training programs as HR official must be aware if latest labour laws so they act accordingly as strategies or policies which goes against the laws would be challenged. HR officials must be trained enough to handle ERP related HR functions as ERP is complex software which requires training to be practised confidently.

6.3.1.4 Integrity and Anticorruption

This course of BB seems effective in all direction as it covers all the areas which are relevant to compliance system. This course includes transparency and accountability along with all the

measures, strategies and policies that could be helpful in banking field to be used as anti-corruption. One thing should be included in this course that is BPR.

Guideline:

Teach code of conducts of banks: This refers to ethics training through seminars which doesn't not only make employees aware but also strengthen the prevention of corruption. Indeed, when employees are aware, they could better report corruption but also monitor each other's activities in relation with unethical practices. Operational procedures of banks can be included in the course so the employees would be able to identify any unethical act by any official.

Teach usage of KPI: This issued to keep check and balance over the activities within banks and their outcomes as per the defined key performance indicators which identify the weaknesses or negligence of employees in their duties. Corruption doesn't not only belong to financial matter but negligence in the duties is also referred to non-financial corruption.

Business process reengineering is one of the core areas of compliance which act as an engine or source of operational activities. In every department, a specific duty like HR duty is to hire is based on a specific process to conduct proper hiring. Business process reengineering is comprised of several steps, techniques and methods. Business process engineering is a fundamental duty of compliance department and no international standard of business law emphasis on is conduction of business process engineering but its healthy practice to control over business process corruption which doesn't only result in financial loss but also affect bank's performances.

6.3.1.5 Strategic Planning and Management

In fact, the current course of BB is believed to be ineffective in terms of course contents. There are several models as well as tools and all of them should be added in the course. If we look at strategic planning course, BB designed the course in broad sense without focusing on fundamental.

This course is highly focused don analysis which comes in soft skills and strategist need fundamental as well as advanced knowledge of tools and techniques to do better analysis. If we consider business analysis and business strategy course, then employees must know the use of strategic tools and techniques. The course designed by BB named as business strategy includes overall strategies which are more focused on business development rather than change management i.e. strategic culture.

Guidelines:

Cultural audit technique: Cultural audit must be included in strategic culture course as it is a detailed process in which analytical models are helpful and 4 perspectives are considered while doing cultural audit. Such perspectives include competitive situation, business strategy, organisational structure as well as culture and leadership styles. It is mandatory for decision makers to understand the cultural audit process to keep it balanced.

Analytical phase: The analysis of strategic planning and management which covers all essential information which must be known by senior manager in banking field. There should be a detail course on strategic culture which develop skills in employees to assess the strategic culture and change according to the needs.

Theoretical knowledge: Strategic planning must also include course of strategic theories named as prescriptive, descriptive, emergent, complexity, adsorptive, knowledge management, Resource based view and transaction cost which gives understanding to the employees in the formation of strategies.

Formulation of policies, strategies and techniques to control over employee's behaviour must be included in the course. The course must include types of culture as in banking field, there are several types of culture and senior management should be skilled to manage all of them. The course must include solving case studies which develop contextual intelligence in employees. Moreover, types of strategies must be taught in strategic planning course as appropriate as well as effective strategies must be made to get better output.

There are 3 essential pillars named as implementation pillar, managing resistance pillar and evaluation pillar. Every pillar is comprised of tools, theories and techniques which are essential to be known by senior managers. All pillars must be included in the current training and development programs. The current program of BB does not cover those pillars but gives general idea. Furthermore, formulation of strategies is also a detail process which is comprised of several factors, steps, and techniques.

Formulating a Strategy: This area is completely depending on practical approach through case studies as it would be useless if banks keep it simple and give general overview which is actually the case in BB's strategic management program. Formulating strategy is to make or thinks that what the requirements to achieve a specific Goal are and it only comes when program covers practical training through case studies. It is essential to include practical part because it must be kept in mind that experts are required to carry out the matters of strategy formulation in banks.

Implement your strategy: This is second most essential part which also required practical training and must be included in the current BB's strategic program. In this case, three

strategies should be implemented to implement the strategy. The program must cover Elicitation part in which we discover the system Requirements, planning, non-functional requirements, document analysis and the prototyping. This is the most important step to implement a strategy within an organisation. In this step, we have to learn about the new environment in which a new strategy is going to be implement. We use usage critic strategy and the product critic strategy. Secondly, training to organise the gathered data into meaningful and useful format so they cud be easily extracted upon need. Specification deals with the representing and storing the collecting requirement data in a persistent a well-organised fashion. Validation is also an essential part of implementing strategy which tells us the use correct set of data now you are able to implement the strategy according to the requirements. It gives us the green signal about the new strategy to be launched.

Decision making is crucial in organisation, but it is not necessary that very decision gives positive outcome as it is the skill of decision maker to make appropriate and efficient decision. Strategic training program must provide opportunity to apply the knowledge on real situations of banks through case study approach. Every trainee must be given real case study to solve at home after taking training class.

Incremental type strategies must be included in the Strategic training program. Incremental type strategies are made as per the market changes which cerate gaps and engender new requirements like innovations. Incremental strategies give desired outcome when they are designed by analysing the past or using benchmarking technique in which senior managers compare the strategies of rivals and their results. Incremental strategies have significant impact on overall organisations, so such strategies are designed after taking all stakeholders in confidence. Furthermore, decision makers must have analytical skills to make incremental strategies and to do so, using of analytical models and tools is necessary for decision makers in organisations.

Cultural audit refers to the analysis of the culture before making any decision to change it. Culture in organisation play vital role in making companies successful and unsuccessful on long run and it must be audited by time to time as per needs. Cultural audit is a detailed process in which analytical models are helpful and 4 perspectives are considered while doing cultural audit. Such perspectives include competitive situation, business strategy, organisational structure as well as culture and leadership styles. It is mandatory for decision makers to understand the cultural audit process to keep it balanced. In fact, imbalanced culture doesn't give desired outcome and deteriorate the whole process of organisations which eventually liquidate organisations.

According to Prescriptive Theory, the Strategic training program must include prescribed guideline which was designed in previous years to deal with specific issues. Those guidelines strategies in fact which must be taught to the trainees. The guideline is based on the situations which re handled through prescribed solutions, designed by senior management in organisations. This theory believes that things or strategies must be defined clearly before any situation occurs so management can respond instantly as per prescribed guideline. In strategic management, this theory is followed to avoid delays in decision making and control subordinate decision making at crucial stages by giving them clear guidance. This theory is opposed for many reasons which include ignorance of unexpected events, negate requirement of skilled employees to make effective decision and avoid risk taking by employees which suppress their confidence. Hence, this theory is important in daily decision-making process and advocate the requirement of training of problem-solving skills among senior management who are responsible to develop pre-define solutions

The Strategic training program must include informative session in which secondary sources would be provided like strategies and actions of rivals in specific situations, impact of different factors and journals which provide reliable as well as valid knowledge. Descriptive theory is similar to prescription in the sense that senior management use this theory to develop solutions but in descriptive manner by explaining each factor separately and also take help by analysing the past incidents. The formulated solutions according to this theory cover multiple dimensions of single issue by covering all impacting factors. This theory advocates the need of problem solving plus research methodology skills for senior management to analyse the problem first before applying any solution.

The Strategic training program must include complex related issues of companies regardless of sector as banks is also a profitable organisation similar to other companies and all go through some similar issues. This theory supports unusual events and continuous change management in order to make effective decision rather than sticking to on course of actions like descriptive and perspective. This theory is used by those organisations that operate in complex environment where market is not stable. This theory is used rarely by organisations but studied as one of the core theories of strategic management. Organisations use scenario-based approach to train employees which develop skills to deal with unusual events and make them capable at least to make efficient as well as effective decisions.

The Strategic training program must include bench marking approach in which the trainees would be given assignments to collect the data regarding rival's strategies and actions which develop a sense to change the current strategies upon need. This theory refers to unusual events

but in the matter of factors instead do situations. This theory believes that management should be skilled enough to mould or alter strategies as per need by analysing the impact of different factors at the time of occurrence rather than relying on predefined solutions like in descriptive theory. It is fact that sometimes factors behave in different way due to other factors in different situations which makes complex for senior managers to predefine the strategy to deal with such factors according to past situational analysis. Complex situation is managed by such employees who are skilled in solving scenario-based problems.

The Strategic training program must include training in finding the market gaps and all the trainees must be given assignments to find the market gaps related to banking field. Innovation and seeking market gaps are essential to fulfil the new demands and needs of consumers. This theory refers to the capability of employees to identify the market gaps through intense market research and acquire new knowledge which enhance overall business growth.

Training in knowledge management must be included in the Strategic training program which is linked with ERP to some extent as gathering the data is done through ERP but using the data is different matter. Knowledge management refers to the value adding in services and products through various means. Managing knowledge within organisation has become crucial for survival in harsh competition where things get changed frequently like changing in consumer's buying behaviour. Knowledge is further divided into two subgroup which are explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge is in written form like business intelligence which is utilized by all employees as per need in decision making.

Explicit knowledge is gathered through business software's and different strategies as well as practices which is useful for senior management in decision making. In fact, gathering business intelligence is a skill which is essential for management in organisation. Tacit knowledge is codified into employee's brain which is transferred through training and teaching. Employees have personal reservations in transferring their skills and knowledge into newcomers or unskilled employees, but it can manage tactically through effective strategies in which HR play vital role. The Strategic training program must include those events in which trainees interact with each other and learn from each other by asking question on their concerned issues.

As we know that, due to globalization, business has become complex and difficult for companies to survive in intense competition especially in international market. Globalization affected all sectors regardless of size and nature of business including banking sector. Such effects are related to several perspectives including money exchange, customer's demands, customer's preferences, supplier power, market opportunities and threats and technological advancements. In fact, without strategic stance, no company or bank can survive even run

smoothly. There are several phenomena's that are considered by organisations regardless of sector to create value for customers and business. The value for business comes by cost efficiency and value for customers comes by quality product or service by utilizing available resources and capabilities. So, value management must be taught along with strategic planning that gives clear understanding to the employees to use the right phenomena which could work better to achieve the desired objectives.

6.3.1.6 Training Course on ERP

Utilization of business intelligence was rated almost equally by the recipient as shown in figure 23. Practical application of ERP was rated as highly important. The current course is focused on general concepts and ignored business intelligence. There are several things comes under business intelligence like cleaning of the data and converting information into actionable knowledge. The rating regarding effectiveness of ERP program, designed by BB is not being considered due to equal number of ratings as half said in effective and half of them said effective. Here, the most important is to consider high ratings regarding business intelligence as it was rated as highly important by the recipients.

ERP is software and the course, designed by BB is primarily focused on familiarization and implementation instead of utilization in various ways to get the most of it. BB's course covers payroll and marketing module only whereas ERP is used for several departments including collecting business intelligence. In fact, in marketing business intelligence play pivotal role in bringing effectiveness in marketing related decision making. ERP gives control over business matters like organisational management, event management if any, training management and personal administration which are covered in BB's course.

The course also covers billing area and small area of supply chain management that is purchasing. This course includes business intelligence gathering, using and cleaning of the data. In fact, companies need information to make effective decision whether they are related to organisational management or event management. ERP gives static information which is raw by nature and can be used as it is like in purchasing matters, fulfilling event's requirements and provide control over employee's lunch to administration.

In order to get the best of the collected information is to use it as business intelligence which requires skills of converting information into actionable knowledge. BB should include the training on business intelligence. The spreading of this information at all levels within organisation is necessary to get desired outcomes. Without knowledge sharing, no company

can be successful. This knowledge sharing through technology refers to explicit knowledge. This knowledge management depends on information management and timely processing raw data into understandable format so everyone within organisations can utilise this available data efficiently. Business intelligence is divided into three major areas which must be taught separately in depth in the new course. Data cleaning is a primary step in gaining business intelligence which is normally done by technical staff that restricts the potential of gathered information. Non-technical staff must be well trained to extract valuable information from the gathered data as per need then refine to achieve valuable knowledge. Indeed, non-technical staff must rely on their own research rather than on technical staff which has limited view over different business areas like financial, marketing, material, and HR.

6.3.1.7 Manner and Etiquette

During manner, motivation of employees and evaluation of employee's behaviour by senior managers were given high recommended status by the recipients. The current program was also rated effective as shown in the figure 29, so we can take this in another way by considering motivation of employees and evaluation techniques to evaluate employee's behaviour as additions the course which will make the current course more effective. Indeed, according to the recipients the current course is effective enough to teach manners so we cannot ignore such ratings as the recipients were expert in banking field. According to the researcher, this course seems short as it doesn't cover motivation which is extremely important for businesses regardless of the sector. Motivated employees are key assets for any company and only satisfied employees perform in professional manner and please customers.

This course must be revised to make it effective. Manners and Etiquettes can be taught but cannot be forced as satisfaction of employees pay significant role in compelling employees to treat customers mannerly. Motivation is remarkable for the commitment of the employee and this is achieved by external as well as intrinsic elements. This course must include all the motivational theories to give clear understanding to senior management to keep the lower staff motivated.

6.3.1.8 Core Risk Management

Physical security and internal compliance were considered important for banks' employees. Majority were agreed that the current program of BB is ineffective as shown in the figure 32 and it should be revised. The current course seems effective as it covers almost all the important areas that have been discussed in literature review but practically practical application of

compliance like IT audit training and business process reengineering audit are not included in the current course. If we see at physical security, it is a part of compliance system. This course can be used in delivering complete knowledge regarding compliance.

Compliance plays vital role in dealing with such negligence and corruption by doing audit time to time. Audit is not only related to financial matters but there are several types of non-financial audits like IT audit and business process reengineering audit. This course needs to be revised little bit by adding IT audit and business process reengineering audit along with other risk management areas. Business process reengineering audit refers to the improvements in business processes for betterment and to ensure efficiency in operational activities. BPR is practiced by line managers in every department in organisations and also specifically done by compliance department if there is any. BPR audit can be done by only those who have necessary knowledge to conduct as it requires specific skills to carryout for effective outcome. In order to conduct effective IT audit and BPR audit, procedure of conducting the audit must be known by a compliance manager. However, the current course is effective one to deliver quality knowledge regarding core risk management.

6.3.1.9 Corporate Social Responsibility

This course seems effective as it is comprised of guidelines of environment risk management which covers all the measures regarding CSR. According to the recipients, strategic management skills are highly important for CSR course as shown in the figure 33 whereas half of the recipients said that the program of BB is effective whereas half of them said it is ineffective.

Guideline:

This course also includes general discussion on CSR of banks which help in forming the base for those who are not familiar with CSR. The current course also includes green banking, but discussion is not good enough to practically train employees who would carry out CSR activities successfully. Strategic management skills must be injected in this course to make this course fully effective. Strategic management assists decision makers to formulate effective CSR strategies which are crucial to gain cost efficiency with great impact.

Awareness of CSR must be created through seminars as a part of training and development as employees must be known the importance of CSR for banks as it brings stability for organisations.

Strategies must be taught regarding the society and the environment which create brand image in the society for banks. Banks must show that they are responsible organisation who care about citizens. Such strategies may include green environment strategies, charity works and health awareness programs. In banks, CSR is normally done at higher level, but branch managers could exercise CSR strategies

Banks must organise events and seminars in which different NGOs must be invited who are pressure group. CSR must be exercised in collaboration with NGOs who assist organisations like banks to practice effective CSR strategies.

Companies Act and other legal guidelines from the state must be the part of training and development programs so employees specially who are responsible to develop CSR strategies act accordingly. Training must be given to maximize the profit for the bank also to gain something like developing brand image. Training for quality customer service is necessary to practice effective CSR as customers is one of the shareholders which must be satisfied by organisations.

Training on philanthropist CSR must be included in the current training and development programs. It refers to charity work and work related to social welfare and wellbeing. This helps banks to get brand image and develop good image in the eyes of people that could drive sales as people connect themselves emotionally with a specific bank who is involved in charity works. Guideline of United Nations regarding CSR must be included in CSR training program of BBs which would guide bank's employees who are responsible to develop and exercise CSR during the formation of CSR strategies.

6.3.1.10 Research Methodology

The recipients endorsed that the importance of case study approach in research methodology course is undeniable and it add value as it gives practical application of solving real issues through research methodology. The evaluation tools were also given importance by the recipients whereas the current program of BB was considered as ineffective by majority and effective by minority. Indeed, the current program is comprised of several important things, but we cannot negate that case study approach and evaluation tools must be taught along with other areas.

BB carefully designed the course that covers almost everything, but no practical application was discussed in the entire course. Practical application is another issue but indeed, this course covers all the necessary areas of research methodology. It covers techniques and analysis methods which are compulsory to do research on an issue. This course seems effective, but

evaluation tools and case study approach are not included, and they are extremely significant to give practical training. In fact, theoretical knowledge is not just enough to engender research methodology skill sin employees. Case study approach engenders problem solving skills and those cases are based on real issue of banks. Moreover, evaluation tools are related to strategic ones and in banking field, those tools are necessary to do the right analysis that is why they must be included in this course.

Case study approach equips researchers to formulate practically possible and useful solutions as per the real problems. In research methodology, the selection of appropriate research methods, strategies and philosophies don't give desired outcome until the researcher use sophisticated analytical tools along with research methodology. Research proposal is a first step towards research in which research methodology is used whereas analytical part is advanced level to get the solution of the identified issues. In research proposal, researchers identify the issues and define the path to reach the conclusion whereas in analytical part, different evaluation tools help researchers to get the secondary data. In banking field, employees must know the relevant analytical tools to assess the situation of a bank. It is also necessary to use the right analytical tool as per need which refers to contextual intelligence. In research methodology, literature review section is solely based on secondary data but when researches are based on case studies, analytical tools are essential to get the relevant data.

6.3.1.11 Advance course of Leadership

The recipients agreed that the current course is effective enough but indeed some areas are missing like case study approach and evaluation tools which were given importance by the recipients. Some of the courses are similar as mentioned in HRM courses like team building and negotiation. Leadership course is based on general concept ad focused on familiarization rather than practical approach. Let suppose that the theories include Trait theory, but no practical application of trait theory is included in this course which makes this course highly ineffective and need to be revised. Leadership development, leaders must know all the types of leadership style and the techniques which are used to engender required traits in employees. Indeed, every employee could not be a transformational leader. There are some set of traits in each type of leadership style which are essential to be held by an individual.

Characteristics can be identified through psychometric test and other techniques at the time of hiring by HR department and this is the first step on which the future of organisation and future

leadership development is based. Effective leaders ensure future leadership development in organisations and groom managerial staff to act in the absence of a leader. This phase is repetitive and could be practiced by line managers to identifying the traits of managerial staff for future leadership development. Line managers must be equipped with required skills to use relevant models of trait theory to identify the traits in employees. Skills and capabilities are the second most important area in leadership which is related to professional development of line managers. It is not necessary that if a line manager acquires good leadership traits then he or she must have a skill to act as a leader. Hence, identifying the traits is the most important to identify the required skills as skills depend on the traits of an individual. The following are the methods that should be taught during the course which can make the course effective:

Gordon Allport's 's 4000 traits theory, Raymond Cattell 's Sixteen Personality Factor, Questionnaire, Hans Eysenck 's Three Dimensions of Personality, The Five-Factor Theory of Personality (The Big Five / OCEAN), Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI-2) and Myers-briggs Type Indicator.

6.3.1.12 Public Private Partnership

Managing resistance of employees was given high importance as it comes indeed when two companies or banks started joint venture. Employee engagement was not given much importance because majority did not consider it at all which may be due to lack of knowledge or they were not sure that employee engagement could play role in public private partnerships. After all, the current program was rated ineffective by the majority and this is good enough to support the concept of employee engagement. The gathered literature supports the concept of employee engagement that how it helps bank in managing resistance as well as engage employees to develop peaceful working environment.

The current course includes all the areas which are relevant to operational activities as well as managerial to some extent like security management, Security Management, Risk Management, Acquisition and Development of Information Systems and Service Provider Management. Indeed, when bank merge with other banks, those areas must be managed in order for smooth operations, but we cannot deny the importance of employee engagement as employees are primary asset and role players in public private partnerships. In fact, employees carry out operational activities and if banks fail in managing their employees then public

private partnership becomes unsuccessful. When organisations merge with other organisations or they do joint venture with other companies then it is obvious that resistance come from the employees that should be managed efficiently otherwise the initiative of starting new business or partnership fails. It is one of the primary skills of senior management and first step towards the initiative of setting up new partnership or acquisition. Mergers and joint ventures also merge cultures of different organisations which create cultural issues. So, managing resistances through detailed process is a first step to develop favourable working environment to practice other approaches like employee engagement. Managing cultural issues come in public private partnership like managing employee's resistances and engagement of employees.

The new course must include all the types of employee engagement that are intellectual engagement, affective engagement, and social engagement. It is necessary to train senior manager regarding each EE type as each type has its own factors, process, methods and techniques which are practiced by senior managers to engage the workforce. Alignment of employee engagement practices must also be included in the course as this skill is necessary to avail the full potential of EE. This is important for senior management to train their employees if they are not to align different organisational elements to get the maximum of EE tools and techniques. Diagnostic tools are paramount areas in EE which includes general surveys, hybrid questionnaire, Utrecht EE scale, Gallup workplace audit, financial ROI, interview techniques and focus group method. EE is a lengthy course, but it is necessary to make public private partnerships.

6.3.1.13 Further Research Recommendation

There is a significant gap on the selected topic as there were not enough research has been conducting. This study aimed to contribute to the body of knowledge by fulfilling this gap. This study has identified the main cause that affect the BB's training and development program. It has used many theories in practice to justify the effective training and development program especially for compliance regulations within the banking industry. This study has provided effective guidelines and policy recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of BB's training and development program which was the main objective of the study. This study also briefly discussed the benchmarking standard for effective training and development program for bank employees. It would have been ideal and appropriate to compare a good practice training and development program of a high standard central bank of a first world country i.e. Bank of England. However, due to lack of time and other limitations it has not been

possible to do so in the study. This can be recommended that a further research should be conducted to compare the training program of BB with a different central Bank from another country.

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Appendixes

Appendix 1: LinkedIn recipients

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original content is a screenshot of the LinkedIn website. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Appendix 2: Gmail proof of recipients

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Appendix 3: Gmail proof of recipients

28/09/2019

Gmail - Doctoral Survey

Figure redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original content is a screenshot of a Gmail email. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Appendix 4: Interviews

Personal details withheld. Original content is a photograph of completed interviews forms. Please contact the thesis author for further information.